

D8.1: Alternative near-zero pathways

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
CCN	Cooperation and Collaboration Network
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EGD	EU Green Deal
EP	European Parliament
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FSC	Food Supply Chain
FSFS	Framework for Sustainable Food Systems
FW	Food Waste
GA	Grant Agreement
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GD-SO	Green Deal Support Office
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
JRC	Joint Research Centre of the European Commission
MAGNET	Modular Applied General Equilibrium Tool
MS	Member State
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SFS	Sustainable Food Systems
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WFD	Waste Framework Directive
WPL	Work Package Lead

Executive summary

This report is the first deliverable (D8.1) from the ZeroW Policy Team (WP8). It addresses the urgent challenge of food waste (FW) within the EU. Aligned with the Farm-to-Fork Strategy and the EU Green Deal, the ZeroW project sets ambitious short-term, medium-term, and long-term objectives to significantly reduce per capita FW levels by 2030 and achieve near-zero waste by 2050. Recognizing the complexity of food systems, the report underscores the need for a systemic approach, considering diverse factors and variables throughout the supply chain.

The focus of the report is to draw an overview of the state-of-play of Food Loss and Waste (FLW) in the EU, or **trend pathway**. Stakeholder engagement processes, including interviews and working group meetings, have enriched the report with valuable insights from agrifood sector experts. These inputs contribute to the formulation of **three alternative pathways** for the future, each proposing distinctive approaches to FW reduction through changes in consumer behaviours, innovation, and policies.

While these alternative pathways are not forecasts, they serve as thought-provoking scenarios, stimulating dialogues within the agrifood research and innovation communities. These conversations will play a pivotal role in shaping the direction of some important workstreams of the projects, influencing modelling and simulation tasks, and contributing to future publications.

By presenting alternative pathways, the report sparks discussions that contribute to a 'just' transition towards near-zero food waste by 2050. Further future debates will be necessary to determine the most suitable 'just' transition pathway, considering environmental, social, and economic dimensions of sustainability, and incorporating new elements from the latest research papers.

1. Introduction

This chapter provides a high-level summary of the ZeroW project (section 1.1), as well as a mapping of ZeroW outputs within T8.1 of WP8 (section 1.2), an overview and structure of this report (section 1.3) and relations with other ZeroW deliverables (section 1.4). We end this chapter with a word about our geographical scope and considerations for this report (section 1.5).

1.1 ZeroW project summary

Figure 1 ZeroW at a glance

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2 ZeroW approach

To reach its goals ZeroW is divided into 11 WPs with different goals, tasks and deliverables.

1.2 Mapping ZeroW outputs

This report is the first deliverable of WP8 - *Policy recommendations for just transition to near-zero FLW*. WP8 focuses on providing alternative transition pathways towards near-zero FLW in 2050, defining a 'just' transition pathway and intermediate targets to get to this situation, and finally providing short-, medium-term policy recommendations for policymakers across the EU.

The purpose of this section is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

Table 2 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D8.1 Alternative near-zero FLW pathways</i>	Will report on the process and results of building pathways to near-zero.	All chapters and sections	This report provides a comprehensive report on the process, activities and results of building pathways to near-zero within the ZeroW working groups.
TASKS			
<i>Task 8.1 Alternative near-zero FLW pathways</i>	<p>This Task will employ a back casting approach to explore and build alternative transition pathways leading to near zero FLW food systems by 2050. This will be realised in the following steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. development of a trend pathway that looks into the future, based on historical trends and with no significant changes in the current policies, innovations and consumer behaviour (Business As Usual – BAU); 2. formulation of three alternative, distinctively different, pathways aimed at achieving a near-zero FLW food system. Each alternative pathway is based on a different balance of changes in policy, FLW innovations and consumer behaviour, thus reflecting the flexibility in response options towards near zero FLW. 	All chapters and sections	<p>This document provides a report of the following activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding the current state of play of FLW, including the collection of intelligence and information about FLW policies (SECTION 2.2.1) and initiating the development of a trend pathway (SECTION 2) - Formulating alternative pathways to near-zero FLW, looking into the future and suggesting different levels of change in policies, innovation and policy-making to reach a near-zero FW situation by 2050 (SECTION 4) - Organising working group meetings and analysing feedback from external

To validate the scenarios, the project team will organise 3 Working Groups (WGs) to explore, separately at the beginning each of three key areas (policy, innovation & consumer behaviour). Examples (non-exhaustive) in the policy area include:

- a. accurate policy tools to establish EU-wide comprehensive measurement of FLW, including unharvested food waste;
- b. policies to promote structural changes in food chains (e.g., short supply chains);
- c. use of existing policy tools such as the Common Agricultural Policy to mitigate FLW and perform FLW prevention at farm and retail levels;
- d. inclusion of mandatory criteria related to FLW reduction in public procurement;
- e. policies to support valorisation strategies, etc.

Subsequently, the WGs will be brought together to focus on the interactions and the potential of synergies and/or trade-offs among the three key areas, towards a near-zero FLW system. The WGs will involve stakeholders from various backgrounds addressing each key area. Enrolling the right members will be ensured through the professional contacts of the ZeroW partners and the Advisory Board members, and also through the network of Safe Food Advocacy Europe.

stakeholders that inform the above two points (SECTION 3.1)

1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Amongst its many objectives, the ZeroW project aims to contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets set by the Farm-to-fork Strategy (F2F) and the EU Green Deal (EGD), in particular to halving the per capita food waste levels (at consumer and retail stages) by 2030. On the short-term (i.e. by the end of the project in 2025), we collectively aim to reduce FW by 20% at retail and by 25% at consumer level through our Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs); whilst on the medium-term (i.e. 2030) we aim to contribute to the 50% reduction of per capita FW at retail and consumer levels and, on the long-term (i.e. 2050.), we wish to reach a situation of near-zero per capita food waste (FW).

The medium- and long-term objectives cannot be met with ZeroW innovations alone and must take into account several factors and variables that determine current food systems in the EU and that will evolve over time. It is thus paramount to examine the alternative developments of food systems from production to consumption, adopting a systemic approach that addresses the origin of the problem throughout the supply chain.

In this report, we aim to define the state-of-play of FLW in the EU building in order to define a trend pathway of FW reduction. As progress towards FW reduction at EU level has arguably been slow, we will then define three alternative, distinct pathways looking into the future. Each of them involves implementing innovative and sustainable practices to minimise or eliminate the generation of FW throughout the entire food supply chain (FSC), with different levels of change in the approaches taken towards policymaking, innovation and consumer behaviours. In order to define such pathways, one ought to include feedback and inputs from various expert stakeholders from the agrifood sector, to draw a picture (or rather, several) of what could be a conceivable future without FW. Through working group meetings and interviews, we initiated a collaboration with stakeholders along each stage of the supply chain, providing a better understanding of all the dynamics around FW generation and reduction in the EU. To allow the team to delve deeply into overarching frameworks, directives, and initiatives that impact FLW management across the entire EU, striking a balance between aiming for comprehensive insights and practical considerations stemming from resource constraints, the scope of our investigation is exclusively at the EU level rather than highlighting policies at the national, regional or local levels.

This deliverable is constructed in four key chapters:

- In the **first chapter**, we concentrate on describing the context of the present report (sections 1.1, 1.2, 1.3), mapping the synergies between the work of the ZeroW Policy

team (WP8) and other WPs, to provide elements of explanation concerning the framework of our work: how this report contributes to the modelling (or quantitative analysis) of the ZeroW project; how the other WPs of the ZeroW projects supported the creation of stakeholder groups to support the present report in its conclusions (section 1.4). We end this chapter with some considerations with regards to our geographical scope (section 1.5).

- In a **second chapter**, we aim to define a theoretical framework and a trend pathway for food waste reduction at EU level. We firstly describe the scope of our investigation with some considerations (section 2.1). In the following section (section 2.2), we draw a state of play of FLW management at global and, particularly, EU level based on a literature review (section 2.2.1), and complemented by an analysis of the barriers/opportunities to FW reduction at each stage of the FSC (section 2.2.2). We subsequently aim to make a non-exhaustive inventory of policy initiatives that give indications on the current trends in FW policymaking and its evolution in the near future (section 2.2.3). We close this general overview of the state of affairs by taking a look at the most recent FW data from Eurostat (section 2.2.4) and at important information provided by the EC and its Joint Research Centre (section 2.2.5), which both importantly contribute to the understanding of the trend pathway.
- In a **third chapter**, we proceed with some methodological considerations with regards to the scope of our investigation and the stakeholder consultations processes we led (through interviews and working group meetings).
- This knowledge collection and stakeholders' engagement processes contribute to our **fourth chapter**, where we develop three distinct scenarios or "alternative pathways" looking into the future aimed to help inform the FLW modelling and simulations ran in upcoming tasks of the ZeroW and to serve as a basis for future conversations with ZeroW partners and stakeholders to ultimately determine what a 'just' transition towards near-zero FW can be. Our conclusions regarding these alternative pathways are shared in a concise **fifth and final chapter**.

We would like to note that, despite building on the trend pathway described in this report, the alternative pathways are in no way forecast but present insights, with different levels change in consumers behaviours; in innovation; and in policies. They aim to merely spark debates and conversations around what a "just' transition pathway towards near-zero FW by 2050 would be, providing distinct, and somewhat purposely radical, approaches to FW management. Such conversations will be held within the ZeroW consortium and ZeroW

external stakeholder working groups in the upcoming months and reported in future publications of the project.

Appendixes at the end of the report indicate:

- The list of short-listed external expert and stakeholders contacted by the ZeroW Policy Team;
- The interview grid designed to support bilateral conversations between the ZeroW Policy Team and external experts and stakeholders.
- An analysis of barriers/opportunities faced by the ZeroW SILLs and relevant to this report;
- An overview of WP8 and WP9 regular interactions
- Contributions from SILLs periodic reports

Figure 3 D8.1 Structure

1.4 Synergies with other Work Packages

This section showcases the intricate interplay between Work Package 8 (WP8) – Policy recommendations for just transition to near-zero FLW and the broader activities within the ZeroW project, highlighting their collaborative synergy, strategic methodologies, and aligned pursuit of a shared objective: defining a ‘just’ transition pathway to near-zero FLW.

Figure 4 Objectives of WP8 & interactions with other WPs (PWG: Project Working Groups; EAB: external advisory board)

Figure 4 presents a high-level overview of these synergies and connections that we will elaborate on in the subsequent sections.

1.4.1 Modelling Food Loss and Waste economics from Farm to Fork (WP1)

Defining a conceptual model

As ZeroW aims to develop a conceptual framework to consider near-zero FLW food systems and to determine which essential conditions must be met for such systems to come about, interactions between both WP1 and WP8 are needed: while WP1 focuses on developing an economic model encompassing the food supply chain actors and quantitatively assessing various FLW interventions by running simulations within the FLW model, WP8 focuses on providing hypothesis and assumptions that can help inform the model itself (see section 2.1 - Methodology). Said assumptions are formulated based on qualitative research performed in all of WP8 tasks, namely through working group meetings with high-level experts, policy-makers and food sector stakeholders (see section 2.4.1).

Table 3 below describes the interconnected approaches adopted by both WPs.

	Qualitative analysis (WP8)	Quantitative analysis (WP1)
Conceptualisation	Concerned with understanding FLW reduction strategies and generation streams from stakeholders' perspective	Concerned with quantitative data about FLW generation and reduction (incl. prices, among others)
	Assumes a policy-oriented, negotiation-focused reality	Assumes a fixed reality, based on measurements and/or estimates
Methodology	Data obtained through stakeholders' contributions to Working Groups and interviews	Data are collected through measuring FLW variables (from official datasets)
	Data are analysed and reported by themes according to three dimensions of change (Consumer Behaviours, Policies, Innovations)	Data are analysed through numerical comparisons and reported through statistical analysis

Table 3 ZeroW methodological approaches to define a 'just transition' pathway

Economic model calibration/simulation

WP1 economic model considers 6 stages of the supply chain (primary production; transportation/handling/storage; processors; retailers; food services; final consumers, both at home and away from home). In order to calibrate the model, WP1 and WP8 are collaborating to gather the data below, namely through interviews and exchanges with experts:

Simulations will inform the conversations between WP1 and WP8 during the second phase of WP8 (Task 8.2 A 'just' transition pathway and intermediate targets to near-zero FLW by 2050) and will aim at defining, *inter alii*, what a 'just transition' pathway would be.

1.4.2 Systemic Innovation management & demonstration (WP4)

Defining FLW

In June 2022, WP4 published its first public deliverable (ZeroW Project, 2022a) which, among other considerations, needed to propose a FLW definition to be used throughout the ZeroW project for consistency. Traces of conversations between WP4 and WP8 can be found in this document, namely as regards the different existing definitions for food loss and waste. WP4 and WP8 interacted do discuss the EU and FAO definitions as well as the definition proposed by the [FUSIONS project](#).

Conversations led to an agreement to use the definition of FLW that ensures the comparability of future food waste solutions, i.e. the EU definition of food waste (see Figure 5), as provided in the amendment to Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste. Concerning the issue of the measurement/accountability of edible and inedible parts of foodstuff when assessing FLW in the ZeroW project, it was decided that the approach described in Delegated Decision 2019/1597, which deals with a common methodology and minimum quality requirements for the uniform measurement of levels of food waste, and where both the edible and inedible parts are quantified as food waste, should be followed.

Figure 5 ZeroW methodological approaches to define a 'just transition' pathway

SILLs periodic report analysis

Such conversations not only supported WP8 in ensuring a consistent understanding of FLW when holding stakeholder discussions, they also supported ZeroW SILLs in their own activity reports, which were analysed by both WP4 and WP8. Barriers/obstacles faced by SILLs in their development are often linked with legal, technical or economic constraints which are

influenced by FLW reduction policies, and keeping constant interactions between WP8 and SILLs (through WP4) was paramount. The result of a first analysis of such barriers is reported in the present document (see section 2.2.2).

1.4.3 Fostering systemic innovation & building capacity towards near-zero Food Loss and Waste (WP6)

As part of its task to gather stakeholder from three macro-regions (T6.1 Innovation scale-up success factors and incentives in targeted EU regions), WP6 organised several workshops in each macro-region represented in the project (Northern, South-West and South-East/Central Europe). The ZeroW SILLs were presented, with a focus on credibility, relevance and observability in said regions. As crucial policy leaders, WP8 partners were invited to contribute to the discussion held in the framework of these workshops, which will be documented by an upcoming report from the ZeroW project (D6.1 – Scale-up success factors and targeted EU regions). WP8 also contributed to identifying relevant stakeholders for the workshops.

1.4.4 Exploitation, sustainability & commercialisation of project outputs (WP7)

Although no formal interactions were held between WP7 and WP8, the pivotal role taken by the WP7 Market Analyses (ZeroW Project, 2022b) helped shape the present document, namely by contributing to section 2.2.5 below.

1.4.5 Cooperation with European Commission services & other project/initiatives (WP9)

WP8 and WP9 interact on a regular basis to liaise with EU institutions and other projects (see Appendix 4) with meetings held with EC services and EU institutions in 2023). WP9 partners particularly provide WP8 with useful updates, event notifications and queries from sister Horizon 2020/Horizon Europe projects taking part in the following networks/platforms:

- [Cooperation and Collaboration Network](#) (CCN): this network of over 30 other projects and initiatives worked on, or are currently working in the field of food losses and food waste;
- The [Green Deal Support Office](#) (GD-SO): the GD-SO was established to support the research and innovation projects funded under the Green Deal Call and to help

facilitate collaboration, share best practices and increase their impact. ZeroW is participating in the GD-SO Working Group on food.

- The [FOOD2030](#) Project collaboration network: this network is aimed at joining forces across projects, partnerships and networks working on shifting the food system to become more fair, healthy and sustainable.

These recurring conversations informed the content of the present deliverable and helped create bridges with experts on the topic of FLW reduction and sustainability in food systems.

1.5 Geographical scope and considerations

The ZeroW Policy team decided to narrow the scope of its investigation on FLW policies within the EU exclusively to those described at the EU level rather than highlighting policies at the national, regional or local levels. While this decision is primarily rooted in pragmatic considerations, with capacity emerging as a significant challenge as the complexities involved in conducting a comprehensive analysis of FLW policies across all member states and various regions within the EU represent a considerable challenge, the Policy Team considered that, by focusing solely on EU-level policies, efforts could be best streamlined and would allow the team to delve deeply into overarching frameworks, directives, and initiatives that impact FLW management across the entire EU. It is a recognition of the practical limitations associated with investigating a diverse array of policies at multiple administrative levels simultaneously. By homing in on EU-level policies, the ZeroW Policy team ensures a more focused and thorough examination of the regulatory landscape while also maintaining the feasibility of the research project. This approach is designed to strike a balance between the desire for comprehensive insights and the practical considerations of conducting an in-depth investigation within resource constraints.

Nonetheless, particular attention has been and will be paid to activities reported by [EU Member States](#) during meetings of the EU Platform on FLW, where public authorities regularly share best practices and progress at national level.

Moreover, the European Commission has made these initiatives known thanks to the [EU FLW Prevention Hub](#), which acts as a community of practices which, among other initiatives, provides information on national, regional or sectorial targets to reduce FLW. Additionally, it entails monitoring activities and available data on FLW, as well as initiatives, policy and legislative measures etc. Finally, data on FLW levels in EU Member States is readily available since 2022 through [Eurostat](#), following the new EU rules on mandatory FLW level measurement – these are pivotal to the following investigation (See section 2.2.4).

2. Building a trend pathway

In this second chapter, we aim to provide both a theoretical framework to this report and a trend pathway (or a 'state of affairs') through the analysis of resources from a variety (institutional) actor working on FW understanding (through FW monitoring, measurement and analysis) and reduction (through policy-making) at EU level.

We firstly describe the scope of our investigation with some considerations (section 2.1). In the following section (section 2.2), we aim to draw a state of play of FLW management at global and, particularly, EU level based on a literature review (section 2.2.1), and complemented by an analysis of the barriers/opportunities to FW reduction at each stage of the FSC (section 2.2.2). We subsequently aim to make a non-exhaustive inventory of policy initiatives that give indications on the current trends in FW policymaking and its evolution in the near future (section 2.2.3). We close this general overview of the state of affairs by taking a look at the most recent FW data from Eurostat (section 2.2.4) and at important information provided by the EC and its Joint Research Centre (section 2.2.5), which both importantly contribute to the understanding of the trend pathway.

2.1 Introduction

In 2020, the Farm to Fork Strategy of the European Commission clearly identified FLW reduction as one of the key policy priorities to achieve sustainability. Reducing FLW indeed brings savings for consumers and operators, and donations of food surpluses represent a social dimension, but also importantly ties in with policies on the recovery of nutrients and secondary raw materials for human consumption, the production of feed, food safety, biodiversity, bioeconomy, waste management and renewable energy (e.g. biofuels).

FW generation has often been regarded as the consequence of the sole excessive behaviours and attitudes of consumers, rather than an economic outcome of the consumer's utility maximisation goal (Lusk and Ellison, 2017) and the social and material contexts – or *Food environments* – in which food is provided (Evans, 2011; Evans, 2012). Rather than a focus on the individual consumer alone, one ought to investigate the bottlenecks, incentives and barriers to FLW reduction at every step of the food chain, from the very first steps of primary production to the final consumption of food products (away from home, in households, including when food has been donated and redistributed through, e.g., charity organisations)

- in other words, the consequences of multifactorial interventions in complex and globalised food systems.

As the problem seems to find its origin through-out the supply chain, it is important to design pathways which take a systemic look at the problem. This implies that only through collaboration between all (public and private) stakeholders, shared intelligence and innovation can positive food system transformation be achieved. To inform on this subject, previous research, initiatives and projects (such as FUSIONS) explored how FW should and can be reduced and how reduction would affect food sales and prices (Drabik et al., 2019). Such FLW reduction may have potential broader consequences, which cannot be underestimated. The embedded complex relationships have not yet been completely explored and the respective challenges addressed – hence why more qualitative and quantitative analyses are needed at the EU level.

At the EU policy level, the European Commission has proposed mandatory FW reduction targets for Member States as part of the 2023 revision of the Waste Framework Directive (WFD) (see section 2.2.5), which should arguably contribute to the SDG 12.3 goal of halving per capita FLW by 2030. In order to move further towards a near-zero FLW situation (by 2050), the ZeroW project intends to provide further reliable EU targets, which will require clear alternative pathways that are currently missing.

ZeroW considers that all FLW issues (see section 4) should be embedded in a holistic approach to act upon FLW, including defining what a 'just' transition pathway towards near-zero FLW (considering the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability) would be and provide evidence to inform forthcoming policies. The answer to the latter question will be explored in future ZeroW deliverables (namely, D8.2), building on the work described in the next sections.

2.2 Determining a trend pathway

In our pursuit of understanding bottlenecks, and to pinpoint the specific needs for systemic innovation towards near-zero FLW in food systems, understanding the intricate web of factors influencing food loss and waste (FLW) becomes paramount. This section delves into an exploration aimed at determining a pathway for the reduction of FLW by looking at current trends and policy developments (following a 'Business as Usual' (BAU) approach).

In this section, we will first present the result of a brief literature review. By delving into existing academic works and grey literature, we aim to provide an overview of the state of play of FLW management in the EU and provide figures, uncovering established practices and innovative approaches.

We then present an assessment of barriers and opportunities, based on previous ZeroW deliverables and inputs from WP8 investigations. This section therefore focuses on identifying and comprehending the obstacles hindering FLW reduction, as well as recognising the untapped opportunities, which both underline the need for further policymaking in the area of FLW management. We complement this by incorporating first feedback inputs from ZeroW SILLs, provided through their periodic reports (see appendix 5), as they provide unique perspectives on systemic changes.

Furthermore, we proceed with a review of ongoing EU legislative initiatives for FLW. Our examination includes a brief review of ongoing legislative initiatives within the EU, providing insights into the regulatory framework influencing FLW reduction efforts.

Lastly, we examine the important workstreams undertaken by JRC and Eurostat, in the past years, and their publications. As both JRC and Eurostat are key repositories of data and insights, a meticulous review of their publications pertaining to FLW management is undertaken to extract valuable empirical evidence and trends contributing to our analysis.

This first state of play is a mere attempt at summarising the complex reality of FLW trends, policies, and challenges of today, in view of understanding the current state of FLW but also to discern a trajectory that leads towards a more sustainable and efficient future in FLW management. This section lays the foundation for the subsequent section (section 2.6) defining alternative pathways towards near-zero FLW, providing an overview that informs our future policy considerations and conversations within the project and with external stakeholders, including key policymakers.

2.2.1 State of play – Literature review

As the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) points out, one of the striking pieces of evidence of the failure of the current agrifood system, and therefore the urgent need to transform these into more sustainable models, is the scale of FLW (FAO, 2022, p. 2). Estimates suggest that out of all food produced globally, 14% is lost (FAO, 2019) and 17% is wasted (UNEP, 2021).

The issue of FLW is also a **significant economic, environmental and social problem** at the EU-level. In 2020, total food waste amounted to 57 million tonnes, representing 127kg per inhabitant (Eurostat, 2022b). It is estimated that in the EU food waste contributes to at least 6% of its total GHG emissions and costs the EU more than 143 billion per year (FUSIONS, 2016, p. 5). Another striking fact is the estimation that the amount of food waste in the EU is higher than the amount it imports from outside the EU (Eurostat, 2022a). According to the most recent EU MS data published by Eurostat in October 2022 on national FW levels, households generate 55% of the total FW while the other 45% occurs in the earlier stages of

the food supply chain with primary production accounting for 11%, processing and packaging for 18%, distribution and retail 7%, and finally food services for 9% (Eurostat, 2022b).

The problem of FLW is important to address because it constitutes an integral part in the transformation of food systems into more sustainable models. In fact, FLW negatively impacts the three key dimensions of sustainable development. Firstly, FLW causes considerable **environmental damage** and contributes to climate change by putting unnecessary pressure on the environment and overusing natural resources. FLW is associated with 8–10% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (IPCC, 2019; UNEP, 2021), and contributes to the acceleration of biodiversity loss (EC DG RTD, 2020). This leads diverse environmental groups to argue that FLW reduction is critical in the global fight against climate change and biodiversity loss (Feedback EU, 2022, p. 4; WWF, 2021, p. 3).

Secondly, FLW also has significant **economic costs**. Indeed, the fact that enormous amounts of food end up lost or wasted at the global level does not mean that everybody has access to affordable and nutritional food. Today, hunger and food insecurity remain big challenges with between 702 and 828 million people suffering from hunger in 2021 (FAO et al., 2022, p. xiv). Consequently, this has led some to argue that reducing FLW could contribute to the fight against hunger and food insecurity and help in making healthy food accessible and affordable to all (FAO, 2022, p. 2; FAO et al., 2022; Boysen et al., 2022). Thirdly, the highly inefficient use of resources associated with FLW also has **negative social impacts**, as it contributes to increased global inequalities (FAO, 2023). Therefore, reducing FLW could also help with eliminating poverty and increasing global wealth and income (JRC 2022, p. 4). To stress the importance of FLW reduction, the next section discusses the impacts on these three dimensions in more detail.

The environmental impacts of food waste

FLW puts unnecessary pressure on the environment as it involves the needless over-exploitation of limited resources for the growth, production, processing, transport, and distribution of food products which ultimately end up being wasted (Gustavsson et al., 2011). This overuse of resources associated with FLW is considerable, with Kummu et al. (2012) estimating that around 24% of total freshwater resources, 23% of global use of fertiliser and 23% of global farmland are used to produce food that ends up lost or wasted. Such wasteful use of resources poses serious environmental problems, ultimately threatening the availability and quality of water (Lundqvist et al., 2008), soil health (UNEP, 2009; Traumann

et al., 2015), biodiversity (Pretty et al., 2015), and air quality, which are key for the health of humans, nature, animals, and ecosystems in general (Cuéllar and Webber, 2010).

FLW's negative impact on air quality is connected to its direct and significant role in global warming by contributing to the up to 30% of global greenhouse gas emissions generated by food and agriculture (JRC, 2022). It is estimated that global FLW contributes to 8–10% of global GHG emissions with a global carbon footprint estimated at 4.4 gigatonnes of CO₂ per year (IPCC, 2019; UNEP, 2021; FAO, 2015). In Europe, Scherhauser et al. (2018) conclude that FLW generates 186 megatonnes of CO₂ per year. In addition to GHG emissions resulting from the use of agricultural machinery and vehicles for the production and transport of food that ends up wasted (Weber and Matthews, 2008), food waste management is also a significant source of GHG emissions (Mokrane et al., 2023). Landfills in particular generate large quantities of methane whose warming effects are 20–25 times stronger than those of carbon dioxide (EPA, 2022; EPA, 2023; IPCC, 2007).

While the environmental costs of FLW are clear, it is important to remember that they differ between countries and depends on the quantity of waste, its type, and the stage at which it occurs (Mokrane et al., 2023). For example, the environmental impact of FLW is reportedly the biggest at the primary production step of the food supply chain (FSC) because of the large amounts of emissions generated at that stage. However, there is no doubt that reducing FLW of all types (at every step of the FSC and everywhere) would have beneficial consequences for the environment. Therefore, a reduction in FLW has been presented by defenders of the environment as critical in the context of the global fight against climate change and biodiversity loss (Feedback EU, 2022; WWF, 2021).

The social impacts of food waste

In addition to its environmental impact, the inefficient use of resources associated with FLW also has significant social impacts. First, as mentioned earlier, the enormous amounts of food waste at the global level coexist with the fact that between 702 and 828 million people suffered from hunger in 2021 (FAO et al., 2022). This issue of food security is important because it pertains to the fundamental right to adequate food, which is essential for the health and wellbeing of both individuals and entire nations (FAO, 2022; Thyberg and Tonjes, 2016). The apparent paradox of the coexistence of food insecurity and FLW means that, as Gjerris and Gaiani (2013) point out, FLW has an ethical dimension. Consequently, this has led some to argue that reducing FLW could contribute to the fight against hunger and food insecurity and help make healthy food accessible and affordable to all (FAO, 2022; FAO et al., 2022; Foresight, 2011; JRC, 2022).

While as Mokrane et al. stress, it is difficult to precisely determine how FLW contributes to the problem of food insecurity, and consequently, how reducing it would help alleviate the problem of global hunger, experts suggest there is real potential in taking measures to improve the management of resources and minimise FLW (Ingram et al., 2013). For instance, Stuart (2009) suggests the reduction in FLW through better resource management would mean that resources not consumed to produce the surplus food could be used for growing/producing food for the parts of the world suffering from food insecurity. According to Abbade (2020)'s estimates, the quantity of food lost and wasted globally could help feed 939 million adults with a 2000kcal and 50g protein daily intake per person.

Beyond the problem of food insecurity, as Mokrane et al. (2023) highlight, FLW also has more indirect social impacts. For instance, the unnecessary overuse of resources and the depletion of natural resources and pollution it creates contributes and/or exacerbates problems such as energy insecurity, health issues, poverty, and wars and conflicts. Moreover, in high-income countries such as in Europe, FLW is connected to what the literature refers to as 'metabolic waste' (FAO, 2014; Sundin et al., 2016) which refers to excessive food consumption resulting in negative health consequences such as overweight and obesity (Serafini and Toti, 2016). Finally, food waste also constitutes 'nutritional waste' as FLW represents a loss of nutrients (Chen et al., 2020).

The economic impacts of food waste

FLW not only has environmental social dimensions, but is also economically costly, especially when it comes to waste disposal (Mokrane et al., 2023). At a global level, the FAO (2014) estimates the cost of FLW around USD 1 trillion and USD 2.6 trillion when including its environmental and social costs. The economic costs at the EU-level are not negligible either, with Eurostat (2022b) estimates suggesting a price tag of EUR 130 billion. While these economic losses associated with FLW affect all actors of the food supply chain (Thyberg and Tonjes, 2016), the extent of these varies depending on the stages along the chain and the regions where FLW occurs. In contrast to high-income countries which suffer most economic losses in the consumption stage of the FSC, it is in the primary production stage that lower-income countries experience the biggest economic losses related to FLW (Mokrane et al., 2023). Consequently, global disparities and inequalities keep increasing due to the inefficiencies of the current food system.

Tackling Food Loss and Waste

As the problem has become increasingly evident over the last decade, it was defined as a specific sustainable development target in the UN's 'Agenda for Sustainable Development'.

Indeed, within the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12, which focuses on sustainable and production patterns, target 12.3 states that *“by 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses”* (FAO, 2022, p. 2). Although this target demonstrates the international consensus on the need to tackle the issue of FLW at the global level, this target has been criticised for only imposing a specific 50% reduction target on retail and consumers while only calling for reduction of waste in earlier stages of the food supply chain such as primary production (WWF, 2021).

After consultation of stakeholders, the FAO also developed a ‘Voluntary Code of Conduct for Food Loss and Waste Reduction’ (CoC FLW). As its name indicates, this code of conduct, which was endorsed by the FAO conference in June 2021, is entirely voluntary and consequently not legally binding (FAO, 2022, p. 3). This code of conduct “promotes the mainstreaming of FLW reduction in all policy frameworks related to agrifood systems and recognizes the importance of fostering coherence and coordination across the policies, institutions, and legislation relevant to FLW reduction” (FAO, 2022, p. 3). The Code of Conduct for FLW proposes a food hierarchy to guide how to prioritise FLW reduction and management. Such hierarchy first prioritises preventing FLW occurrences in the first place. This prevention strategy is followed, in order, by recovery and redistribution of surpluses for human consumption (e.g., in food banks), diversion of remaining surplus for animal feed or for transformation into non-food items, composting, incineration, and in last resort, incineration or landfilling (FAO, 2022, 5–6).

As a bloc, the EU has also committed to the 50% reduction at the consumer and retail stages of the food supply chain by 2030, as well as the overall reduction of FLW across the entire food supply chain of the SDG 12.3. which it signed in 2015 (European Commission, n.d.-d). This is reflected in its EU Farm to Fork (F2F) Strategy, which takes place within the context of the broader EU Green Deal and includes FLW prevention as one of its key elements. To achieve this objective, the European Commission has developed plans to introduce legally binding FW reduction targets to be set up across the EU in July 2023, and intends to also revise existing EU rules of date marking (European Commission, n.d.-a).

At the EU-level the relevant legal framework on the issue of waste is set by the WFD which establishes the basic concepts, definitions, and principles for waste management in the Union. One of those key principles is a five-step “waste hierarchy”, establishing an order of preference for the waste management and disposal which constitute the foundations of the EU strategy on this issue (European Commission, n.d.-c).

In 2018, the Waste Framework Directive had already been amended, requiring Member States to reduce food waste at each stage of the food supply chain, monitor waste levels and report back regarding progress made (European Commission, n.d.-b), and making it mandatory for Member States to design food waste prevention programmes and promote food donation and distribution of food surpluses for human consumption. This reflects the principles of the food waste hierarchy (adaptation of the general waste hierarchy to the specific problem of food waste). Similarly to the hierarchy promoted by the FAO, the food waste hierarchy guiding the EU's approach to food waste management first prioritises "prevention actions, followed by reuse pathways of surplus food fit for human consumption, reuse of food no longer intended for human consumption as animal feedstuff, recycling of material into high added-value products (without complete degradation), recycling of nutrients, recovery of energy and, as the least preferable option, the disposal of food waste". (European Commission's Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy, 2020, p. 8).

In July 2023, the Commission published a targeted revision of the WFD, and more specifically (as called for in the F2F strategy) proposals for legally-binding targets for EU Member States (European Commission, n.d.-c). We further describe this new proposal and its content in another section of the present report (see section 2.2.5).

2.2.2 Understanding the barriers and opportunities for FLW reduction

While it is difficult to get a precise idea of the extent of FLW, estimations listed above provide a good idea of the problem's global scale.

There are factors driving FLW at a general-level. One of those factors is globalisation, as it increases the risks of FLW by lengthening the food supply chain, adding more intermediaries, and thereby creating longer distances between the different actors (Mokrane et al., 2023; Priefer et al., 2016; Thyberg and Tonjes, 2016). Moreover, the phenomenon of migration from rural to urban areas also contributes to increasing the distance between consumers and producers, thereby increasing the likelihood of food ending up lost or wasted (Mokrane et al., 2023; Priefer et al., 2016; Thyberg and Tonjes, 2016). Furthermore, while there have long been cultural differences in terms of a culture's appreciation for food, which explain differences in the amount of FLW (Thyberg and Tonjes, 2016), there also are general changes in consumer habits and expectations in terms of availability, variety, and freshness which also contributes to large quantities of FLW (Mokrane et al., 2023; Priefer et al., 2016). Finally, as Thyberg and Tonjes (2016) discuss, in some cases policies contribute to increasing FLW, such as by mandating its disposal, putting barriers for redistribution, or by prioritising health concerns over the objective of food waste reduction.

The following sections showcase the key barriers and opportunities identified along each stage of the FSC. Some of these barriers and opportunities apply to more than one stage, with important overlaps concerning especially the wholesale and retail sectors.

There are six main categories: political, economic, sociocultural, technological, legal, and environmental. Data used for this section has been sourced from the Deliverable D7.1 (Market analyses) of the ZeroW project and updated for the purpose of this deliverable. For further clarification, Appendix 3 provides a summary table of the key barriers and opportunities.

Cross-sectoral barriers and opportunities

Before delving into the specific barriers and opportunities for each stage, it is imperative to highlight certain cross-sectoral ones that apply to most stages.

The first and most widespread one concerns the nature of the FSC itself, which is very long and complex. This complexity is worsened by the lack of human capacity for measurement and investment in personnel dedicated to food redistribution logistics, and by the lack of inspections and fining system on food waste generation by FSC operators (UN Economic and Social Council, 2021, p. 6).

Moreover, various legal obstacles extend across sectors. For example, there is a lack of a compulsory and firmly established quantification and reporting system for FW that FSC operators are required to adhere to, as only Member States authorities are obligated to comply with mandatory FW measurement (European Court of Auditors, 2016, p. 9).

Similarly, there is no mandatory regulation on food surplus management to avoid food dumping, with the only exception being France (Chrisafis, 2015). More importantly, according to the 1501 European Waste Code, food waste collected with its packaging is not actually considered food waste, and therefore does not need to be measured (YourDsposal, 2023).

Moreover, in some Member States such as France and the Netherlands, the governments keep funding subsidies to green energy or biogas plants (Messad, 2023). These subsidies incentivise FSC actors to sell their food surpluses to energy and local biogas producers because they receive concrete economic advantages. Consequently, these subsidies should be considered as a main barrier to the proper management of food waste because they hinder prospects for food waste revalorisation (e.g., transformation into long-lasting food such as juices). FSC actors are more likely to choose the option to sell their waste to energy production if it remains a cheaper, faster, and more convenient process compared to alternatives for revalorisation and reuse.

Finally, some environmental considerations apply to most sectors as well. For instance, Pyrolysis serves as an environmentally-friendly option for managing food waste. The resulting biochar, containing 10–50% carbon, is employed to directly capture carbon, and subsequently applied to enhance soil quality in agricultural settings. Nevertheless, a portion of the carbon stored in the biochar may be emitted into the atmosphere, with estimates ranging from 10–20%. This release depends on various factors, including pyrolysis conditions, soil pH, and climatic conditions (Elkhalifa et al., 2019, p. 317). Furthermore, composting represents a rapid means of valorising FW, yet it results in the emission of

greenhouse gases (GHGs), with 1 tonne of treated FW potentially generating up to 342kg of CO₂ (Awasthi et al., 2019, p. 6). Integrating carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies into composting reactors can mitigate this environmental impact. On the other hand, the compost utilised for soil enhancement aids in carbon sequestration and improves soil conditions. However, FW may contain trace amounts of heavy metals which can accumulate in reactors, contaminating the resulting compost and posing a risk of soil and groundwater contamination. Additionally, the release of antibiotic-resistant microorganisms into the environment is another area of concern (Awasthi et al., 2019, p. 8–9).

Stage 1: Primary production

Figure 6 Stage 1 - primary production

The political landscape features both barriers and opportunities for the reduction of FLW. Generally, EU policies are required to create a level playing field for European agriculture to remain competitive. For instance, the new 2023–2027 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is reducing subsidies that support production, moving towards economic help to environmentally-related public goods and services. To secure full funding, the new Common Agricultural Policy will require a series of measures aimed at enhancing sustainability. Simultaneously, it will uphold support for innovation in the agricultural sector through the implementation of ‘Eco-Schemes’.

Moreover, the Farm-to-Fork and Biodiversity strategies favour the adoption of new technologies to reduce the use of pesticides by 50%, fertilisers by 20%, nutrient losses by 50%, and dedicate at least 25% of agricultural land to organic farming. (European Commission 2023, November 10).

Finally, the UN's Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 12.3) places more importance in tackling the levels of food waste generated at the retail and consumer stages of the FSC, while only calling to reduce food losses at the farm stage. This may represent a considerable barrier to the overall reduction of FLW (WWF, 2021). From an economic standpoint, most European farms are small: in 2016, 67.6% of all EU farms had an economic output between EUR 2,000 and EUR 8,000 per year, limiting their capacity to invest in technological innovations.

Moreover, current market structures separate producers from consumers through intermediaries, making it difficult for farmers to assess market needs and demand, often leading to mismatches in volume, time of planting and harvesting, and subsequent produce surpluses that lead to food losses (WWF 2021). Most importantly, the food selling price at the farmgate is set by the middleman. If there is no market value for the produce, products are either left on the field or harvested and processed into compost. (Sujata et al., 2020, p. 6).

Some often-overlooked barriers are sociocultural, as agriculture remains unattractive for young people due to being physically demanding and repetitive, thus leading them to favour the adoption of automation/robotics technologies (UK-RAS, 2018).

Fundamentally, the balance of power favours markets over farmers, as they lack leverage to set prices for their produce. There is a direct correlation between lower-income farmers and levels of waste because they cannot invest in new farming technology to prevent waste. If supply is low, food prices increase and these are reserved for export or higher-income domestic markets, leading to undernutrition locally (WWF, 2021). Nonetheless, Process Analytical (PA) manufacturing provides opportunity for employment mostly in rural areas and Process Analytical Technologies (PATs) can improve working conditions by reducing repetitive tasks and fatigue (CEMA, 2019; Zarco-Tejada et al., 2014). Simultaneously, advanced automation technologies have the potential to attract highly skilled workers to the agricultural sector, potentially reversing the ongoing demographic shift from rural to urban areas (UK-RAS, 2018).

Technological barriers for primary production remain challenging. Full automation in farms is still not attainable because only larger companies can afford the required investment. The

transition needs to be gradual, meaning that new machinery will initially coexist with existing production systems. New opportunities derive from the high demand of certain components for automation, which has lowered their cost, allowing competitive production and favouring the development of new technologies. Some of these technologies already used in other industries can be readily adapted to the agri-food sector, while others will need to be specifically developed for agriculture. Zarco-Tejada et al., 2014). While persisting sub-optimal storage and cooling conditions reduce the lifetime of fruits and vegetables (IIR, 2023), the International Consortium for Innovation in Post-Harvest Loss and Food Waste Reduction was launched in 2019 to develop technologies to improve shelf life and minimise spoilage of produce, thus attempting to address these challenges (Foundation for Food and Agriculture Research, 2019).

Furthermore, primary production faces important legal barriers that may hinder progress on the reduction of FLW, such as the legislation on infectious diseases outbreaks prevention (Regulation (EU) 2016/429, 9 March 2016). At the same time, legislation such as Directive (EU) 2019/633 on unfair trading practices in business-to-business relationships in the agricultural and food supply chain aims to tackle power imbalances between actors in the agri-food supply chain to protect weaker suppliers from stronger buyers. Among 'black' practices, it prohibits the cancellation of orders of perishable food products on short notice, which can positively impact the issue of food loss (European Commission, 2009).

Finally, an environmental perspective highlights the fact that food production is responsible for a great part of the man-made environmental footprint, and that its inefficiencies cause FLW, resulting in unnecessary use of resources. However, the use of digital innovations in agriculture is considered to have a positive environmental impact by reducing the use of pesticides and fertilisers, contributing to the mitigation of climate change and the protection of soil and biodiversity (Zarco-Tejada et al., 2014).

Stage 2: Food processing

Figure 7 Stage 2 - Food processing

Every food product must gain approval from the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) before being processed and entering the market, including materials that get in contact with foods, such as food packaging. Moreover, the Global Protocol on Packaging Sustainability (GPPS) launched in September 2011 provides common principles and metrics in packaging in the context of sustainability to address environmental, economic, and social impacts (The Consumer Goods Forum, 2011).

The Upcycled Food Association has developed standards and certifications for upcycled foods and ingredients, which aim to increase public awareness and transparency for these products. Crucially, upcycling enables the reintroduction in the FSC of food products that would have likely been discarded. Therefore, to urge policymakers to improve its acceptability, it should be included in the waste management hierarchy (Moshtaghian et al., 2021, pp. 6-7).

The economic barriers for the food processing stage are fundamentally related to the nature of the highly diverse European food and drink industry, with 99.2% of the sector's 290,000 companies being small or medium-sized (Food Drink Europe, 2020). However, a few large companies with significant market reach account for 55.8% of the total value added in the food processing industry (Eurostat, 2021). Consequently, small and medium-sized companies will favour technologies that offer short-term, measurable benefits, thus limiting investing capacity.

Another identified barrier derives from the general encouragement of FLW reduction through accreditation schemes and voluntary programmes, such as the FAO's Voluntary Code of Conduct, which do not include legally binding targets (FAO, 2020).

Additionally, certain market practices and standards continue to hinder progress toward FLW reduction, such as the overproduction of bread and bakery products driven by the marketing standards of the retail sector (Fortune Business Insights, 2022). There is also low financial support to businesses for investment in food upcycling technologies, insufficient availability of qualified staff, and often too little time to unpack, sort, and redistribute food for logistics (Babu and Shah, 2023; Boz and Robinson, 2021; Jones et al., 2021). Industrial food processing has higher food discard levels, both in terms of usable parts of the animal/product and shape/weight (Jones et al., 2021). Nonetheless, the packaging and processing sector has actively addressed its impact on FLW. In recent years, packaging consumption/usage has increased by 10% while its waste decreased by 43%, showing progress towards sustainability and recycling (EUROPEN, 2021).

From a sociocultural perspective, the food processing sector faces the fact that the adoption of new technologies in the food and beverage industry depends on the consumers' acceptance and awareness of the benefits it brings, in terms of health and how the food is produced, even when they lack a solid knowledge about the technology (Rajauria et al., 2019, p. 2). The same applies for packaging, with food packaging companies taking decisions that depend on consumers' lifestyles and preferences, which constantly evolve and ultimately determine the success of innovations (EUROPEN, 2011). For instance, as upcycled foods use new processing technologies that may not be well-known by consumers, food neophobia and technophobia become significant barriers to any progress as they may negatively impact the technologies' acceptability (Moshtaghian et al., 2021, p. 9).

Moreover, consumers are often more aware of the environmental impact of the food packaging than that of food waste. Thus, they may choose a food with environmentally friendly packages even though this may lead to higher levels of food waste. Furthermore, the size of the packaging poses an issue, as consumers often find portions too large for their requirements, and some are willing to pay a bit extra for smaller-portioned packages (Hebrok and Boks, 2017, p. 389).

In relation to technological factors, the food and drink processing industry in Europe is at the forefront of adopting robotic technologies, where these are already extensively deployed to automate tasks (UK-RAS, 2018). There are currently 30,000 robots applied in the food and drink industry in Europe with a 52% increase in sales between 2013–2017 (Food Drink

Europe, 2021). A potential obstacle arises from the fact that integrating upcycled ingredients into a food product alters its essential quality parameters (appearance, colour, texture, etc.) in a manner that may be challenging to improve. Consequently, this should be explicitly disclosed in food products containing upcycled ingredients, and the addition of carbon footprint labels may improve acceptability even if consumers are affected by the change in parameters (Moshtaghian et al., 2021, p. 9).

Additional challenges relate to machine breakdowns that may cause food to be damaged or discarded, and the human errors during the handling process that result in the same outcome (TÜV SÜD, 2023; FoodBev Media, 2019). More specifically, the packaging value chain features extensive complexity because decisions made at one of the levels can impact subsequent stages downstream. For example, the choice of a material for packaging can affect the end-of-life options once the product is consumed. Thus, decisions must be taken for each case while taking into consideration all stages of the value chain (EUROPEN, 2011). Current technological trends to address this issue include recyclable packaging, augmented reality and cloud labelling in smart packaging, and edible packaging (Benzi, 2021, p. 5).

Legally, several Directives and Regulations affect the food processing industry, outlined in Appendix 3. Lastly, consumers tend to associate increased sustainability with regional and decentralised production systems. Nevertheless, this might not always hold true, as economies of scale often render large-scale systems more sustainable, benefiting from more efficient transport and processing methods (Zdravkovic et al., 2021, p. 7). The emerging concept of food upcycling seeks to diminish FLW by reintegrating these products into the human food supply chain. It is reasonable to expect that this approach offers a more environmentally-favourable impact compared to alternative food waste management methods, such as landfilling or incineration. Nonetheless, this should still be objectively assessed through Life Cycle Assessment studies (Moshtaghian et al., 2021, p. 11).

It is important to note that while packaging is commonly viewed as a source of waste with high environmental impact, it plays a crucial role in maintaining the quality of the enclosed food, and consequently, minimising FLW. The environmental impact of the food production process is estimated to be up to ten times greater than that of the packaging alone. In this context, it is imperative to point out that under-packing has a more significant environmental impact, leading to greater FLW generation, compared to overpacking (EUROPEN, 2011). This example showcases the need for the supply chain to reach a balance between safety and environment. In case of conflict between these two, health should take precedence. Thus, sustainability concerns must be individually assessed in each specific case (EUROPEN, 2011).

Stage 3: Distribution and wholesale

Figure 8 Stage 3 - Distribution and wholesale

The EU F2F Strategy, requires a series of commitments towards addressing health and sustainability issues in food and beverage trade and serving companies (i.e., environmental footprint reduction, reformulation of food products for healthier diets, etc.). It also aims to find ways to facilitate food recovery and redistribution to those most in need (Laaninen and Calasso, 2020, p. 9). Holistically, the proposed legislative framework by the EU for Sustainable Food Systems strives to enhance the sustainability of the entire food supply chain, encompassing production, processing, distribution, and consumption. This comprehensive framework, including the Sustainability Labelling under the Farm to Fork Strategy, is designed to empower consumers in making sustainable food choices. It will offer information on nutritional, climate, environmental, and social aspects of foods (Baldock and Hart, 2021, pp. 8–9).

Moreover, the Renewable Energy Directive 2018/2001/EU, revised in 2021, aims to accelerate uptake of renewable energy sources by at least 40% in 2030, effectively doubling their current share. It emphasises the promotion of innovative practices for recycling food waste and converting it into biogas (Directive (EU) 2018/2001, 11 December 2018).

Looking at the economic aspect of the wholesale sector, in 2018 there were 2.67 million companies involved in the food wholesale, retail and services sectors at the European level. These generated a turnover of EUR 2.4 trillion with an added value of EUR 424 billion and 16.4 million employees, in an industry dominated by micro-enterprises (Eurostat, 2021). The prevalence of these micro-enterprises and SMEs means it is likely difficult for them to make

heavy investments in solutions to reduce FLW, especially since they might require support from other stakeholders. One way to address this would be through case studies and sharing best practices that highlight the economic benefits of FLW reduction (EC Health and Food Safety Directorate-General, 2021).

Moreover, the Waste Framework Directive recommends that public entities employ fiscal measures as incentives for preventing food waste, often tied to activities like food redistribution or waste management (such as implementing fees based on the weight of waste collected by local municipalities). Additionally, certain Member States provide financial assistance to prevent food waste and fund innovative projects exploring solutions that contribute to circular food systems (EC Health and Food Safety Directorate-General, 2021). Some countries are even applying waste or incineration taxes or pay-as-you-throw principles to households to cover waste management costs and incentivise FW diversion from the landfill to other uses (Hebrok and Boks, 2017, p. 387). Several barriers remain because it is generally time consuming and costly to unpack food items, and thus faster to dispose of the items in residual waste containers (Garcia-Garcia et al., 2017, pp. 2212–2213).

The wholesale sector continues to face several technological barriers. For instance, package size is often a problem for consumers. Portioned and divisible packaging emerges as a potential solution. Some companies are now introducing meal kits featuring recipes and precisely measured ingredients, typically operating on a subscription-based business model (Hebrok and Boks, 2017, p. 389).

Additionally, most technologies employed for revalorising FLW are in the early stages of development, mainly validated at the laboratory-level. Demonstrating industrial-scale feasibility remains unaccomplished, necessitating robust logistics and high availability for managing FLW streams and upscaling processes. The significant challenge lies in the substantial variability of FLW streams, demanding the establishment of a system capable of analysing their composition and determining the most effective technology for treating each type of FLW (EC Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy, 2020; Tsegaye et al., 2021, p. 20). An additional challenge that similarly applies to the retail sector concerns the often-insufficient logistics capacity for food donations (BIO by Deloitte, 2012, p. 62).

Lastly, some Regulations can provide both barriers and opportunities for the wholesale sector, such as Regulation (EU) 1308/2013 (December 2013), providing the rules on marketing standards for fruits and vegetables, and the annexes of Regulation (EC) 852/2004, which concern food hygiene, further amended by Regulation (EC) 2021/382 in March 2021. The new amendments aim to ensure safety in the food to be donated to charities by defining

aspects for assessing food safety in donations. There are practices related to the areas covered by these legal documents that still hinder progress toward FLW reduction. For instance, companies may tend to use a shorter expiration period for products to avoid liability/image deterioration in case of food safety concerns (Van der Sluis, 2013, p. 13). Moreover, certain government practices equally represent significant limitations. In Denmark, there is currently no tax reduction/refund for businesses that donate food while businesses must bear the costs of redistribution. Therefore, companies prefer to sell the food on discounted prices to the Danish Food Surplus store WeFood to be able to pay a lower VAT based on the last selling price of the food item (Gram-Hanssen et al., 2016, p. 38; Harris, 2016).

Stage 4: Retail

Figure 9 Stage 4 - Retail

At the wholesale/retail level, the estimated total cost of FW can be up to 2% of total sales. Therefore, taking preventive measures could reduce economic losses (EC Health and Food Safety Directorate-General, 2021). However, business-led marketing standards and practices have a significant impact on FW in the wholesale, distribution, and retail sectors. Some examples include standards on shape, appearance, 24/7 shelf life, and EU-wide availability (Herzberg et al., 2022, p. 2261). It is important to mention that the food retail sector leads the food redistribution process in Europe, which comes with associated costs related to staff, storage, logistics, and others such as energy, website/IT solutions, the costs of purchased food, legal assistance, and food safety control (Wageningen University & Research and ECORYS, 2019, p. 13). An increase of almost 60% of food recovered and redistributed from the European Food Bank Federation’s (FEBA) members has been recorded in the period between 2016 and 2020 (FEBA, 2022). Inherently, the revalorisation of food implies costs, however, these costs would need to be lower than the market prices of the obtained products in order to make economic sense for retail businesses. Furthermore, taking measures to prevent FLW upstream in the food supply chain could diminish resources available for waste management innovations downstream in the chain, potentially compromising their economic feasibility and attractiveness (EC Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy, 2020).

A crucial challenge is that, despite the acknowledged high impact of FW at retailer/consumer-levels, there is little research assessing the viability of technologies for food waste

management. Currently, the food wasted in the food service industry is manually measured, with a worker weighing and logging the discarded food. Automating this process would enhance the quantification of FLW, enabling benchmarking and the establishment of new standards and policies (Martin-Rios et al., 2020, p.4).

From a legal perspective, EU Member States have implemented both legislative and non-legislative initiatives to diminish FLW. Notably, certain EU countries like France and Italy have enacted laws specifically addressing FW prevention at the retail-level. In France, retailers are prohibited by law from discarding edible food, mandating them to establish contracts with food banks for regular donations. Non-compliance results in fines. Meanwhile, Italy offers tax refunds as incentives to retailers who donate unsold food to charitable organisations. These measures have the potential to stimulate the demand for solutions aimed at enhancing efficiency in food bank management (Laaninen and Calasso, 2020, p. 9). Additionally, the following Regulations may provide opportunities for FLW reduction: EU Regulation 1169/2011, also known as the FIC regulation, outlines the labelling criteria for food products. Notably, the revised regulation introduces changes to the rules governing date marking, specifically "use by" and "best before" labels. Additionally, Regulation (EC) 853/2004, which outlines specific hygiene requirements for food of animal origin, amended by Regulation (EC) 2021/1374 in August 2021, grants authorisation for the freezing of meat intended for donation to food banks and other charitable organisations at the retail-level, specifying the conditions under which such freezing is deemed appropriate.

Research shows that at the retail-level, bread and beef contribute the most to environmental impacts through food waste. Exploring solutions that prioritise waste prevention or alternative uses for these specific food types could have a significant positive effect on sustainability. For instance, considering excess bread as animal feed is one potential avenue worth exploring (Brancoli et al., 2016, pp. 44–45).

Stage 5: HORECA sector

Figure 10 Stage 5 - HORECA sector

Within the HORECA sector, there are unique and specific features to consider. For instance, one economic barrier to FLW reduction relates to the often too large dish portions and the exaggerated number of items on canteens' buffets (Wu and Chih-Ching, 2022, p. 2).

Furthermore, from a more technical standpoint concerning food donations, there is insufficient logistics infrastructure to timely capture and redistribute all food surpluses (Ceynowa et al., 2023, pp. 12–13). It is useful to highlight the limiting role of government obligations for this sector. In Denmark, HORECA is obliged to divert food waste to compost or biogas plants. Moreover, only 1% of FW donated as Food Surplus Donations is not legally binding. It is often less costly for HORECA businesses to throw away food than donate it (Gram-Hanssen et al., 2016, p. 38). Lastly, the donation of cooked food in Nordic countries such as Denmark and Finland is complex: the HORECA Food Safety Regulation on food donation procedures mandates that delivery must be made within a limited time lap (2/3hrs) for safety concerns. Thus, such a small window for redistribution plays a role in disincentivising businesses from donating food surpluses (Ofei et al., 2015, p. 515; Norden, 2014, pp. 67–68; Danish Agriculture and Food Council, 2023).

Stage 6: End Consumers

Figure 11 Stage 6 - (End) consumers

The end stage of the food value chain, namely the consumption of all food products, is crucial for finding ways to reduce food waste. For instance, consumers' purchasing and conservation habits have a direct economic impact (World Economic Forum, 2021).

The role of consumers becomes even more central when considering the sociocultural dimension of FW. Various factors influence consumers' behaviours impacting FLW, including cultural context, perceptions, and attitudes towards food (Mak et al., 2020, p. 4). For numerous consumers, pricing emerges as a crucial determinant in their food choices, significantly impacting the likelihood of opting for sustainable and healthy diets (Eurostat, 2021). In this context, individuals may be more inclined to purchase food that does not conform to cosmetic standards if it is priced lower compared to visually "perfect" food (de Hooge et al., 2018, p. 699).

Consumers themselves can contribute to reducing FLW either by decreasing their food purchases or by ensuring the consumption of all the food they buy. If consumers opt to buy less food, it could lead to a decrease in demand, resulting in lowered food sales and prices, thereby affecting the well-being of producers. Conversely, if consumers maintain their level of purchases to prevent food waste, there is a risk of health issues associated with consuming all the purchased food, such as obesity (Lusk and Ellison, 2020, p. 7).

Crucially, the literature presents contradictions regarding the effectiveness of raising awareness about FW among consumers. While certain studies emphasise the need for

behavioural change, others contend that awareness alone may not substantially decrease FW due to the highly complex nature of this problem. Consequently, blaming consumers would be considered unproductive (Hebrok and Boks, 2017, p. 384).

Lastly, the support and acceptance of carbon labels remains a divisive issue across the EU. According to a 2020 survey performed by the Carbon Trust, two thirds of surveyed consumers think that labels indicating the carbon footprint of a product is a good idea. France, Italy, and Spain are the countries where acceptance of carbon labels is highest, with Sweden experiencing the greatest increase in support compared to previous surveys, yet still lower compared to other countries (Carbon Trust, 2020).

Furthermore, consumers still face a high probability of confusion regarding date marking (i.e., the interpretation of “best before” and “use by” dates) which increases food waste (Eurobarometer, 2015). Lastly, waste generated downstream in the supply chain, particularly at households, exerts the most significant environmental impact as it represents the final stage and accumulates the footprints from preceding steps. Approximately 4.4 gigatonnes of CO₂ annually, constituting 8–10% of total anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions, are attributed to FLW, with the majority occurring at the household-level (Mak et al., 2020, p. 2; United Nations, 2021). FLW is also a contributor to air and water pollution, biodiversity loss, and soil degradation. Despite these environmental concerns, consumers often prioritise factors like price over the environmental impact of FLW. Consequently, campaigns highlighting the environmental consequences of FLW may have limited efficacy due to consumer fatigue from constant messages on the subject (Hebrok and Boks, 2017, p. 383). More detailed barriers and gaps, as well as a compendium of tools, best practices, and recommendations have been identified by the Commission’s JRC in a technical report following the deliberations of the European Food Waste Forum. These are outlined in Section 2.2.5

2.2.3 Monitoring ongoing EU legislative initiatives

Before delving into specific ongoing EU legislative initiatives, it is useful to provide an overview of the European Green Deal (EGD) and the Farm to Fork strategy (F2F), which constitute the basis for the political commitment to reduce food loss and waste in the EU. The EGD is a comprehensive plan aimed at making the EU climate-neutral by 2050, transforming its society into a fair and prosperous one with a modern, resource-efficient, and competitive economy (European Commission, 2023, November 10; European Commission, 2020a). The F2F Strategy is a key component of the deal, entailing a plan to make the EU's food system more sustainable, healthy, and environmentally friendly. The strategy aims to ensure that food systems are resilient to crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic and are sustainable in the long run. Crucial objectives include reducing the environmental impact of food production and consumption, promoting healthy diets, and ensuring food security and safety (European Commission, 2020a).

Within this context, the Circular Economy Action Plan represents an additional and crucial component. It aims to ensure that waste is prevented, and the resources used are kept in the EU economy for as long as possible, aiming to make sustainable products the norm in the EU (European Commission, 2020b). Specifically, this action plan commits to significantly reducing total waste generation: it aims to halve the amount of residual (non-recycled) municipal waste by 2030, promote safer and cleaner waste streams, and ensure high-quality recycling.

Furthermore, the F2F strategy has introduced a crucial new form of citizen engagement, the European Citizens' Panel on food waste. It allows randomly selected citizens from all 27 Member States to discuss and make recommendations on how to reduce food waste more effectively. The panel is composed of 150 citizens, with one third of young people aged 16–25 and is representative of the EU's diversity in terms of gender, age, education, occupation, and geographical origin. From 16 to 18 December 2022, the panel met in Brussels and deliberated on the following questions (European Commission, 2023, February 10–12):

- How can we reduce food waste along the food supply chain and in households?
- How can we support food business initiatives to prevent and reduce food waste?
- How can we encourage consumer behavioural change to prevent and reduce food waste?

Following the deliberations, the panel produced a citizens' report with 23 recommendations, which was published together with the Commission's legislative proposal on food waste reduction on 24 February 2023. The recommendations cover three main areas: cooperation

in the food value chain, food business initiatives, and consumer behavioural change. Some key ones include (European Commission, 2023, February 12):

- Setting an overarching goal to reduce food waste at the EU-level, with legally-binding targets for Member States and monitoring mechanisms.
- Associating food waste reduction with a fair and equitable food supply chain that ensures solidarity and cooperation between actors, with mechanisms to facilitate the redistribution of surplus food to those in need.
- Promoting education and awareness-raising campaigns to build understanding and appreciation of the value of food from an early age.
- Supporting research and innovation on sustainable packaging and labelling solutions to extend the shelf life of food products and reduce confusion among consumers.
- Encouraging food businesses to adopt voluntary commitments and best practices to prevent and reduce food waste, such as donating surplus food, optimising portion sizes, and offering discounts for near-expiry products.

The outcome of this panel will keep supporting the Commission's work on food waste, which will incorporate these recommendations as part of the EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy (European Commission, 2023, February 12). In order to fulfil these objectives and achieve the EU's food waste reduction targets, more specific initiatives and legislations have been set up to provide guidelines and delineate a holistic approach to attain a truly sustainable society centred on waste prevention.

Waste Framework Directive revision

The WFD establishes a waste hierarchy that favours the prevention of waste over the following range of options, ordered from the most favourable to the least favourable: preparing for reuse; recycling; other waste recovery options; and disposal of waste, with landfills and incinerations as the very last resort (European Commission, 2023, July 5). The WFD requires Member States to take measures to prevent waste generation and collect certain types of waste separately. Crucially, it provides review clauses concerning prevention measures, food waste, and waste oils, as review is part of the Farm to Fork strategy. A targeted amendment in July 2023 (yet to be adopted by EU co-legislators) added a specific focus on textile waste and introduced the implementation of the "polluter pays principle". Besides providing guidelines for waste prevention, the WFD revision aims to propose legally-binding targets to reduce food waste and has been subject to an impact assessment (see below, section 2.2.5). The ultimate goal is to reduce all waste, including food waste, and

minimise the environmental impact of waste management (European Commission, 2023, July 5).

Legislative Framework for Sustainable Food Systems

The current sector-based legislative framework governing the EU has generally shown inadequacies in addressing sustainability. The main issue concerns the lack of a horizontal regulatory instrument active at the Union-level, guiding and coordinating changes across existing legislation. Therefore, the Commission has proposed a crucial initiative within the Farm to Fork strategy: the Framework for Sustainable Food Systems (FSFS). The core objectives include promoting policy coherence at both EU and national-levels, integrating sustainability into food-related policies, and enhancing food system resilience (European Commission, 2020c). More specifically, it aims to ensure an enabling environment for future policy and legislation by raising the political and legal profile of the sustainability, including climate neutrality concepts of the food system. Furthermore, it envisions a food environment that allows consumers to choose healthy and sustainable diets, while optimising food production, distribution, and consumption leading to an increased resource efficiency that will drastically reduce food loss and waste (European Commission, 2020c). To achieve this objective, it will include a “sustainability labelling framework”, which is described in the next section. It is crucial to highlight that the FSFS goes beyond the linear food supply chain approach and aims to ensure coherence with all EU food related policies (e.g., agriculture, fisheries and aquaculture). The FSFS is expected to be adopted by the Commission by the end of 2023 (European Commission, 2020c).

Food information to consumers: a new “sustainability labelling framework”

As mentioned previously, the FSFS will include a sustainability labelling framework, which originates from a review of the Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 on Food Information to Consumers (FIC). As part of the Farm to Fork Strategy and as an extension of the FSFS objectives, the Commission announced the intention to revise the FIC Regulation to ensure better labelling information and allow consumers to make healthier and more sustainable food choices (European Commission, 2020d). It will do so by introducing harmonised mandatory front-of-pack nutrition labelling and setting nutrient profiling criteria to restrict claims made on foods. Moreover, it will extend mandatory origin or provenance information for certain products and revise the rules on date marking, meaning the “use by” and “best

before” dates on food products. The latter is especially important because the issue of date marking continues to be a source of confusion among consumers, leading to high amounts of household food waste. Essentially, consumers continue to misunderstand and misuse it, with a 2015 Eurobarometer showing that less than 1 in 2 consumers understand the meaning of date marking: “use by”, which indicates the ultimate food safety date, and “best before”, which refers to the date food retains its optimal quality (Eurobarometer, 2015).

Therefore, the FIC revision and the new sustainability labelling framework can directly address the end stage of the food value chain (consumers), which is responsible for the highest amount of food waste annually. By clarifying and improving the EU’s sustainability labelling framework, consumers will feel empowered to make more informed and sustainable choices without confusion, potentially leading to less wasteful behaviours and thus towards a mitigation or reduction of FLW. This will be done in synergy with other labelling initiatives, such as the animal welfare labelling and the Green Claims Directive. The overall framework will allow consumer to get precise nutritional, climate, environmental, and social information of food products, while companies will be made accountable and will have to verify and provide evidence for their green claims (European Commission, 2020d). In fact, providing precise information on climate and environmental concerns on food products, and thus emphasising the consequences of food waste, may be useful levers appealing to individual motivation and psychological factors. The underlying reasoning is that building on emotions and engagement might motivate consumers to undertake a more active role in food waste reduction efforts (JRC, 2023).

Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation

Another crucial initiative is the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR) proposal published on 30 November 2022 and expected to enter into force by 1 January 2025. This legislation aims to harmonise national measures concerning the management of packaging and packaging waste, replacing the current Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive. Thus, the measures outlined in the PPWR will be binding and uniformly applicable to all EU companies and Member States that place packaging on the market. The objectives are the following (European Commission, 2022, November 30):

- Finding economically viable ways to make all packaging waste on the EU market recyclable by 2030.
- Increasing the use of safe recycled plastics while decreasing that of virgin materials (e.g., new plastics).

- Voicing support for reuse and refill options through setting long-term packaging targets (e.g., reducing unnecessary packaging).

Thus, the PPWR sets targets to reduce excessive packaging and increase the circularity and recyclability of all EU packaging, which should significantly address the sheer volume of post-consumer plastic waste produced annually (Global Business Club, 2023). Moreover, the PPWR addresses the issue of quality and safety of packaging materials, more specifically the presence of hazardous substances or so-called “forever chemicals”. These substances known as per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a group of synthetic chemical compounds that have water and dirt-resistant qualities, but are also highly persistent, bio accumulative, and toxic to humans and the environment. Some of these substances may also be carcinogenic or harmful to human health in some respects (e.g., affecting the reproductive or endocrine system) (Harvard School of Public Health, 2023; European Parliament, 2023). The PPWR proposes to ban the use of PFAS in food contact materials and other packaging applications, unless they are essential for health, safety, or functionality reasons.

The PPWR also requires the European Commission to establish criteria for identifying essential uses of PFAS in packaging and to review the list of essential uses every five years. The PPWR aims to phase out the use of PFAS in packaging by 2030, unless there are no feasible alternatives (European Commission, 2023, October 19; Packaging Europe, 2023).

The revision of marketing standards for agri-foods and the Unfair Trading Practices Directive

The marketing standards for agri-food products are rules that regulate the quality, composition, labelling, and presentation of certain agricultural and food products in the EU market. The aim of these standards is to ensure fair competition, consumer protection, and product differentiation. The term “agri-food” encompasses the production and distribution of food and non-food products of agricultural origin, and is a sector that has experienced a very slow reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in recent decades, thus generating a significant climate impact (EPRS, 2023). Agri-food systems represent the backbone of any economy and play a central role in ensuring food security and nutrition, which is why the EU supports a steady transition towards a sustainably agri-food system (EPRS, 2023). In April 2023, the European Commission proposed to revise the existing marketing standards applicable to a set of agricultural and food products: fruit and vegetables, fruit juices and jams, honey, poultry, or eggs (European Commission Representation in Cyprus, 2023; European Commission, 2010). These revisions and new rules aim to help consumers make

more informed choices and empower them to contribute towards food waste prevention. The following points summarise the main changes introduced by the Commission (European Commission Representation in Cyprus, 2023; European Commission, 2023, October 19):

- Clearer and mandatory origin labelling rules for products such as honey, nuts and dried fruits, riped bananas, and trimmed, processed, or cut fruit and vegetables.
- Crucially, “ugly” fruit and vegetables are exempted from complying with marketing standards if sold locally and directly by producers to consumers, or if affected by exceptional circumstances such as natural disasters.
- Fruit juices may bear the mention “with no added sugars” or “reduced-sugar fruit juice” on their labels.
- The fruit content of jams should increase from 350 grammes to 450 grammes minimum per kilo of finished product, and the allowance of the term “marmalade” applies for all jams.
- The ban of the use of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in food contact materials and other packaging applications, unless they are essential for health, safety, or functionality reasons, in accordance with the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation.

This initiative complements the Unfair Trading Practices Directive as part of the EU’s efforts to improve the functioning and fairness of the food supply chain. While the proposed revision of marketing standards promotes the sustainability and quality of agri-food products, the Unfair Trading Practices Directive aims to protect the interests of farmers and consumers. Adopted in April 2019 and entered into force in November 2021, it specifically protects farmers and small suppliers of agricultural and food products from unfair practices by larger buyers in the food supply chain. The directive bans 16 unfair trading practices, such as late payments, short-notice cancellations, unilateral contract changes, misuse of trade secrets, and commercial retaliation. The directive also allows some practices, such as return of unsold products or payment for promotion, only if they are agreed beforehand in a clear and unambiguous manner. Most importantly, it establishes a minimum level of enforcement across the EU, requiring each Member State to designate a public authority to monitor and investigate complaints, impose sanctions, and cooperate with other authorities (European Commission, 2021, November 1; Directive (EU) 2019/633, 17 April 2019).

As of November 2023, this Directive has been in force for two years in the EU, and both positive impacts and limitations have been identified. For instance, farmers can now rely on a minimum level of protection and see their bargaining power improved. Consequently, as

buyers and suppliers must agree on unambiguous terms, there is also increased transparency and trust in the food supply chain. An additional benefit concerns the enhanced cooperation among national authorities. Nonetheless, challenges in the directive's implementation remain, such as its divergent transposition and application by different member states who can retain some discretion resulting in legal uncertainty. Moreover, there is still a low level of awareness among farmers and small suppliers who may lack information and resources, while some national authorities may lack the capacity or powers to effectively investigate complaints or impose sanctions (European Commission, 2021, November 1; Foote, 2021; European Brands Association and Food Drink Europe, 2021).

2.2.4 Measuring and monitoring FW levels: Eurostat data

In 2018, a revision of the WFD introduced, among other provisions, a request to the EC to adopt a legislation on FW measurement by 2019, in order to set mandatory rules for EU Member States to monitor FW levels and report progress made in FW reduction. The EC was delegated to establish a common methodology for FW measurement beforehand, with a delegated decision (Delegated Decision (EU) 2019/1597) entering into force in October 2019, together with an implementing act (Commission implementing decision (EU) 2019/2000). Consequently, the first data collection on FW was undertaken by Member States in 2020, in view of reporting on national food waste levels by mid-2022.

The EU Statistical Office (Eurostat) is publishing data from FW mandatory reporting since October 2022, when the first EU-wide results of the first measurements (from reporting year 2020) were finally available. In September 2023, Eurostat published (incomplete) results of the second dedicated statistical monitoring of the amounts of FW in the EU by stage of the FSC, corresponding to reporting year 2021. The official figures (see figure 12) show that 54% of accounted FW (according to the EU definition and the scope of the mandatory reporting rules, therefore excluding food losses) is occurring at household stage, while the remaining 46% are generated by primary production (9%), food manufacturing and processing (21%), retail and distribution (7%), and restaurants and food services (9%).

Overall, Eurostat declared that FW approximately accounted for 10% of the total food supplied to consumers in 2021.

Figure 12 Food waste in the EU by main economic sectors (Eurostat, 2021)

Eurostat provided, namely, important data on:

- Total amounts of FW in the EU per stage of the FSC
- Total amounts of FW in the EU per country

FW measurement is paramount to understand the measures to take in FW reduction strategies. Importantly, these new data enabled the EC to take action and suggest new provisions to the WFD (see section 2.2.5). From a ZeroW perspective, having access to databases (on waste generation and treatment, on waste streams) is a key that help understand national situations and inform conversations about geographical contexts (see section 1.5).

2.2.5 JRC complementarity

It is of importance to highlight that the Joint Reach Centre of the European Commission has undertaken a lot of important work to understand FLW production trends. Exchanging with JRC and monitoring progress of its work have therefore been pivotal in the work of the ZeroW policy team, as the outcome of the workstreams described below contributed to the understanding of the trend pathway.

The ZeroW policy team focuses on two main research projects that the JRC conducted: the European Consumer Food Waste Forum, aimed at tackling consumer food waste; and the important inception impact assessment developed in the framework of the Waste Framework Directive revision.

European Consumer Food Waste Forum

The JRC, in partnership with the Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE), has established a cross-disciplinary European Consumer Food Waste Forum (ECFWF) aimed at tackling consumer food waste. Through collaborative efforts, researchers and practitioners work together to identify solutions and create tools for mitigating consumer food waste. The project's objective is to issue research- and evidence-based recommendations and develop tools to tackle the challenges of consumer food waste, complementing the work of the EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste with a compendium of best practices and tools to facilitate effective interventions (European Commission, 2023, October 24).

So far, the forum's main outcome consists of the publication of a compendium of tools, best practices, and recommendations to "help all key players engaging in actions to prevent food waste" (European Commission, 2023, October 24). Overall, the compendium emphasises a systemic approach that takes the key drivers and levels of behavioural change into account when targeting FW reduction at the consumer-level. Moreover, it encourages cooperation with all stakeholders and contends for concrete actions towards sustainable food systems (European Commission, 2023, October 24).

This compendium (JRC technical report), published on 5 July 2023, is highly relevant to the ZeroW project because it informs the analysis on changes of consumer behaviours and thus the alternative pathways outlined in section 4. A set of six generic types of evidence-based interventions to reduce food waste have been identified, as shown in Figure 13. The interventions 1–3 aim to reduce food waste at home, focusing on different drivers of food

waste, while 4–5 cover food waste out-of-home and 6 concerns both (JRC 2023, July 5, pp. 15–16).

1		Prompts and tools for households
2		Coaching for households
3		Local awareness campaigns
4		Classroom education programmes and actions in school canteens
5		Nudges out-of-home (food services)
6		National food waste prevention programmes

Figure 13 Six generic types of evidence-based interventions (JRC 2023, July 5)

Prompts and tools for households (JRC 2023, July 5, pp. 16–18)

These interventions encompass physical, textual, or digital prompts that encourage consumers to reduce their food waste at home, for instance by adopting new habits and routines. All actors, including food producers, can design these prompts and target any type of consumer and household.

- The aim is to use nudges and prompts to enhance consumers' food management skills and support their adoption of new habits and routines. These tools are designed to empower consumers to incorporate behaviours into daily life.
- As "assisting tools", they can be textual or digital prompts that function as reminders, such as a "use-it-up" sticker next to a product's expiration date. More specific tools include shopping lists, menu planners, food waste diaries, and tools to measure portion sizes.
- These tools are especially relevant for those households and groups with unpredictable consumption patterns, lacking time, skills, and motivation to take action. Their strength lies in their applicability to a large target audience without

exponential costs. Moreover, they can be combined or integrated with other awareness-raising elements.

- To measure potential FW reduction, these tools typically take a minimum of one week. Furthermore, it is imperative to carefully identify and assess the specific behaviour that should be changed to guarantee better implementation prospects. The impact assessment should also be long-term.

Coaching for households (JRC 2023, July 5, pp. 19–21)

This category comprises tools aimed at breaking wasteful consumer routines by increasing consumers' knowledge and boosting their skills in the kitchen. All actors can implement these coaching programmes and target any type of consumers, but especially those in charge of purchasing and preparing meals within the household.

- Coaching interventions focus on all aspects of food management: planning, shopping, storing, preparing, and using leftovers.
- Activities include information workshops, sharing of material through media channels, training or kitchen laboratories. Creative approaches such as thematic challenges (e.g., cooking with leftovers) can also be effective.
- The most effective coaching programme included individual sessions for personalised feedback and training. Moreover, there are synergies for integration into local action plans, literacy schemes, and awareness campaigns.
- Before conducting the coaching programme, it is crucial to ensure relevance of the targeted consumer group(s). For instance, they can be beneficial for households with higher waste levels. When conducting the coaching, it is important to spread the call for participation through various social media platforms tailored to the target group.
- Additional funding and adapt materials improve the coaching's implementation, as well as collaboration with local institutions such as universities and NGOs. Sustainability should also be included in the design phase.

Local awareness campaigns (JRC 2023, July 5, pp. 22–24)

These campaigns comprise actions to improve the visibility of the impact of food waste and encourage consumers to change their behaviours. They can take place anywhere and target any type of consumers but should always be relevant to communities and households in their respective contexts. Even if they can be implemented by any actors, typically NGOs or local authorities do so.

- Their scope is to raise awareness and influence consumers' attitudes, beliefs, and ultimately change their behaviours within households.
- Their "messaging strategy" can build on the local context to include relevant information, such as specific waste management strategies or food waste costs. Local needs should always be integrated to improve effectiveness.
- These campaigns are typically combined with skill training as well as material and economic incentives, often relaying national and international communication campaigns (e.g., World Food Day).
- Upon starting an awareness campaign, it is imperative to understand the audience and the context for the campaign. Combining initiatives and promoting synergies improves its implementation. An example would be the Trifocal Programme, which successfully combined multiple activities (cooking workshops, pop-up events, toolkit provisions) to reach different audiences.

Classroom education programmes and actions in school canteens (JRC 2023, July 5, pp. 25–28)

This first type of out-of-home intervention specifically targets school environments, which are widely recognised as crucial in developing awareness and knowledge of food waste among the young generations.

- These interventions' aim is twofold: educating children through classroom activities and simultaneously reducing food waste occurring during school meals. Typically, educational material on FW is included in wider curricula addressing sustainability or economics.
- National education administrations and NGOs can provide teaching material, while implementing multiple actions in the canteen, such as co-creation of menus with children and food waste reduction challenges.
- Despite schools' constraints regarding resource availability, these environments have extensive potential for positive impact and synergies. For instance, schools are a controlled environment resulting in easier data collection. Most importantly, these initiatives can lead to positive spill-over effects on household food-related behaviours because children can share awareness and behaviours with their families, thereby impacting the household's saving-behaviour. This spill-over can result in multi-level effects.

- Upon conducting these interventions, it is important to collaborate closely with school staff, identify and validate teaching materials, and most importantly use a creative approach (e.g., including games, challenges, etc.) to involve children and commit them to behaviour changes.

Nudges out-of-home (food services) (JRC 2023, July 5, pp. 29–30)

This second type of out-of-home interventions consists of nudges targeting consumer food waste in contexts outside of households, such as collective catering for companies, school or university canteens, and restaurants.

- Nudges are designed to stimulate and encourage consumers to reduce their FW by smartly influencing their behaviours. Thus, they address specific drivers of food waste and employ various mechanisms.
- These mechanisms can be easy to implement. For instance, restaurants and canteens often want to build a culture of “food waste reduction” and green reputation and can easily implement nudges such as encouraging consumers to only take the food they need (“the right portion”).
- Nevertheless, nudges always require a specific cultural organisation and collaboration with workers, who can encourage consumers to take home their leftovers.
- Consequently, nudges can be very context-dependent. It is difficult to predict their effectiveness and it is generally recommended to tailor interventions to specific groups of consumers and foster partnerships between different actors. An example of the latter would be a partnership between commercial restaurants and the regional waste management company.

National food waste prevention programmes (JRC 2023, July 5, pp. 31–35)

The ECFWF deliberated on the crucial role that programmes organised at the national-level can play in supporting all the different types of interventions and improve large-scale awareness of food waste reduction and associated campaigns. National governments and agencies are key implementers, targeting the entire population.

- These programmes are “umbrella initiatives”, useful to define a comprehensive national strategy to reduce food waste and create an enabling environment for the implementation of different interventions. They foster coordination among actors and facilitate individuals’ behavioural change.

- They mainly operate by fostering cross-sectoral collaboration and the adoption of a systemic approach. Collaboration between actors is key to strengthen outreach and improve implementation prospects.
- These programmes can be easily integrated into EU-wide debates on food waste prevention and other global initiatives. Moreover, they provide relevant evidence for other public policy challenges, such as plastic packaging reduction.
- Their successful implementation benefits from a clear baseline structure that identifies “waste hotspots” in the population to prioritise actions and strategise accordingly. Moreover, it is crucial to ensure the application of an evidence-based and data-driven approach throughout the programme, especially since they usually run for several years or permanently.
- Building a relevant network of actors and fostering multi-stakeholder debate may be essential components of a successful strategy. Furthermore, the implementation of a successful programme necessarily comprises knowledge and expertise from different fields while carefully but consistently disseminating interventions.

Gaps identified by ECFWF and research needs (JRC 2023, July 5, pp. 51–54)

After providing interventions to reduce food waste in and out-of-home, the ECFWF identified remaining gaps in food waste reduction efforts that should be considered. Most importantly, it is necessary to gain a deeper understanding of factors driving food waste and identify relevant levers associated with them. Interventions can only be successful if informed by an accurate and in-depth understanding of the underlying causes of food waste, especially when considering specific contexts such as local environments. The current uncertainty and confusion surrounding the most common drivers of food waste makes it difficult to evaluate the most effective interventions. Therefore, additional research and practical guidance are required to assist in the identification of the most effective interventions for minimising food waste, taking the drivers and levers carefully into account. Furthermore, insufficient understanding of how behavioural factors influence both food waste and the efficacy of reduction interventions restricts their applicability to other countries, household profiles, or consumption contexts. Thus, further evidence is needed to explore the potential transferability of these interventions and enhance the effectiveness of their strategies.

In relation to the intervention design, several aspects need improvement. The ECFWF identified the potential of segmentation in paving the way for better targeted and tailored interventions. It opposes the generic “one-size-fits-all” approaches and it can be especially

applicable to identify “hot spots” or vulnerable groups who could benefit the most from a specific intervention. However, the understanding of behavioural hot spots and vulnerable groups regarding food waste is limited, and evidence of the effectiveness of more targeted interventions is also lacking. Thus, further research should be focused and context-specific to better conceptualise, define, and identify the most relevant targets, audiences, and behaviours. Practical guidelines should be developed to facilitate this process of segmentation and empirical testing. Moreover, there is a lack of clarity regarding the role and significance of behavioural factors, such as motivation, which should also be addressed by these practical guidelines. Most importantly, there is currently no dedicated theory or model that specifically targets or tailors interventions for FW reduction. Future research should include efforts to develop such a specific theory or model.

Lastly, evaluating these interventions and sharing more evidence-based resources, knowledge, and experiences should be priorities. Crucially, the evaluation should be consistent and reliable for each intervention. In this regard, the EU common measurement methodology plays a central role as it can help standardise the monitoring and reporting of food waste. Quantification methods should be further developed depending on the specific objectives, while it is important for practitioners and implementers to be fully informed about the costs of the interventions. A growing body of research recommends considering the scalability early in the intervention design process, given the current lack of consideration and the related knowledge gap concerning the long-term effectiveness of behavioural interventions.

A persisting lack of understanding of the potential negative consequences of food waste reduction interventions on various food value chain actors is also a pressing issue. Consequently, future research should shed light on these potential consequences, investigating any potential impact and incorporating the evidence into the interventions. Similar efforts might also help anticipate or investigate potential drawbacks. A recurring problem with these efforts concerns the lack of motivation to take action. Practitioners often struggle to access evidence-based and actionable resources on food waste reduction interventions, especially if there is confusion on drivers and levers. As a result, they may be discouraged from taking further action. This is the reason why it is fundamental to keep promoting the sharing of knowledge and experiences, as it motivates action.

Interventions should be shared and updated regularly through networks of relevant stakeholders. Knowledge and data-sharing hubs have the added benefit of fostering interactions between experts and policymakers, who can then take the required actions. In

this regard, governments should be more involved as both coordinators and facilitators of food waste reduction interventions, as an active role from their side remains a rare occurrence.

Further actions to reduce food waste (JRC 2023, July 5, pp. 55–56)

From a holistic point of view, the final deliberations of the ECFWF recommended the following actions for future research and interventions:

- Combining different interventions that address various mechanisms underlying food waste to change consumer behaviour. An example would be combining awareness-raising initiatives with practical tools and nudges that reduce FW. Segmentation has great potential in adapting interventions to local contexts and needs.
- Considering spill-over effects of food waste prevention actions. It is crucial to recognise that efforts to reduce food waste at one step of the household food management process can occasionally lead to food waste at another step. An example would be when donated food or restaurant leftovers taken home are later wasted. However, spill-over effects can also be positive, such as when children change the household's routines after school initiatives. Generally, future interventions need to consider both desirable and unintended effects to improve their effectiveness.
- Some promising types of interventions are under-studied, such as financial incentives or communication of social norms. Rather than overlooking them, future research should investigate their potential effectiveness.
- Better quantification methods and measurements of food waste will greatly benefit targeted interventions. Additionally, information about food waste reduction or targets should be explicitly expressed, especially to appeal to environmentally conscious consumers who may then take action.
- To adopt a systemic approach to tackle food waste, research needs to focus on how individual factors can induce food waste at different stages of the supply chain. In this context, understanding and acknowledging the role of contextual factors is crucial, especially the legal and policy landscape and the market environment.

Impact Assessment report for a revision of the WFD

Produced in early July 2023, this impact assessment report accompanies the WFD revision proposal (see section 2.2.3). It considers the revision of the Waste Framework Directive and its reduction of waste generation and the transition to a circular economy, focusing on two

resource intensive sectors: textiles and food. The ZeroW policy team analysed the conclusions of the impact assessment report for the food waste part only.

This impact assessment importantly describes and justifies what is to be achieved by the revised directive, and the policy options that have been assessed using the [Modular Applied General Equilibrium Tool](#) (MAGNET), which analyses policy scenarios on agricultural economics, bioeconomy, food security, climate change, and international trade.

Baseline ('Business as Usual') scenario

The JRC formulated a baseline (or as the EC calls it, 'Business as Usual') for FW generation meant to provide a reference (scenario) for the impact assessment of the FW reduction targets. It "assumes a continuation of ongoing policies, regulations, and market trends on the future situation of the wider bioeconomy up to 2050" (European Commission, 2023, November 22). Baseline drivers and assumptions were made based on the Global Energy and Climate Outlook updated on a yearly basis by the JRC:

- Drivers such as economic growth, demographic development, land use and management, technology change (in production technology development, feed efficiency, forestry biomass), energy, policy mechanisms and reforms, consumer preferences, and food waste, were explored.
- Assumptions for each of these drivers based on several available datasets and indices.

In the specific case of food waste levels, they were projected following the FW Mobility Functional Areas (MFA) data (for the 2014–2020 period) and the GDP per capita development following a couple of studies (for the 2020–2050 period).

Although the JRC acknowledged the scarcity of data, the authors made specific assumptions (IIA, 2023, pp.166–176), resulting in an estimation: for the EU-27, a stable development of FW generation is projected for the period 2020–2030, i.e.. 56.98M tonnes of FW to 57.04M tonnes. This has been put in relation (through the MAGNET simulation) with proportions of change in GDP and population, as illustrated in figure 14 from the JRC impact assessment report:

Figure 14 FW generation in the EU-27 in relation to change in GDP and population (period 2020-2030)

Some MS populations are estimated to decrease in the coming decade, while GDP evolution will greatly vary based, both resulting in different estimates in FW generation or reduction based on ongoing regulations.

The impact assessment report also sheds light on the most important commodities evaluated in the MAGNET simulations: cereals, dairy, eggs, fish, fruits, meat, oils, sugar beets, vegetables.

Categories such as ‘other food’, ‘others’, or ‘food service’ have also been considered to account for the FW distribution across stages of the supply chain and across the following food groups: primary production, processing and manufacturing, retail and distribution, and households.

However, the JRC did not consider modelling food losses as well, despite this being called by stakeholders during public consultation processes, as this would “require analysis of the consequences of applying existing waste management rules on biomass from primary production (which is currently excluded)” from the EU FW definition and mandatory measurement (European Commission, 2023, November 22, p.170)¹.

¹ On this topic, it must be noted that the WASTELESS project (funded under Horizon, GA No. 101084222) published in August 2023 a White book for FLW reduction, measurement, and monitoring practices (in its D1.1). This deliverable importantly maps FLW measurement and monitoring practices; this works provides a good overview of practices (including legislative initiatives at EU MS level), including actions at primary production stage. Another comprehensive screening of all initiatives could contribute to a better understanding of the gaps in EU/national legislation with regards to food loss and waste measurement and management at primary production level and, ultimately, could provide a justification for further revisions of the WFD to include legal dispositions to tackle unmeasured segments of FLW streams in the FSC.

Setting FLW reduction targets

The EC built upon the impact assessment report to formulate three policy options ahead of the revision of the WFD (see below, table 4):

2030 Food waste reduction target on:	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3	Option 4 (voluntary)
Primary production	N/A	N/A	10%	N/A
Processing and manufacturing	10%	10%	25%	N/A
Retail and consumption	15%	30%	50%	Voluntary target 50%

Table 4 The three policy options (WFD revision)

As the EC acknowledges it in the impact assessment report, selecting target levels is always “to some extent arbitrary”. The targets were set based on several existing pieces of work: an EC-funded study by LEI Wageningen UR (Rutten et al., 2013, p. 17) concluded that 50% reduction targets would be “ambitious”, while 40% and 30% would respectively be “realistic” and “modest” for the period 2012–2020. Being confronted with actual results from FW reduction measurements, the proposed targets have been lowered respectively to 15%, 20%, and 30% for 2014–2025. The Impact Assessment tested scenarios for FW reduction levels at 15% (Option 1) and 30% (Option 2), according to this update, and adding another scenario equivalent to SDG 12.3 – i.e., 50% reduction at retail and consumption stages, as described above in table 4.

Additional targets were tested for earlier stages of the food supply chain: a 25% target (Option 3) for FW from processing and manufacturing, based on the call of the [UNFSS Coalition on Food is Never Waste](#), was set. Arguing that operators have an inherent economic incentive to reduce FW and that the potential for future FW reduction is limited, the EC proposed a more moderate target for this stage at the level of 10% (Options 1 & 2), generally in line with commitments to reduce food waste made under the [Code of Conduct](#).

And finally, to ensure covering the whole food supply chain, a 10% reduction target has also been set on primary production (but only in Option 3, as the EC noted that primary production is not covered by the index measuring progress towards SDG 12.3 ([FWI - Food Waste Index](#))).

An Option 4 was also considered, relying on setting voluntary target for Member States, based on formulation of SDG Target 12.3 i.e., 50% reduction of food waste for the retail and consumption stages (jointly), with no specific targets for earlier stages. This option would therefore not be mandatory, and would only be subject to obligations when it comes to the annual reporting of food waste levels. The JRC noted that actions taken by Member States following their political commitments (SDG12.3) since 2015 have not allowed to make significant progress towards 50% FW reduction by 2030, and importantly states that “there is no reason to believe that including an obligation for Member States to set voluntary targets, in the WFD, would lead to significant improvement in this regard” (European Commission, 2023, November 22, pp. 69–88)

Assessing the Impacts of FW reduction targets

As explained in the above sections, the JRC used the MAGNET model to simulate the impacts (both positive and negative) of different scenarios (see the proposed reduction targets or options above in table 4). The EC explored the environmental, economic and social impacts, as well as the impact on FW as a whole, of all first three scenarios² (European Commission, 2023, November 22, pp. 69–88):

- **Overall impact on FW levels:** Option 3 performed the best in reducing FW, with approximately 23,500 tonnes of FW prevented in 2030 compared to the baseline 2020. The deciding factor in achieving a higher reduction is located at consumption stage, while the impact of FW reduction at earlier stages of the FSC (‘primary production’, ‘processing and manufacturing’) is more limited.
- **Environmental impacts:** Options 2 and 3 lead to reduced emissions of greenhouse gas overall, despite certain non-food activities being impacted by FW reduction and subsequently producing more GHG emissions. Option 3 performs best with an estimate -44% overall GHG reduction and land use, among other impact categories (marine eutrophication and water scarcity have also been included in the assessment).
- **Economic impacts:** the JRC estimates that FW reduction results into a decrease of demand for food, as prevented FW remains available for human consumption. This is however not resulting into a decrease in EU food production, but rather a decrease

² It must be noted that the MAGNET model was not used for Option 4, as it was not possible to assign specific reduction levels for this option. The impacts of Option 4 were estimated to be similar to those of option 1.

in food imports and exports. The reduction in consumer demand appears to be the highest for commodities such as vegetables, cereals, and fruits. Overall, the JRC estimates that all three options are only marginally affecting the economy, with Option 3 presenting a slight decrease in net income in EU27 (0.022%) while Options 1 and 2 present a slight increase; it is to be noted that negative economic impacts are compensated by positive impacts of other (non-food) economic sector benefitting from FW reduction. The impact assessment investigates the impact of the options on trade, production of agricultural sector and market prices of food, farm income, and costs of implementation.

- **Social impacts:** the JRC explored the impact of the scenarios/options on food affordability and jobs in the agrifood sector. Overall, the JRC notes that the greater the FW reduction, the more affordable the food gets, and the more savings households make. The role of food donation to less advantaged segments of the EU population is also underlined; whilst other 'grey' social impacts (such as lost leisure time due to an increased attention to food conservation, preparation, donation, etc.) are mentioned, but mostly addressed in the EUFCW forum publications (see the above title in this section).

The impact assessment report notes potential negative impact of reduction targets on small and medium enterprises, although as an indirect effect, due to limited resources and capacity to adapt to the legal framework. No impact on fundamental rights is noted; on the contrary, digitalisation is likely to be impacted, with new technologies having a great role to play in driving future innovation in the field.

Ultimately, the EC, in its proposal for a WFD revision, favoured Option 2, arguing that it would be the most effective option to provide a policy impulse in Member States, while being proportionate and feasible. While Option 3 would offer the most environmental benefits and best reflect the political commitments (referring to SDG12.3 and the EGD/F2F Strategy), the EC assessed that progress made in MS was too slow and limited, and was therefore doubtful of the technical feasibility of such an option by 2030.

2.2.6 Conclusions

In the above sections of this chapter, we have seen, through a brief literature review, how FLW have social, environmental, and economic impacts. In order to best understand how to find effective solutions to these many challenges, we have explored both the barriers and the opportunities to FLW reduction identified by ZeroW sources (including WP7 and SILLs, see appendix 5) and other projects. We have furthermore scoped the ongoing legislative initiatives undertaken by the EC and other EU institutions which have a direct or indirect impact on FW generation or reduction. We have then complemented this state-of-play by looking at the latest available data from Eurostat and, finally, at the important work published by the JRC in the framework of the European Consumer Food Waste Forum and the Revision of the WFD. The latter provided several elements that form the most up-to-date trend pathway (or baseline scenario) and FW reduction targets, which we importantly rely on to formulate the three alternative pathways described in the following section.

In the next chapter, we described how the ZeroW policy team led an investigation throughout the year by engaging with external stakeholders of the agrifood sector, to attempt to establish a basis for a state-of-play that would inform a trend pathway, and subsequently the formulation of the three alternative pathways or scenarios (described in section 4.4) towards near-zero FLW.

3. Methodology

As detailed in chapter 1, one of the main goals of the ZeroW project is, in the coming months, to understand and define a ‘just’ transition pathway to near-zero Food Loss and Waste (FLW) in 2050, and to furthermore set intermediate EU targets and deliver short- to medium-term FLW policy recommendations supporting this ambition.

Such an objective will be attained through the successful completion of tasks within this work package (WP8), starting from the development of a trend pathway that looks into the future, based on historical trends and with no significant changes in the current policies, innovations and consumer behaviour (see section 2). The subsequent step consists in formulating alternative, distinctively different, pathways aimed at achieving a near-zero FLW food system (as shown in figure 15).

Figure 15 Different pathways towards near-zero FLW

Each alternative pathway is based on a different balance of changes in policy, FLW innovations and consumer behaviour, thus reflecting the flexibility in response options towards near zero FLW; they also integrate some ‘pragmatic’ elements derived from current policy developments and recent publications from the EU Institutions and bodies. In particular, they are formulated with regards to the discussions around the proposal of new (mandatory) sets of FW reduction targets for EU Member States (MS).

Balances of changes and choices have been defined through the identification of policies in force, constant monitoring of activities performed by all relevant public institutions (including assisting research centres and academic bodies), and consultation processes with stakeholders in the food sector. In order to do so, the ZeroW Policy Team organised 3 Working Groups (WGs) to explore each of three key areas:

- **Policy:** policies are instrumental in reducing FW by establishing guidelines, targets, and incentives. They provide a regulatory framework that encourages responsible practices, supports the adoption of innovative technologies, and promotes transparency in reporting.
- **Innovation:** innovation is key to reducing FW, driving the adoption of advanced technologies and sustainable practices. It optimises processes and enhances FSC efficiency.
- **Consumer** behaviours: while FW is a cross-sectorial issue that requires holistic solutions, consumer behaviours must be looked at specifically as food is mostly wasted at household level. Consumer behaviour play a vital role in reducing food waste by influencing purchasing habits, storage practices, and overall awareness. Encouraging mindful consumption, minimising overbuying, and utilising food efficiently contribute to a more sustainable and waste-conscious food system.

Subsequently, the outcomes of the WGs are brought together to focus on the interactions and the potential of synergies and/or trade-offs among the three key areas, towards a near-zero FLW system.

In coming months, the alternative pathways will be assessed using both a quantitative approach (through the work of ZeroW WP1, FLW modelling) and a qualitative approach (through the external stakeholder Working Groups):

- a. **Quantitative approach** (reference is made here to the work described in section 1.4): ZeroW WP1 project team (led by the Wageningen University and Research) will develop and use economic and system dynamics (SD) models to understand and analyse the effects of various policies to reduce FLW in the supply chain. These will empirically model a FSC that commences with consumers who consume food either at home or away from home. At home, food consumption will partly be covered by food donations that stem from individual upstream stages of the supply chain. Including food donations enables the ability to model the role of food banks in reducing food waste, as well as their impact on prices along the food supply chain. Processors, retailers, and food services (i.e., hotels, restaurants, and institutions) will represent the middle parts of the supply chain. Farmers will be at the upper side of the food supply chain, and both their decisions with respect to the downstream actors, as well as ways to reduce pre-harvest losses, will be considered. The empirical model will also include the ways of disposing of food waste, such as landfill/incineration, land/sewage, and donations. These model extensions will be

useful in quantifying to what extent restrictions imposed on the disposal of food loss and waste can contribute to its reduction.

The macro-level results of modelling FLW interventions will not only provide insights into the effects of a reduction in FLW on the GDP of the EU and the employment in agriculture and food processing sectors but will also capture the important interactions with the instruments of the new Common Agricultural Policy of the EU.

- b. **Qualitative approach:** ZeroW Policy Team (led by Safe Food Advocacy Europe) further validates the findings of the FLW modelling through the external stakeholder working groups exploring separately three key areas (policy, innovation, and consumer behaviour). Working groups have also provided opinions and inputs to guide the modelling exercises performed by WP1, in particular by providing insights on potential future policies to apply along the food chain to reduce FLW.

3.1 Working Group meetings

As mentioned in the above section, the ZeroW Policy Team (WP8) designed three dedicated spaces to discuss the following key topics:

- Policy
- Innovation
- Consumers behaviours

Feedback from 14 WG meetings have been regularly shared with ZeroW WP leaders during Project Steering Group (PSG) meetings, and in bilateral exchanges. WG reports contribute to the aforementioned F2F approach by integrating all relevant contributions from external stakeholders to the project FLW modelling, and defining at least 3 different alternative pathways looking into the future at different balances of changes in policy, FLW innovations, and consumer behaviour – to reflect the flexibility in options towards near-zero FLW.

In this section, we describe each of these three Working Groups and detail their expected outcomes and guiding questions, providing further information about the content of the sessions and the timeline of this consultation process. We provide further information about specific inputs gathered through subsequent stakeholders' interviews.

Stakeholders involved

In order to best represent the diversity of interests, expertise and opinions on FLW reduction, as well as to contribute to policy learning (Challies et al., 2017), the ZeroW Policy team identified 104 potentially interested stakeholders amongst the groups and sub-groups identified in figure 16 (see appendix 1):

Figure 16 Contacted stakeholders for ZeroW external stakeholders WGs

Based on the principle of voluntary participation and provision of inputs, stakeholders participated in the sessions described below. Several presentations were provided by the engaged organisations, with the addition of pieces of feedback from organisations who could not commit to attend the WG meetings on a regular basis but still wished to contribute to the conversations:

Table 5 Stakeholders parttaking in ZeroW external stakeholders WGs

<p>Civil Society Organisations and Citizens</p> <p>Future in our Hands (NGO & non-profit/Norway)</p> <p>European Food Banks Federation – FEBA (NGOs & Non-profit/EU)</p>	<p>Industry and Innovators</p> <p>COPA COGECA (Farmers/EU)</p>
<p>Institutions and policymakers</p> <p>Andalusian Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development. General Secretariat for Agriculture, Livestock and Food (Regional Institutions/Spain)</p> <p>Emilia-Romagna Region - DG Agriculture (Regional Institutions/Italy)</p> <p>Municipality of Tel Aviv (Local Institutions/Israël)</p>	<p>Research communities</p> <p>University of Bologna (Regional Institutions/Italy)</p> <p>University of Copenhagen (Universities/Denmark)</p> <p>IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute (Research Centres/Sweden)</p> <p>World Resource Institute (Research Centres/International)</p> <p>Joint Research Centre (EU Institutions/EU)</p>

These presentations tabled perspectives from the four categories of identified stakeholders: research communities, institutions and policymakers, CSOs and citizens, and industry and innovators. The WG also benefited from different perspectives offered by the diversity of scopes of the different participants: local, regional and national organisations, EU and international organisations, and organisations from and outside of the EU.

Innovation working group

This WG explores how innovation can influence forward-looking food systems to implement solutions to reduce FLW. Innovation indeed plays a critical role in reducing FLW by identifying and implementing new solutions to address the issue from the farm all the way to the fork. Innovation can notably contribute to reducing FLW in the following ways:

- Improving food processing and storage: Innovations in food processing and storage technologies can help to reduce the amount of food lost due to spoilage, pests, or improper storage conditions. For example, the use of modified atmosphere packaging can extend the shelf life of fruits and vegetables.
- Developing new products: Innovations in product development can help to create new food products that are more resistant to spoilage and have a longer shelf life. For example, the use of edible coatings and films made from natural materials to extend the shelf life of fresh products.
- Reducing food waste in the supply chain: Innovations in logistics and supply chain management can help to reduce food waste by improving the efficiency of distribution and minimising the amount of time that food spends in storage or transit. For example, companies are using data analytics to optimise routing and minimise the amount of food that is discarded due to spoilage.

Overall, innovation can play a crucial role in reducing FLW by creating new technologies, products, and solutions that help to reduce waste at every stage of the food supply chain.

Guiding questions to stakeholders have been primarily derived from analyses of D7.1 (Market analysis), SILLs periodic reports, and exchanges with WP1 leaders. The ZeroW policy team first intended to request inputs on potential innovations, barriers/obstacles and opportunities in the following stages of the food supply chain, and relating to (if applicable) specific commodities.

The aim of this WG was to provide concrete solutions in terms of the expected support for:

1. Innovations in food processing and storage;
2. The development of new products;

3. Innovations in logistics and supply chain management that can help to reduce food waste;
4. Innovations in marketing that encourage consumer behaviour change.

Policy Working Group

Policies play a critical role in reducing FLW by creating a regulatory framework that encourages businesses and consumers to adopt behaviours that reduce waste. Policies can contribute to reducing FLW in, among others, the following ways:

- Setting targets and goals: Governments can set targets and goals for reducing FLW, which can help to focus the attention of businesses and consumers on the issue. For example, the United Nations has set a target of reducing FLW at retail and consumers stages by 50% by 2030.
- Establishing regulations and standards: Governments can establish regulations and standards that require businesses to measure and report their FLW, and to take steps to reduce it. For example, some countries have implemented regulations that require businesses to donate unsold food to charity or to use it for animal feed.
- Providing incentives: Governments can provide incentives for businesses and consumers to reduce FLW, such as tax breaks or subsidies for investments in waste reduction technologies. For example, some countries provide tax credits for businesses that donate food to charity.

Overall, policies can play a crucial role in reducing FLW by creating a regulatory framework that encourages businesses and consumers to adopt behaviours that reduce FW. By setting targets, establishing regulations and standards, providing incentives, and educating consumers, governments can help to create a more sustainable food system that wastes less food and resources.

This WG discussed (among others) the following ongoing policies, initiatives, and trends:

- Accurate policy tools to establish EU-wide comprehensive measurement of FLW, including unharvested food waste and food losses;
- Policies to promote structural changes in food chains (e.g., short supply chains);
- Use of existing policy tools such as the Common Agricultural Policy to mitigate FLW and perform FLW prevention at farm and retail levels;
- Inclusion of mandatory criteria related to FLW reduction in public procurement;
- Policies to support valorisation strategies, etc.

This WG should provide concrete expectations in terms of:

- Targets and goals
- Regulations and standards (to measure and report FLW, to donate unsold food to charity or to use it for animal feed, etc.)
- Expected incentives
- Policies for consumer education & promotion of FLW reduction

Potential policies to be applied should be expressed in the following ways:

- What is to be achieved (i.e., targets)
- How it is to be achieved (through which policies)

Information on policies/other measures is especially important if we want to model endogenous changes in the rates of FLW as opposed to exogenous (i.e., imposed on) ones.

Consumer behaviour Working Group

Consumer behaviour plays a critical role in reducing food loss and waste (FLW) at a systemic scale. Changes in consumer behaviour can contribute to reducing FLW in several ways:

- Reducing over-purchasing: Consumers can reduce FLW by buying only what they need and avoiding over-purchasing. This can help to reduce the amount of food that ends up being thrown away because it has gone bad.
- Proper storage and handling: Consumers can reduce FLW by properly storing and handling their food. This includes keeping perishable foods at the right temperature, storing food in airtight containers, and using up leftovers before they go bad.
- Choosing "ugly" produce: Consumers can help to reduce FLW by choosing to buy produce that may not look perfect but is still edible. This can help to reduce the amount of food that is discarded due to cosmetic imperfections.
- Donating excess food: Consumers can reduce FLW by donating excess food to food banks or other organisations that help to distribute food to those in need. This can help to reduce the amount of food that goes to waste.
- Supporting sustainable practices: Consumers can support sustainable farming practices by buying locally-grown produce and products, or products that are certified as sustainably produced. This can help reduce the number of resources used to produce and transport food, which in turn can reduce FLW.

Overall, consumer behaviour can play a crucial role in reducing FLW at a systemic scale by promoting more sustainable practices and reducing the amount of food that goes to waste.

By making small changes in their own behaviour, consumers can help to create a more sustainable food system that wastes less food and resources.

The project aims to gather data and identify solutions to reduce food waste at consumer-level, including household and food services (or 'away-from-home'). Some of the guiding questions include:

- The identification of (new) drivers of consumer FW and levers for behavioural change (supported by the work performed by the EU Consumer Food Waste Forum, see section 2.2.5);
- Research and data collection on interventions to prevent and reduce consumer food waste, particularly in EU Member States;
- Evaluation of the identified interventions based on their feasibility, reach, and effectiveness;
- Definition of research protocols and recommendations for effective interventions and further research, to be tailored and carried out at national and regional-levels;
- Development of a compendium of multi-dimensional, multi-level, and evidence-based set of tools that can be applied by the EU Member States, as well as regional and local administrations.

This WG should provide concrete expectations in terms of policies supporting:

- Reduction of over-purchasing;
- Proper storage and handling of food;
- Purchasing products regardless of aesthetics;
- Donations of food surplus;
- Locally-produced food.

3.2 Ad-hoc interviews

Despite the aforementioned WG meetings enabling the ZeroW policy team to gather a lot of valuable inputs and insights from food chain actors and policymakers, it was assessed that some additional exchanges and investigation would be needed to, namely, inform the ZeroW modelling work (see section 1.4.1), as specific could not be obtained in a wider conversation group, given time and availability constraints. For this reason, the ZeroW policy team collectively decided to hold ad-hoc interviews with representatives of specific sectors of the food chain at the EU-level, statistics and research institutions (Eurostat, JRC), projects (e.g., EU Consumer Food Waste Forum), and international organisations (e.g., FAO).

Although engagement activities were not successful with all organisations, the interviews that took place were very fruitful; the results of these have, together with inputs gathered during WG meetings, contributed to inform the alternative pathways described in section 2.6. Interview grids for the interviews have been designed and can be found under appendix 2.

Overall, targeted stakeholders can be found under Figure 17³: some stakeholders were very responsive, and interviews could be organised (*light green*), while others were not available but were engaged through other means (*green*) (e.g., bilateral informal interactions, exchanges of resources via emails, etc.). In particular, the ZeroW policy team could deepen its interactions with JRC and Eurostat through WG meetings and interactions within the EU platform on FLW and the Advisory Group on SFS (meetings of these groups have been listed under section 1.4.5). The latter also provided useful insights regarding public positions of interest groups and stakeholders that the ZeroW policy team could not interview (*dark green*) concerning, among other things, the setting of mandatory EU FLW reduction targets.

As regards consumers, the authors of the present report highlight the important work undertaken by the EU Consumer Food Waste Forum, which shed light on many initiatives and actively contributed to the conversation on consumer behaviours through its many publications (see chapter on 2.5.5).

³ The ZeroW WP8 team organised interviews with the following organisations: COPA-COGECA, EUCOFEL, EUROCOMMERCE, EUROCOOP, EIT-Food. The other organisations providing feedback for our work through other means are: EIP AGRI, FOODDRINK EUROPE, the JRC.

Figure 17 Overview of targeted stakeholders

3.3 Other consultation processes

In parallel to the standardised approach described above, the ZeroW policy team leader (SAFE) engaged with several EU-funded projects in the GD-SO and CCN network such as FOODRUS and SISTERS on preliminary conversations concerning policy recommendations, as part of the activities described in section 1.4.5. These useful discussions helped centralise received feedback and share best practices with other projects.

Moreover, the policy team networks engaged in discussions to monitor ongoing policy changes throughout the 2023 calendar year's work period. SAFE's collaboration with the 'Prevent Waste Coalition' – a group of Civil Society Organisations like the European Environmental Bureau, Zero Waste Europe, and Feedback Global/Feedback EU – and start-ups, notably 'Too Good To Go' which leads in food waste (FW) reduction, has been pivotal. They are dedicated to advocating for the reduction of FLW and striving for ambitious policy goals to fulfil SDG 12.3. This partnership has enabled the ZeroW project to stay informed about political and policy shifts, especially regarding the ongoing revision of the WFD, and has enriched the conversation with valuable perspectives from civil society.

3.4 Timeline

A first round of 14 Working Group meetings was held from May 2023 to July 2023, following the calendar shown in tables 6, 7 and 8.

WG meetings were organised twice a month and qualitative panel of contributors/stakeholders, representing (as explained above) all actors of the food chain. ZeroW SILLs representatives and other WPLs were also invited to provide presentations for *ad hoc* contributions to the WG meetings.

Policy

Wed 10 May 2023	Introduction of the ZeroW project, objective of the WG and timeline
Wed 24 May 2023	Emil Beddari (Future in Our Hands, NO)
Wed 7 June 2023	Eva Sali (COPA COGECA), Maria Del Mar Catedra (Andalusian Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water, and Rural Development)
Wed 21 June 2023	Claudia Giordano (Department of Agricultural and Food Sciences, University of Bologna)
Wed 5 July 2023	Pr. Iva Pires (Associate Professor, New University of Lisbon) Pr. Bent Egberg Mikkelsen (Professor of Urban Food Systems Transformation, University of Copenhagen)

Table 6 Timeline Policy WG

Note: Due to technical difficulties during the e-meeting, Pr Iva Pires' presentation could not take place. Inputs have been gathered afterwards.

Innovation

Thu 11 May 2023	Introduction of the ZeroW project, objective of the WG and timeline
Thu 25 May 2023	Clara Cicatiello (LOWINFOOD project, University of Tuscia), Kata Trifkovic (Inlecom)
Thu 8 June 2023	Johan Hulten (IVL – Swedish Environmental Institute)
Thu 22 June 2023	WP4 Presentation (BIOS), SILL4 (ILVO)

Table 7 Timeline Innovation WG

Consumer Behaviour

Fri 12 May 2023	Introduction of the ZeroW project, objective of the WG and timeline
Fri 26 May 2023	Laura Garcia Herrero (JRC- European Commission)
Fri 9 June	Sophie Attwood (World Resource Institute)
Fri 23 June	Maria Rossanna (Emilia Romagna Region), Lilli Renner (European Food Banks Federation)
Fri 7 July	Mor Zarbiv (Municipality of Tel-Aviv)

Table 8 Timeline Consumer Behaviour WG

Furthermore, the *ad hoc* interviews were organised throughout the course of October-November 2023 to follow-up on the WG feedback. Meetings with networks and EU institutions happened during the entire year (see Appendix 4).

4. Building alternative pathways

ZeroW aims to contribute to the halving the per capita food waste levels by 2030, in line with the Farm-to-fork strategy and EU Green Deal. On the short-term (i.e. by the end of the project in 2025), we collectively aim to reduce FW by 20% at retail and by 25% at consumer level through our SILLs; whilst on the medium-term (i.e.. 2030) we aim to contribute to the 50% reduction of per capita FW at retail and consumer levels and, on the long-term i.e., we wish to reach a situation of near-zero per capita FW.

The medium- and long-term objectives cannot be met with ZeroW innovations alone, and have to be reached by taking into account a number of factors and variables that determine current food systems in the EU and that will evolve over time. These factors include inflation on food prices, demography, trade (imports/exports) at EU- and global-scale, (global) geopolitics, climate change, etc. It is thus paramount to examine the alternative developments of food systems from production to consumption, including feedback and inputs from various expert stakeholders from the agrifood sector, to illustrate what could be a conceivable future without FW.

Using the methodology described in the above sections and resources gathered and listed in this report, we developed three distinct scenarios or “pathways” looking into the future. These assumptions will not only help inform the FLW modelling and simulations ran in upcoming tasks of the ZeroW, they will also serve as a basis for future conversations with ZeroW partners and stakeholders to tackle challenges of today and, ultimately, determine what a ‘just’ transition towards near-zero FW can be, including all dimensions of sustainability (economic, social, environmental).

Despite building on the trend pathway described above, these scenarios are in no way forecast but present different ways of dealing with the required change in consumers eating, purchase and waste disposal habits; in innovation from a business model point of view as well as from the technological point of view; and in policies, with their many broad or precise reach and varying level of obligations.

4.1 About levels of change in policies

As far as public policies are concerned, the need to investigate various approaches becomes key as societal challenges are multifaceted and dynamic. A singular policy prescription may not suffice in addressing the complex and evolving nature of FLW reduction issues. Therefore, a careful investigation demands a nuanced understanding that can only be achieved through the exploration of different policy approaches. By scrutinising a range of approaches, we ought to shed light on synergies, identify potential bottlenecks, and tailor solutions that are adaptive to the intricacies of the issue at hand.

Investigating different approaches allows for a more inclusive and culturally sensitive policymaking process where strategies are developed to resonate with the many specific cultural, economic, and social characteristics of EU communities. In essence, a comprehensive exploration of distinct policy approaches is fundamental to crafting sustainable, resilient, adaptable, and socially equitable solutions for the multifaceted challenges posed by FLW management.

Voluntary commitments have emerged in the past decades in EU policy-making to complement, and in some case replace, as new policy instruments, the somewhat “old-fashioned” traditional hierarchical top-down mechanisms and legal norms (i.e. regulations, directives), “shifting (some) responsibility to private actors”. (Lenschow and Rottmann, 2005, p.3). As they are not legally binding and do not define the exact mechanisms, technologies or institutional arrangements to reach an agreed target, they allow for a lot of flexibility while still being subject to public controls on the basis of good will and co-decision on intermediate steps. They are therefore defined as hanging in a low level of hierarchy as far as legal norms are concerned but present a high degree of public-private cooperation and consequently are more likely to inspire trust and support from a significant segment of the private sector. Used as another of these “soft” instruments, **financial incentives** (both for private sector entities and consumers at large) can jointly contribute to shift business or consumers behaviours, as well as provide support to innovation and research in the private sector – although the impact of these should always be compared to the actual ambitions phrased in the terms of the instruments used by public authorities designing such policies as, for instance, practices such as “greenwashing” have been called out more and more in recent years (Ramus and Montiel, 2005, pp. 377-378).

On the other hand, **mandatory policies**, sometimes referred to as “hard” policy tools, are legally binding with precise obligations, which present a much smaller level of flexibility in the implementation of change measures (Zentner, 2017, p.18), but allow for a stricter follow-up on common EU objectives.

All the above tools have already been explored in the field of FLW management, in different forms to design different measures (informational, collaborative, organisational, regulatory, economic or technical instruments). Below, we list but a few of those, which were often referred to and mentioned in the ZeroW external stakeholders’ engagement process described in the previous section (section 3.1), and namely highlighted by Carmen Priefer, Juliane Jörissen and Klaus-Rainer Braütigam (Priefer et al., 2016):

- Setting targets (voluntary or mandatory), which are helpful to raise awareness, stimulate attention and mobilise political action; more importantly, they are pivotal to assess progress and evaluate the fitness and effectiveness of implemented FLW reduction measures and whether efforts have to be made;
- Improving data collection and sources, by harmonising data measurement with (mandatory) criteria and uniform expression of data (i.e. using same units of measurement, the same definitions of terms) for food waste as well as food loss;
- Establishing horizontal coordination of FLW management in the FSC, to increase efficiency and reduce (as much as possible) governance imbalance between FSC actors (including consumers);
- Reviewing ongoing food safety regulations to account for the waste production potentially generated by food safety regulations, e.g. with regards to date-marking/expiry dates;
- Acting on marketing standards and unfair trading practices;
- Supporting short(er) supply chains that foster closer links between food producers and consumers;
- Reviewing tax regulations that potentially hinder FLW prevention and encourage businesses not to follow the FW hierarchy, e.g. VAT exemptions on edible food surpluses used as by-products or bioenergy materials, when they could be resold or redistributed to humans;
- Introducing (new) taxes on waste management, e.g. ‘Polluter Pays Principle’ (PPP)-derived taxes;
- Implementing more efficient food waste management routines in public services, hospitals, restaurants and other food services, including menu planning, awareness-raising to both staff and consumers;

- Promoting food redistribution programmes for charitable organisations and food banks.

Each FW pathway will explore a specific variation of change, with differences in the implementation of the above policies: firstly (P1), we look into a scenario that follows current EU ambitions from the latest positions provided by the co-legislators (*“pragmatic” approach*); secondly (P2), we look into a future where more obligations/mandatory rules are put on food system actors, from MS to private actors (*“vertical” approach*); thirdly (P3), we explore a pathway where change would mostly rely on voluntary commitments and financial incentives (*“horizontal” approach*).

4.2 About levels of change in innovation

Innovation is pivotal in addressing FW reduction, as it plays a central role in developing and implementing sustainable practices across the entire FSC. As sometimes rightfully observed (Bilali, 2018), it is however quite a misleading term which requires a definition: as the OECD and Eurostat put it, innovation is *“the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service), or process, a new marketing method, or a new organisational method in business practices, workplace organisation or external relations”* (OECD and Eurostat, 2005, p. 46).

Innovation thus refers to both technological and non-technological implementation of progress. Technological advancements contribute to increased resource-efficiency in production, reduced environmental impact, and minimised waste. The integration of digital technologies, data analytics, and artificial intelligence further facilitates smart decision-making, optimising resource allocation and reducing inefficiencies. Collaborative efforts among stakeholders, including farmers, researchers, policymakers, and technology developers, are essential to foster an environment where continuous innovation leads to a more sustainable and resilient agro-food system that can meet the growing demands of a rapidly expanding global population while safeguarding the planet's ecosystems.

However, non-technological innovation also plays a very important role in shaping change in food systems, as social and organisational innovations are likely to drive transition to sustainability or, rather, as technological innovation alone is unlikely to change food systems paradigms where poverty or environmental impacts are treated as a consequence rather than a constitutive factor (iPES FOOD, 2015, p. 16).

Building on the reports from the ZeroW SILLs and FW generation barriers and opportunities, the ZeroW policy team presents in each pathway a specific variation of change of approaches, where the relationship between innovation and sustainability is presented in different ways: firstly (P1), we examine a scenario where innovation is seen as a means of developing new products, production or management processes, services, techniques that produce business value (in economic terms), in a conscious search for a decrease of environmental impact of food systems (i.e.. a *“green growth” approach*); secondly (P2), we look into a pathway where (non-)technological innovation is driven by social, environmental or sustainability concerns (or *“sustainability first” approach*); thirdly (P3), we observe a pathway where innovation is viewed as a driver of FW reduction and where new products, services, technologies, techniques, etc. produce inherently social, economic and environmental benefits (or a *“solutionist” approach*).

4.3 About levels of change in consumer behaviours

Transformation in consumer behaviours and whole relationship towards FW is also required to enact change in a holistic way. With an increasing awareness of environmental sustainability and a desire to contribute to global efforts in minimizing FW, more conscientious practices are emerging and developing mindful food consumption habits, “zero waste” practices at individual and household levels, greater emphasis on meal planning, proper storage techniques, re-use/revalorization of leftovers, “ugly” products consumption, etc. This positive trend will nonetheless be impacted by trends, awareness-raising, and thus, overall, by the wider food environments in which consumers live, consume and dispose of food.

As the High Level panel of Expert on Food Security and Nutrition (HLPE) from the Committee on World Food Security (CFS) defines it in a recent report(a *“food environment refers to the physical, economic, political and socio-cultural surroundings, opportunities and conditions that create everyday prompts, shaping people’s dietary preferences and choices as well as nutritional status”*. In summary, the context *“in which consumers engage with the food system to make their decisions about acquiring, preparing and consuming food”* and, therefore disposing of it. (HLPE-FSN, 2017, p. 28).

Therefore, talking about consumers change requires discussing more than awareness-raising and education programmes. It is also important to look at food entry points, i.e. the physical spaces (including infrastructures) where food is purchased/obtained (e.g. restaurants, food services, retail shops, wholesale markets, charities, etc.). One ought to also discuss the personal determinants of food choices (e.g. income, education, values, etc.) within norms (social, political, cultural...).

Finally, food environments need to be looked at through the lens of the market, and evaluate its role in driving change: it has long been discussed (how change in (consumer) demand would influence change in production and marketing of food products and food infrastructures (King and Venturini, 2005, p. 18). Hence, in a *market-driven approach*, any change will be based on an adaptation to the preferences and behaviours of actors, i.e. consumers on most occasions). A *“driving market” approach*, on the other hand, “implies influencing the structure of the market and/or the behaviour(s)” through soft power, regulations or incentives to create a change (Jaworski et al., 2000, p. 45). A choice of approach will greatly impact the level of change in consumer behaviours, as well as other factors including economic growth, environmental impacts and inclusivity of food systems.

Relying on the identified drivers and levers of consumer FW identified in the above sections, each FW pathway below will explore a specific variation of change of approaches: firstly (P1), we look into a scenario that where a market driven approach is secured with a high degree of investment in innovation, and research, coupled to a few market adjustment measures and policies (*“semi-interventionist” approach*); secondly (P2), we look into a future where a set of rules are adopted to regulate markets following a driving market approach through “harder” policy instruments, from MS to private actors (*“dirigist” approach*); thirdly (P3), we explore a pathway that mostly relies on soft power, economic incentives and education and awareness-raising programmes to spark consumer behaviour changes (*“market-driven” approach*).

4.4 Formulating alternative pathways

As described above, the alternative pathways that we have conceptualised combine a set of three distinct approaches to (or levels of) change that may apply in the future, in the areas of EU policy-making on FLW, FLW innovation and consumer behaviours. These different approaches result from careful assessment of existing literature on the topic of FLW management in policy-making, sustainability innovation and consumers studies (as reported in section 2.2), which we matched to our exchanges with external stakeholders (in the working group meetings and interview sessions described in section 2.4).

Approach with regards to...	Pathway 1	Pathway 2	Pathway 3
Policies	<i>Pragmatic</i>	<i>Vertical</i>	<i>Horizontal</i>
Innovation	<i>Green growth</i>	<i>“Sustainability first”</i>	<i>Solutionism</i>
Consumer behaviour	<i>Semi-interventionism</i>	<i>Dirigisme</i>	<i>Market-driven</i>

Table 9 Conceptualisations of the different pathways

These alternative pathways have purposely been described in discriminating (or even polarised) terms, in all three key areas. As stated above, these scenarios are in no way forecast, nor are they recommendations or the only options available to future FSC actors, innovators and policymakers. They merely present a framework in which we can build scenarios that will be explored through our future ZeroW modelling, and serve as a basis for conversations about what a ‘just’ transition pathway would be – which may end up being another pathway, yet to be formulated.

We nonetheless hope to present varying options from which to develop concepts and research in the near future, in the framework of the upcoming reports of the ZeroW project.

Figure 18 Visualisation of the three alternative pathways

4.4.1 Pathway 1- "Green growth": market-drive policy innovation for sustainable FW reduction

In this first pathway, a pragmatic approach to policies on FW reduction is proposed, acknowledging the slow progress toward Sustainable Development Goal 12.3. The focus is on setting mandatory targets at various stages of the FSC, with a combination of legally binding targets and ambitious voluntary agreements. The policy addresses the complexities of implementation, economic impacts, and the need for coordinated national strategies. The proposed targets, expressed as percentage changes from a baseline average of 2020-2022 to 2032, cover processing, manufacturing, retail, and consumption stages. The scope differentiates between retail and consumption, considering concerns about accountability. The scenario also emphasises improving data collection, adjusting FW definitions, and supporting measurement at the food redistribution level. Furthermore, the proposal assumes a continuation of existing processes for FLW management coordination, reviews of food safety regulations, and support for short(er) supply chains. The scenario integrates a green growth and innovation perspective, linking economic growth with environmental and social considerations. It envisions identifying best practices, promoting social/environmental enterprises, and addressing unfair trading practices. Additionally, the scenario assumes an interventionist approach to influence consumer behaviours through awareness-raising, nudging strategies, training, and social influences. The emphasis is on market-driven policies coupled with public investments in innovation and research, aligning with a green growth strategy.

A pragmatic approach to policies

In this part of the scenario, we follow a trend based on ongoing developments from the latest positions provided by the co-legislators, adapted to upcoming challenges with the support of stakeholders' inputs. As already highlighted by the EC and the JRC in their impact assessment towards the revision of the WFD, progress by governments and companies in achieving the SDG 12.3 goal has been slow (Stroodsnijder et al., 2023, p. 2). Only a few front-runner MSs are still in good position to achieve significant progress by 2030, and while a majority of MSs have actions in place at national and local level to tackle FW, few have developed coordinated national strategies or roadmaps. In cases where such plans exist, the EC assessed that monitoring and evaluation of progress is still limited as targets and indicators have often been absent. In such circumstances, one ought to consider a pragmatic option: to consider the above assessment as a "reality-checked" baseline for action and adapt

FW reduction objectives to this updated state-of-play, while trying to maintain high FW reduction ambitions.

A. Setting targets – Mandatory targets at processing, manufacturing, retail and consumption stages, complemented by more ambitious voluntary agreements: as EC policymakers have recalled on many occasions, setting targets and measurement mechanisms is key to achieve success, as well as mindfully accepting the extent of the problem and the need to find effective solutions – in one word: ‘act’. In the case of FW reduction, as Sanne Stroodsnijder, Toine Timmermans (Wageningen University and Research) and Richard Swannell (WRAP UK) put it in a recent presentation to the EU platform on Food Loss and Waste (Stroodsnijder et al., 2023, p. 2), the favoured approach is to set FW reduction targets, measure FW to identify hotspots and monitor progress of reduction, all-the-while taking action on these hotspots. The pragmatic element of P1 lies in the answers to several questions: which FSC stages are these objectives targeting (i.e. their scope)? How are targets formulated (i.e. their expression) and *when* should they be achieved? Answers should account for the complexity of the measures that have to be put in place in all EU MS and which will have a major economic impact on businesses (including SMEs), social legislation and employment, to name but a few considerations.

These questions were asked by the EC to stakeholders during the public consultation process ahead of the WFD revision. In this scenario, we suggest answers to these questions, motivated by a pragmatic approach that takes into consideration the current political “climate” and the likely compromises between co-legislators and political groups, while at the same time ensuring that the overarching objectives of the ZeroW (i.e. reaching a near-zero FW status by 2050) are met.

- Scope: in P1, we consider current trends that lean towards the creation of voluntary agreements (Goossens et al., 2019)) with ambitious targets (50% for retail and consumption, in line with SDG 12.3; 25% for manufacturing/processing, in line with the (FAO, 2023), arguably more likely to stimulate and support private sector actions, especially in the retail, hospitality/food services and food redistribution sectors. P1 considers using such agreements with all good-willing actors of the FSC, with an emphasis on the creation of roadmaps for the above-mentioned sectors. However, as the EC pointed out, progress from some EU MS has still been limited as regards FW prevention and reduction with the absence of strategic plans, which is why P1 does not only rely on voluntary agreements but also on legally binding targets for EU MS, expressed for the retail and consumer stages (i.e. considering the initial scope of SDG

12.3) with the addition of processing and manufacturing (usually considered as “low-hanging fruits” as they have an inherent economic incentive to reduce FW (European Commission, 2023, November 22, p.177):

Food waste reduction target on:	Mandatory FW reduction target (expression)	Voluntary FW reduction target (expression)
Primary production	n/a	n/a
Processing and manufacturing	10% (absolute amounts in mass units)	25% (absolute amounts in mass units)
Retail	30% (per capita)	50% (per capita)
Consumption	30% (per capita)	50% (per capita)

Table 10 FW reduction targets in P1

Target levels are set in accordance with the EC proposal for a revision of the WFD. We exclude primary production from the scope: P1 considers feedback from stakeholders of the primary production sector, arguing that farmers have no reason to discard a valuable product, always attempt to optimise their trade and produce FW only when it is unavoidable due to factors beyond their control (e.g. last-minute cancellation of orders from buyers). We also chose to differentiate retail and consumption stages to reflect the views of some participants to the ZeroW external stakeholders WG fearing that the retail sector could be held accountable for slow progress on household FW reduction, and could on the other hand achieve greater results in FW reduction if considered as a separate category. This would arguably create confusion between what is considered retail FW and what can be attributed to consumption only; such an approach would require taking another look at FW definitions to clearly define liabilities of FW production and, consequently, responsibilities with regards to FW reduction.

- Expression: P1 uses targets that are formulated as percentages of change between the baseline (average between baseline year 2020 and 2022) and the target date (see below) of 2032.
- Target dates for FW reduction: as regards to the baseline year to measure progress, P1 considers an average between data reported in 2020 (first year of EU-wide mandatory measurement of FW) and 2022, as it has been argued by stakeholders that the COVID crisis and geopolitical events have impacted FW production at all stages of the FSC. As regards to the target date, we chose to postpone it to 2032, as many stakeholders are considering that the remaining time towards 2030 (as per SDG 12.3) is too short

to achieve progress. Two more years are added to the initial SDG agenda to account for the entry into force and transcription process of the Directive.

B. Improving data collection and sources – Adjusting current FW definitions and provide greater public support to measurement at food redistribution level: P1

considers the current harmonised FW measurement framework at EU level, with the methodology laid down in Commission delegated decision (EU) 2019/1597 and implemented by Commission implementing decision (EU) 2019/2000. However, we introduce an additional element concerning the need for a definition of ‘avoidable’ and ‘unavoidable’ FW called for by some stakeholders (currently lacking) which would help clarify the distinction between food that is wasted and could technically be used for human consumption (e.g. “ugly” fruits discarded at retail sector) and residues of food that has been eaten (e.g. chicken bones from households). This would introduce new shades in the harmonised measurement methodology and improve the overall quality of the data. P1 does not introduce measurement of food loss, echoing remarks from stakeholders putting the feasibility of this measure in question given the limited resources, time and capacity of the primary production sector. We note that such a claim has also been made by the food redistribution sector (in particular, charities). In this case, we could not exclude food redistribution FW from the overall obligation of measurement for consistency reasons. However, P1 should therefore include measures by public authorities to support food redistribution FW measurement in an effective way.

P1 also provided some basic assumptions regarding the following policy items on the basis of current trends:

Actions	Assumptions
Establishment of horizontal coordination of FLW management in the FSC	The processes in place (Advisory groups, Stakeholder discussion groups, public consultations, EU conferences) are maintained as they are, with a wider involvement of FSC actors.
Review of ongoing food safety regulations (e.g. date-marking/expiry dates)	Existing rules are adapted to maximise consumers understanding of expiry dates as they largely remain unclear. P1 suggests that date-marking is addressed through a change of back-of-pack labels with greater information to consumers regarding the freshness of their products. Other food safety rules are

	maintained, but new FW reduction processes are evaluated and authorised upon positive scientific opinion from the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).
Support to short(er) supply chain	The existing instruments to support SMEs in the EU are maintained and practical implementing policies (such as subsidies, tax reduction or other economic incentives) are undertaken voluntarily by MSs and regional authorities.
Review of tax regulations to support FLW prevention and encourage businesses to follow the FW hierarchy	VAT exemptions on edible food surpluses are applied in all EU MSs, but they apply on FW used as by-products or bioenergy materials as well as for food donations, ie. regardless of the waste hierarchy.
Introduction of new taxes on waste management	P1 does not foresee the introduction of new taxes on waste management for polluters.
Implementing more efficient food waste management routines in public services, hospitals, restaurants and other food services	Policies support awareness raising campaigns in public services to target staff members, and put in place <i>ad hoc</i> measures including monitoring framework (targets, reporting of progress linked with the FSC sector, see FW reduction targets)
Promoting food redistribution programmes for charitable organisations and food banks.	Policies support awareness raising campaigns to promote donations to food banks and charities, and support the creation of bilateral voluntary agreements between retail sector actors and food redistribution actors.

Table 11 Key policy assumptions in P1

Green growth and innovation

In this part of our first scenario, we examine a pathway where innovation is seen as a means of developing new products, production or management processes, services, techniques that produce business value (in economic terms), in a conscious search for a decrease of environmental impact of food systems (i.e. a “green growth” approach).

Green growth is defined by OECD as “fostering economic growth and development while ensuring that natural assets continue to provide the resources and environmental services on

which our well-being relies" (OECD, 2018), and as a practical and flexible approach to support sustainable development. Its main action levers to do so are: the enhancement of productivity by creating incentives to, among other things, reduce waste; the improvement of investor confidence with a higher predictability of markets taking into account environmental challenges; the opening of new markets by stimulating demand for "green" goods; the contribution to fiscal consolidation through the mobilisation of revenues of green taxes and the cancellation of subsidies to harmful practices; the reduction of risks of negative shocks to growth due to shortages of resources or damages to the environment (OECD, 2011).

As far as innovation is concerned, P1 suggests that it will be motivated by a "green growth" approach where, to put it in simply, environmental protection and social considerations are listed as parameters to take into account under an overarching vision of economic growth relying on expanding businesses and markets, which would drive sustainability forward. Innovative practices driving this change would therefore rely on a set of trends:

A. Best practices identification: Such a vision requires the development of the identification of "best practices" in FW reduction and the construction of databases, which are already being reported by existing programmes (e.g. through R&I projects like CHORIZO (Chorizo Project, 2022) and networks (e.g. the EU FLW Prevention Hub (European Commission, n.d.-f)).

B. Development of (new) forms of social/environmental enterprises: P1 sees a wide development of social/environmental enterprises aimed to reduce FW and/or redistribute food surpluses (e.g. [Too Good To Go](#), [Phenix](#), [Happy Hours Market](#)), i.e. profit-oriented companies with a specific social/environmental objective serving its primary purpose – maximising profit while benefiting society and the environment by reducing FW. Based on (innovative) business models, these would, in turn, use profits made to fund social programs. This entails a growth in subsidies for SMEs and R&I programs, as well as a wide promotion of these actors (facilitated access to market, creation of specific work categories for such SMEs in fiscal legislation, etc.).

C. Actions against Unfair trading practices – In P1, the EU authorities and MS would focus on a better conceptualisation of FW though a difference between 'avoidable' and 'unavoidable' FW. 'Avoidable' FW occurring because of unfair trading practices between FSC actors would largely be targeted by the market through the voluntary commitments of FSC actors themselves, and public mechanisms of intervention would target surpluses in the

market to reduce unavoidable FW. Public measures would focus on unavoidable FW and create new business opportunities with regards to unavoidable FW management.

Overall, innovative businesses and markets, in this scenario, would pay attention not only to the technical dimension of innovation, but also to the social, environmental and organisational dimensions – but innovative practices would only be implemented if correlated with economic growth and profitability on the medium- or long-term.

Influencing consumer behaviours: an interventionist approach

To support the Green growth approach described above, this scenario assumes that the political space within the EU would adopt a market-driven approach to policy-making which would at the same time secure a high degree of (primarily) public investments in innovation and research, coupled to a few market adjustment measures. This pathway assumes, in essence, a situation that abides with Keynes law in macroeconomics (Keynes, 1936), i.e. a situation where changes in aggregate demand cause changes in supply.

Such an approach would be adopted towards consumer behaviours as well - it is assumed that consumer demand would shape changes in how food environments evolve. Thus, P1 considers that, rather than being directly shaped and, in a way, “manufactured” by policies, markets evolve on their own; in this situation, governments and EU policymakers are expected to take an “interventionist” stance, i.e. a system based on the limited use of political means to address problems identified with free markets and to influence them to solve specific problems and induce a certain outcome (Ikeda, 2004).

Consequently, P1 assumes that EU institutions and EU MS would keep working on the central role of consumer level solutions to reduce FW, with increased measures to target households, both at home and away from home (including the ones developed in the ECFWF compendium created by the JRC and described in section 2.2.5). These would include awareness-raising campaigns, wider education programmes (in schools and at work), promotion of date-marking information and food donation practices, etc. They would also be complemented by market measures rooting from policy initiatives, such as the creation of (more) incentives for FSC actors to valorise their FW towards consumers. In this scenario, businesses would react in a positive way to such measures as they would provide more economically viable solutions and options to reduce FW.

As noted by one JRC author participating to ZeroW Consumer Behaviour WG (JRC, 2023, July 31), awareness-raising campaigns *per se* are not very successful and would need a few nudging elements (rooting from interventions of innovation and policies) to succeed. P1

therefore assumes that consumer behaviours would evolve towards a reduction of household FW, provided that they are supported by other changes (among others), such as the use of smaller package sizes and improved packaging or product naming in shops; the use of a reformed date-marking system on food packaging; the dissemination and wide use of smart fridges/kitchens or FW calculators in households, ...

The JRC (2023, July 31) listed areas of opportunities under a set of different types of intervention. P1 refers to this base work to suggest a set of actions:

Consumer FW reduction - Types of intervention	Areas of opportunity for action under P1
Awareness-raising	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emphasise through different communication strategies the environmental consequences of food waste to generate better attitudes. - Emphasise food waste-related issues to raise awareness. - Improve consumers' perceptions of their role in food waste reduction. - Emphasise food waste-related issues to trigger guilt, concern and other personal emotions (positive or negative). <p>Such actions would be shared through apps and virtual platforms, and shared in public-funded events and workshops.</p>
Nudging strategies and changes to the consumer choice architecture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design environments that nudge consumers towards food waste reduction practices, with minimal mandatory requirements to FSC actors in contact with consumers. Examples: restaurants decorated with food waste awareness messages. - Provide affordable technologies and tools (e.g. smart kitchen tools) to enable optimisation of food management, funded through public investments.
Training and knowledge enhancement	Introduce and promote meal planning and food storage methods, cooking skills and food waste reduction tips in educational and community-based initiatives, through the promotion of short videos, the gamification of FW reduction

	practices, the promotion of storage solutions that facilitate consumption, of easy tips, ...
Social influences – showing what others have done	Promote in-person and online community activities to disseminate good practices for reduction of household food waste and food management advice and run awareness-raising campaigns on the environmental consequences of food waste, through social sharing platforms or cooking shows.

Table 12 Areas of opportunity for action under P1 (adapted from JRC, 2023, July 31)

In P1, interventions involving awareness-raising, nudging strategies, training and knowledge enhancement and social influences would be driven by the public sector along with funding to R&I. It is thus a scenario where authorities mostly rely on improved information to consumers to develop an increased awareness on FW issues, and consequently spark behavioural changes towards individual FW reduction.

4.4.2 Pathway 2 – Changing the rules: structural governance shift for near-zero food waste

In this second distinct pathway (P2), the focus shifts towards a vertical policy integration approach for FW reduction, envisioning a future where high-level policy-makers, especially EU institutions, assign FW reduction objectives to various sectors. This approach involves mandatory reporting mechanisms and infringement procedures for non-compliance. P2 sets a uniform 50% FW reduction target by 2030, addressing the slow progress on SDG 12.3. It also emphasizes a comprehensive scope, encompassing primary production to consumption, with limited reliance on voluntary agreements. The proposal advocates for improved data collection, extended producer responsibility, and a sustainability-first innovation approach. It envisions a dirigiste scenario, where state intervention influences consumer behaviour through awareness-raising, nudging strategies, training, and social influences. The vision entails businesses adopting sustainable practices or facing fines, creating a structural shift toward FW reduction in the food environment. P2 emphasizes a societal commitment to near-zero FW by 2050, relying on stringent regulations and incentives for businesses to drive change.

A Vertical approach to policies

While P1 investigated a scenario following current EU ambitions from the latest positions provided by the co-legislators, P2 looks into a future where vertical and enforcement of policies integrating governance processes becomes a norm in FW management. Consequently, more obligations/mandatory rules are put on food system actors, from MS to private actors.

Assuming that potential lacks of policy coordination between policy makers and implementers, as it is often an important problem (Adam et al., 2019; Vince et al., 2017) are not undermining the implementation of policies and, thus, their effectiveness, P2 adopts a vertical policy integration approach, where FW reduction objectives are assigned into sectoral policies by high-level policy-makers (i.e.. EU institutions) instructing MSs and private actors to include new objectives into their policies; in this scenario, implementation is monitored through mandatory mechanisms for reporting, and failure to comply with obligations lead to infringement procedures (Giessen, 2011) Such an approach has the advantage of being cross-cutting and able to target environmental, energy, and trade policies in a uniform manner, thus increasing the efficiency of such policies towards the achievement of FW reduction objectives and addressing the most visible bottlenecks by integrating high-level backing of ambitions (especially where commitments – or concrete implementation of commitments – is lacking (May and Burby, 1996).

As recalled in the above P1, progress by governments and companies in achieving the SDG 12.3 goal has been slow. As policy competences to address FW are distributed between EU and national (and sometimes regional or local) levels (Schleyer et al., 2015, p. 176) and as participatory approaches have arguably often failed to achieve societal change by not challenging existing power relationships (Hickey and Mohan, 2005, p. 237), e.g. certain actors' interests are undermining the overarching objectives, P2 considers the adoption of a radical stance from policy-makers, who would seek to consider FW reduction as a priority objective of society. This would result in (highly) binding commitments which would strive go beyond existing explored measures.

A. Setting targets – Mandatory targets all stages of the FSC (“farm-to-fork”), with limited role of voluntary agreements: compared to P1, P2 answers the question of the scope and expression of FLW reduction in a more comprehensive manner, and puts the achievement of the targets as one of the priorities towards 2030, hence respecting the deadline date set by SDG 12.3 *stricto sensu* (as called for on several occasions by both the [European Parliament](#) and [Civil society organisations](#)) and extending the target scope to primary production (as interpreted by [Champions 12.3](#), an international coalition of executives from governments, businesses, and civil society leading global FW action, that has recommended states to interpret SDG 12.3 target as a 50% reduction in all FLW from farm to fork, including “food losses”). This approach takes into consideration the urgency of the FLW situation with regards to the amounts FW and the slow progress made.

- Scope: in P2, FW reduction target levels are set to a uniform 50% for the 2030 horizon, according to the SDG 12.3 target (for retail and consumption) and the Champions 12.3 interpretation (for pre-retail FW). In such a scenario, FW definition is assumed to change to fit the [FUSIONS definitional framework](#), hence including food wasted or lost at primary production level (see point B below). In P2, no distinction is made between consumption and retail stages, as per the current EC proposal for the WFD revision, acknowledging that consumption behaviours are difficult to grasp and influence as they largely depend on the context (Luchs et al., 2015).

Food waste reduction target on:	Mandatory 2030 FW reduction target (expression)	Voluntary 2030 FW reduction target (expression)	Mandatory 2050 FW reduction targets
Primary production	50% (absolute amounts in mass units)	For higher target levels	“Near-100%” (absolute amounts in mass units)

Processing and manufacturing	50% (absolute amounts in mass units)		"Near-100%" (absolute amounts in mass units)
Retail & consumption	50% (per capita)		"Near-100%" (absolute amounts in mass units)

Table 13 FW reduction targets in P2

Feedback from a CSO participant to the ZeroW Policy WG noted that the impact of voluntary agreements on FW reduction should not be overestimated: for instance, in the case of Norway, more than a hundred companies (representing 55% of the Norwegian market by trade volume) committed to yearly reporting of FW levels in 2015, supported by governmental departments. While the cooperation aimed to reduce per capita FW by 50% by 2030 (with sub-goals of 15% by 2020, and 30% by 2025), the reduction expected as the outcome of this joint commitment between governments and private sector proved to be lower, with 9,5% FW reduction achieved by 2020 (One Planet Network, 2023; Szulecka and Strøm-Andersen, 2021). Building on the assumption that voluntary agreements produce similar effects in the EU context, P2 gives a limited role to voluntary agreements, using them only to go beyond mandatory commitments and highlight progress made by frontrunners. In pursuit of the objective of the ZeroW project (i.e. near-zero FW by 2050), P2 also sets a FW reduction target of (almost) 100% by 2050. While the implementing steps towards this objective are not defined, this would set a commitment as well as an obligation for action on the longer-term, counterbalancing the challenges caused by the 2030 target and forcing policy-makers to design long-term, integrated solutions.

- **Expression:** P2 uses targets that are formulated as percentages of change between the baseline (2020) and the target date (see below) of 2030.
- **Target dates for FW reduction:** as regards the baseline year to measure progress, P2 considers the earliest available data reported in 2020 (first year of EU-wide mandatory measurement of FW), to avoid delays to the implementation of actions that would contribute to FW reductions. As regards the target date, P2 considers 2030, as called for by SDG 12.3.

B. Improving data collection and sources – Adjusting current FW definition, harmonise FLW measurement methodologies and report all FLW: as a way to address all FLW from farm to fork, definitions of “food loss” and “food waste” are assumed to change in P2, to fit the [FUSIONS definitional framework](#), hence including food wasted or lost at primary production level – i.e. harvest waste (FW left on field, animals/produce lost to disease, injury,

or poor harvesting techniques) and post-harvest waste (transport/on-farm processing, storage, transport, farm-gate). This would only leave pre-harvest FW out of the scope of the reduction targets (and thus, the measurement).

While it has been argued (see P1) that farmers have no reason to discard a valuable product and are therefore expected to always attempt to valorise food production surpluses (e.g. turning them into animal feed or fertilisers), stakeholders of the ZeroW Policy WG pointed out that there are factors beyond their control (e.g. economic dependence on retailers) that influence FLW generation at primary production level. To address these “unavoidable” FLW (from a farmer’s perspective), P2 assumes that more binding policy mechanisms will be put in place to balance power relationships between FSC actors (see table 14 below).

Participants to the ZeroW stakeholders working groups noted that additional the inclusion of mandatory FW reporting obligations for companies would also support a better understanding of FW dynamics in the EU. P2 therefore assumes that mandatory measurement of private FW levels of FSC actors would be effective and shared publicly through binding legal frameworks.

C. Extended Producer responsibility (EPR) as regards FW reduction: P2 assumes that more regulations will define responsibility of the private sector to prevent and reduce waste throughout the FSC, with food actors above a certain size being required by law to reduce FW according to the waste hierarchy; infringements in all stages of the FSC would be sanctioned by fines (although this would and could not be applied to household FW for quite obvious reasons), and/or would be required to take up financial responsibility of waste management. Such measures including sanctions are already being defined in some specific EU regions (e.g. in the case of the [Catalan law 3/2020 on Food Loss and Wastage Prevention](#)). As they arguably produce better results in existing schemes for environmental policies (Gupt and Sahay, 2015), P2 assumes that such an approach to EPR would develop more and more over the coming years.

P2 also provides some basic assumptions regarding the following policy items on the basis of current trends:

Actions	Assumptions
Establishment of horizontal coordination of FLW management in the FSC	Processes in place (Advisory groups, Stakeholder discussion groups, public consultations, EU conferences) are maintained as they are.
Review of ongoing food safety regulations (e.g. date-marking/expiry dates)	Existing rules are largely modified to maximise consumers understanding of expiry dates as they largely remain unclear and to extend producers' responsibility in FW management. P2 suggests clarifying "best before" and "use by" dates by using different (potentially coloured) labels. FSC actors would be obligated to donate unsold food under "best before" labels (provided it could still be consumed by humans, according to food safety considerations) and valorise products using "use by" labels according to the waste hierarchy. Food safety rules would be adapted to the objective of reducing FW, including different understanding of liability for end-of-chain actors (i.e. similar to the provisions of the 2016 <u>Gadda Law</u> in Italy).
Support to short(er) supply chain	The existing instruments to support SMEs in the EU are maintained with increased funding, and FSC using less than two intermediates between food producers and consumers are prioritised to receive financial support (such as subsidies, tax reduction or other economic incentives).
Review of tax regulations to support FLW prevention and encourage businesses to follow the FW hierarchy	VAT exemptions are harmonised in all EU MS, and apply to the donation of edible food surpluses to food banks or charities. No support is given to the use of FW for by-products or bioenergy materials, unless FSC actors can demonstrate that FW could not be used for human consumption.
Introduction of new taxes on waste management	<p>P2 assumes that the "Polluter Pays Principle" is applied to FW management, where FSC actors (except consumers) are required to pay for their FW, unless they can demonstrate that all measures to prevent, redistribute or reuse were taken according to the waste hierarchy.</p> <p>Local levies on FW generation are imposed on households (Lee, 2023)</p>

<p>Implementing more efficient food waste management routines in public services, hospitals, restaurants and other food services</p>	<p>Policies require public services, hospitals, restaurants and other food services to mandatorily draw out FW reduction plans with targets and implementing measures, in coordination with local authorities.</p>
<p>Promoting food redistribution programmes for charitable organisations and food banks.</p>	<p>FSC actors (except consumers) are required to donate FW to food banks or charities. Public-funded consumer-oriented awareness-raising campaigns on the benefit of food donation are widespread.</p>

Table 14 Key policy assumptions in P2

A “Sustainability First” approach in innovation

As regards the role of innovation in FW management towards near-zero, P2 assumes that it would be driven by social, environmental or sustainability concerns; in other words, society would adopt a radical “sustainable and social innovation” approach (El Bilali, 2018, pp. 206-207), where sustainability and social concerns are integrated into company processes and systems from the inception of a new idea all the way to its commercialisation, with economic profitability being considered as a second priority after sustainability criteria are met. These new ideas would be motivated by the goal of meeting social and sustainability needs.

New technologies would mostly focus on measuring households individual FW generation to facilitate awareness-raising to citizens, as well as reporting to authorities and potential support to taxation.

Like P1, P2 would also rely on a wide development of social/environmental enterprises aimed to reduce FW and/or redistribute food surpluses, made possible by a favourable, predictable binding FW management environment. Profits made would largely be reinvested in structural reinforcements to increase sustainable performance in FW reduction. While primarily driven by regulations and policies, it is to be envisaged that such a pathway would also see an increase of subsidies and fiscal incentives for social/environmental SMEs and R&I private programs.

Influencing consumer behaviours: a dirigiste approach

Building on a similar positive vision of the role of public interventions as P1, P2 proposes a dirigiste scenario where state intervention is viewed as an even greater catalysis of change and has a positive impact on collective behaviours. Such approaches have been historically documented (e.g. post-WWII France and Japan, to name a few, and challenged, as it relies on

a the capacity, in essence limited, of an elite of technocrats to centralise economic plans and effectively implement them (Ansaloni and Smith, 2018).

However, P2 considers a future where any approach assumes that the market is subject to failures or “glass ceilings” that prevent it from reaching ambitious goals (unless strictly directed towards them by rigid policies that suffer little compromises) and is controlled and streamlined in the EU-27, whereby EU and national levels would work hand-in-hand towards the achievement of the FW reduction objectives with a higher degree of collaboration between implementing authorities and “planning centres”.

Such a vision entails that other aspects of the economy (beyond FW management policies) would likely be planned, with controls on prices of goods and a supervision of labour markets, to control the direct and indirect effects of FW reduction measures on household incomes and well-being. As this turn is arguably developing in some sectors (namely, for strategic and geopolitical reasons, we think it is not unlikely that such a turn in visions is also adopted in food environments management (or food system planning, which still lack understanding) at least as far as FW reduction is concerned (Seidl and Schmitz, 2023; Sadler et al., 2014).

P2 proposes a vision of the future where consumer behaviours are shaped by a directed change to food environments, driven by scientific expertise and vertical policy-making, recognising the need for change in the structural and behavioural dimensions of producers.

Therefore, P2 assumes that EU institutions and EU MS would shift away from a vision where change in market behaviours is mostly attributed to adaptation to consumers purchase habits, to a vision where sustainable food environments are considered as the main drivers towards sustainability. Measures aimed to target households FW would consequently include more investments on changes to EU food environments through the development of public and private infrastructures for food donation and FW valorisation, on top of ambitious awareness-raising campaigns/ wider education programmes accompanied by concrete in-store measures to influence consumers purchase habits (e.g. prohibiting use of certain packaging, acting on product-placement in stores to promote FW-free products,...).

In this scenario, businesses would be financially incentivised to adopt such measures (both inherently through the positive financial outcome of reduced FW generation and practically by public fundings), resulting in a positive outcome (i.e. reduced consumer FW generation). Failure to adapt to such demands would result in fines or other similar infringement mechanisms active under coercive policy-making towards public and private actors.

Table 15 below lists different types of intervention that can be envisaged under P2 to affect consumer behaviour. These could include interventions already described under P1, but would also propose integrated solutions, such as:

Consumer FW reduction - Types of intervention	Areas of opportunity for action under P2
Awareness-raising	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emphasise through different communication strategies the environmental consequences of food waste to generate better attitudes. - Emphasise businesses responsibilities in food waste-related issues to raise awareness. - Emphasise food waste-related issues to trigger guilt, concern and other personal emotions (positive or negative). <p>Such actions would be shared through apps and virtual platforms, shared in public-funded events and workshops, but also displayed in stores as part of an integrated policy-making on food environments.</p>
Nudging strategies and changes to the consumer choice architecture	<p>Design environments that nudge consumers towards food waste reduction practices, with greater requirements to FSC actors in contact with consumers, eg. increased quality of food available in food services, reduced portions, providing plates of a shape and size that discourage the self-serving of large quantities of food.</p> <p>Foster the production of technologies and tools (e.g. smart kitchen tools) that enable optimisation of food management, funded through public investments, and limit production of other underperforming tools/technologies.</p>
Training and knowledge enhancement	Incorporation of FW management in school curricula.
Social influences	Use a “carrot and stick” approach, where businesses are socially rewarded and promoted for their contribution to FW reduction objectives, while being publicly pointed at for underperforming.

Table 15 Potential interventions for Consumer FW reduction under P2 (adapted from JRC, 2023, July 31)

Change in local food environments have been highlighted as a performing factor of consumers’ behavioural changes in some sectors, including public health (Mah et al., 2016; Kelly et al., 2011). In P2, interventions involving awareness-raising, nudging strategies,

training and knowledge enhancement and social influences would be driven by the public sector, primarily influencing businesses to shift their practices to design sustainable food environments where FW reduction practices would become the default choice for consumers. It is thus a scenario where authorities mostly rely on dirigiste policy-making and high commitments of businesses to shape customers habits.

4.4.3 Pathway 3 – Innovation first: teaming up for inclusive FW reduction

Lastly, this last alternative pathway (P3) presents a departure from traditional hierarchical policy-making, opting for a collaborative, bottom-up approach involving public authorities, consumers, FSC business actors, and research communities. This shift aims to address ongoing challenges, emphasizing the need for inclusive, ad hoc solutions while considering diverse stakeholder interests.

P3 strategically integrates FW reduction objectives into existing policies, relying on voluntary agreements and collaborative dialogues coordinated by EU public authorities. The proposed targets include ambitious voluntary agreements for FSC actors, leveraging a market-driven framework. The scenario highlights the importance of flexibility, incorporating incentive mechanisms, public-private collaboration, market-driven certification programs, and a dynamic regulatory framework. P3 embraces a solutionist approach, focusing on innovation as a key driver for FW reduction through technology integration. Additionally, the scenario underscores consumer education and awareness as pivotal, emphasizing the role of soft power, economic incentives, and education programs in influencing sustainable behaviours and reducing FW in food systems.

A horizontal, stakeholder-focused approach to policy-making

Unlike P2, P3 proposes a shift away from hierarchical and institutionalised forms of policy-making towards more informal forms of governance, including horizontal interactions between public authorities, consumers, FSC business actors and research communities, in order to collaboratively build adequate, bottom-up and *ad hoc* solutions to ongoing problems, while taking into account limitations, concerns and interests of different stakeholder groups. This approach is not new to policy-making and has been observed both at EU and international stage for years (Tosun and Lang, 2017).

The conceptualisation of EU policy integration has long been studied (Mahoney, 2008). It has been argued that when actors (in this case, FSC operators) are included in horizontal configurations where they themselves shape the conditions in which they operate, there is a risk that a perspective is prioritised over others or, rather that a perspective obstructs reflections and achievements of overarching objectives (Termeer, 2009, p. 302).

However, with challenges as complex as FW reduction, policy coherence across sectors is all-the-more paramount, and bringing all stakeholders on board is crucial. P3 assumes a

situation where a fully horizontal policy integration approach is successfully adopted, implying the incorporation of FW reduction objectives into sectoral policies, thus “greening” them by including environmental and social concerns (Giessen, 2011).

In P3, specific policy objectives are included in existing policies (Common Agricultural Policy, Common Fisheries Policy, etc.), and are implemented by FSC actors through the coordination (by EU public authorities) of dialogues leading to voluntary agreements. This collaborative approach would enjoy a high political acceptance from FSC stakeholders and policy-makers: voluntary agreements’ results would be closely examined and evaluated according to their efficiency, effectiveness and equity, although their empirical evaluation has sometimes proved complex (Cabugueira, 2001, pp. 130-131; Jiménez, 2007). Successful examples of such private sector actions have already been shared in existing platforms (e.g. presentation given in the EU FLW platform by WRAP UK) (Stroodsnijder et al., 2023).

Similarly to P1 and P2, P3 relies on the assumption that progress by governments and companies in achieving the SDG 12.3 goal has been slow; but unlike P1, P3 suggests that rather than adapting FW reduction objectives to this state-of-play, high FW reduction ambitions can be achieved through maximum cooperation of FSC actors in flexible legal frameworks.

A. Setting targets – Ambitious voluntary agreements for all FSC actors, complemented by mandatory targets at processing, manufacturing, retail and consumption stages, complemented:

- *Scope:* P3 assumes a high degree of support and commitment for SDG 12.3 (50% for retail and consumption, in line with SDG 12.3) from MS and the private sector. Like P1, P3 concretely relies on voluntary agreements between public authorities and the private sector, including roadmaps and performance indicators. However, P3 assumes that fewer legally binding instruments would be needed, especially stages excluded from the SDG 12.3 objectives and/or for which no data on FLW level is currently available (primary production; processing and manufacturing). In doing this, P3 acknowledges that most food business operators have no reason to discard food as long as it remains a valuable product, and always attempt to optimise their trade:

Food waste reduction target on:	2030 Mandatory FW reduction target (expression)	2030 Voluntary FW reduction target (expression)	2050 Voluntary FW reduction target (expression)
Primary production	n/a	10%	50% (absolute amounts in mass units)
Processing and manufacturing	n/a	50% (absolute amounts in mass units)	100% (absolute amounts in mass units)
Retail and consumption	15% (per capita)	50% (per capita)	100% (per capita)

Table 16 FW reduction targets in P3

A mandatory reduction target of 15% for 2030 has been set in accordance with one of the options detailed by the EC in its impact assessment of the proposed WFD revision in order to differentiate P3 from our other two alternative pathways, and also to account for the fact that FSC actors are likely to be supportive of more ambitious targets if they are set in a more flexible framework. Mandatory targets would therefore be set to a minimum, but by no means should be understood as a cap to the ambitions of P3.

Concerning voluntary targets, P3 suggests a 2030 target of 50% FW reduction at retail and consumption stage (SDG 12.3) and 50% at processing and manufacturing stage (Champions 12.3 interpretation), and 100% reduction target (ZeroW objective) for both sectors in 2050; while no target is set for primary production for 2030 or, rather, before any measurement obligation is set on this sector. It is assumed that voluntary commitments for 2050 would, on the other hand, include primary production FW as P3 considers a future where FW at this stage is monitored, measured and reported under (new) harmonised measurement frameworks (Joensuu et al., 2020). As primary production is estimated to amount to only 9% of total EU FW in 2021 according to Eurostat, significantly reducing this would, combined with FW reduction from all other FSC stages, lead to a near-zero FW situation in 2050.

- **Expression:** P3 uses targets that are formulated as percentages of change between the baseline (average between baseline year 2020 and 2022) and the target date (see below) of 2030.
- **Target dates for FW reduction:** as regards the baseline year to measure progress, P3 considers an average between data reported in 2020 (first year of EU-wide mandatory

measurement of FW) and 2022, as it has been argued by stakeholders that the COVID crisis and geopolitical events have impacted FW production at all stages of the FSC. The target dates remain those set in SDG 12.3 (2030) and ZeroW (2050).

B. Improving data collection and sources – Adjusting current FW definitions: P3 assumes that the collaboration between public authorities and the private sector will lead to improvements in data collection, reporting and sharing across the FSC, where FW will be measured at all stages gradually, including primary production, building on previous research and assumptions and with coordinated strategies integrating EU level policy-making and local implementation of policies. (Caldeira et al., 2019; Joensuu et al., 2020)

Based on a market-driven approach (see below), P3 proposes to enhance the existing harmonized FW measurement framework at the EU level (Commission delegated decision (EU) 2019/1597, Commission implementing decision (EU) 2019/2000) by incorporating the market demand for a clearer conceptualisation of FW, with the introduction of a distinction between 'avoidable' and 'unavoidable' food waste, promoting food recovery as a business opportunity. This distinction, also present in P1, aims to refine the measurement framework and elevate the quality of data.

In alignment with market considerations, P3 refrains from introducing the mandatory measurement of food loss. This decision aligns with concerns expressed by stakeholders who question the feasibility of measuring food loss, citing limitations in resources, time, and capacity within the primary production sector; however, we assume that such measurement could be envisaged through voluntary actions and made possible by further technologic advancements. This approach ensures that the market-driven framework is realistic, considering the practical constraints faced by various sectors involved in the FSC.

P3 also includes the assumptions presented under the P1 section (see table 11). FW reduction actions would be undertaken under a series of measures/mechanisms:

- **Incentive Mechanisms:** P3 assumes the introduction of more market-oriented incentive mechanisms to encourage businesses to adopt FW reduction practices. This could include tax credits, grants, or other financial incentives for companies implementing effective food waste reduction strategies.
- **(Public-)Private Sector Collaboration:** collaboration between public entities and the private sector would be fostered to develop and implement FW reduction initiatives. These partnerships would aim to create innovative solutions that align with market interests. Similarly, we assume that more collaborative platforms or industry forums

where businesses can share best practices, challenges, and innovations related to FW reduction will spark.

- **Market-driven Certification Programs:** P3 assumes that public-private certification programs for businesses that successfully implement FW reduction measures would be created. Recognising and promoting companies with sustainable practices can create a competitive advantage and motivate others.
- **Dynamic Regulatory Framework:** we assume that the regulatory framework would constantly adapt to evolving market conditions and technological advancements in a flexible way, provided innovation adheres to overarching FW reduction principles.

Above all, P3 insists on the principle of flexibility in implementation of FW reduction measures, recognizing the diverse nature of businesses within the market. Public authorities would mostly tailor and phrase recommendations to be adaptable to different sectors, sizes of enterprises, and regional variations. By incorporating these elements, the proposed measures can be enhanced to better resonate with the principles of a market-driven environment, fostering innovation, competition, and sustainable business practices.

A Solutionist approach to innovation

In this part of the scenario, we describe a (techno-)solutionist approach (but not techno-optimistic, as described by Skaug Saetra (2023)) to innovation in the market, where innovation is viewed as a driver of FW reduction and where new products, services, technologies, techniques, produce inherently social, economic and environmental benefits. This approach has the advantage of prioritising quick technological fixes to solve complex issues. Such stances, while seemingly caricatural, have been observed during recent crises, e.g. in the rise of COVID-19 (Marelli et al., 2022).

This approach would focus on design-thinking, entrepreneurship, as well as simple and efficient solutions that can be marketable and scalable. Theory-based interventions would be central, and any innovative action or intervention taken under this pathway would need to be informed by data, to avoid the temptation of oversimplification of complex problems and other unintended consequences (Stein, 2023).

P3 mostly assumes that society would continue to aim to integrate technology solutions that facilitate FW reduction in the FSC: development and implementation of digital platforms, data analytics, and traceability systems providing real-time information to businesses and consumers, supporting efficient inventory management. This would be coupled to market research and monitoring to understand the evolving dynamics of FW in the industry. Data-

driven insights to continuously refine and improve strategies, ensuring they remain effective and aligned with market trends.

Consumer behaviours driving sustainability

In this part of the scenario, we explore an approach that relies on soft power, economic incentives and education and awareness-raising programmes to spark consumer behaviour changes (*“market-driven” approach*). This approach mostly postulates that consumer education and awareness-raising can align with market FW reduction goals, through smart purchasing decisions, proper storage practices, and responsible disposal, and that such practices should therefore be promoted as the main driver of FW reduction in food systems.

Similarly to P1, P3 assumes that EU institutions and EU MS would keep working on the central role of consumer level solutions to reduce FW, with increased measures to target households, both at home and away from home. While P3 does not suggest that consumers alone should bear the burden (and cost) of change, it suggests that FW reduction could only happen if the commitments driving business actions to influence consumer behaviours (e.g. decisions on date labelling, packaging sizes, pricing strategies in retail stores to avoid overpurchase, etc.) are fully integrated and acted on by consumers themselves. It therefore places extra attention on education programmes and awareness-raising, as long as this follows the perceived (or observed, through e.g. Eurobarometers) trends in consumer preferences, which are assumed to evolve.

This pathway assumes that costs, taste, food safety, geographical origin and nutrient content would long remain the first declared criteria taken into account by consumers when purchasing food products, with a lesser interest being paid to the impact of such products (and their production line) on the environment and climate (EFSA, 2022).

In such a context, the market would have little reasons to jeopardise its profitability by going too fast, and industry front-runners would mostly rely on public incentives (through subsidies or fiscal deductions) or awareness-raising practices (e.g. pricing strategies, messages in stores and on labels) to move towards FW reduction objectives.

While this assumption supports the idea that mandatory high FW reduction targets would hardly be achievable, inaction from FSC actors is however not to be assumed. It would focus on influencing consumers through (very) soft power means. For instance, a participant to the ZeroW Consumer Behaviour WG shared with the authors her study detailing elements influencing social norms by making FW socially unacceptable (Blondin and Attwood, 2022).

Such research papers suggest that consumer FW are mostly driven by individual decisions and actions. FW reduction and prevention must therefore rely on nudging approaches (von Kameke and Fischer, 2018, p. 39) These include the use of social norms to “shame and blame” or reward individual behaviours; the use of public awareness messages to display the economic, social and environmental impacts of FW; sharing tips on shopping planning with consumers via email; informing people of the consequences (including economic ones) of their past food purchase choices;... (Barker et al., 2021, p. 3). We listed above (see table 12, consumer behaviour P1) different interventions to consumer FW reduction, with areas of opportunity for actions. These remain applicable in this scenario, but the originality of P3 would be that most of these initiatives would root from private sector actors, as deemed to be best suited to know their customers preferences and adapt messages to their communication.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, this report represents an effort by the ZeroW policy team (WP8) to address the pressing issue of FW within the EU. As the project sets ambitious short-term, medium-term, and long-term objectives aligned with the Farm-to-fork Strategy and the EU Green Deal, aiming to significantly reduce per capita FW levels by 2030 and ultimately achieve near-zero waste by 2050, we also ought to recognise the complexity of the food systems and the need for a systemic approach. Therefore, the report emphasises the importance of considering various factors and variables that influence FW throughout the supply chain, highlighted in a trend pathway that we attempted to define through the analysis of barriers and opportunities for FW reduction, as well as through the identification of the existing legislation and key publications on the topic.

The report indeed focuses on providing an overview of the state-of-play analysis of FLW in the EU. Furthermore, through stakeholder engagement processes, including interviews and working group meetings, we have gathered valuable insights and feedback from experts in the agrifood sector to construct and formulate three alternative pathways for the future. These pathways, although not forecasts, serve as thought-provoking scenarios, each proposing distinctive approaches to address FW reduction through changes in consumer behaviours, innovation, and policies. The intention behind these alternative pathways is not to predict the future but to stimulate dialogues and conversations within the ZeroW consortium and external stakeholder working groups. These conversations will play a crucial role in shaping the direction of the ZeroW project, influencing modelling and simulation tasks, and contributing to future publications.

Further conversations and debates will indeed be needed to determine which 'just' transition pathway should be called for, considering the environmental, social and economic dimensions of sustainability, as well as including new elements from the latest research papers (e.g.: Russo et al., 2023).

In summary, this deliverable lays the foundation for informed decision-making within the ZeroW project, promoting a collaborative effort to tackle FW reduction at various levels. By presenting alternative pathways, the report sparks discussions that will contribute to a 'just' transition towards near-zero food waste by 2050, aligning with the overarching goals of the ZeroW project and the broader objectives set by the Farm-to-fork Strategy and the EU Green Deal.

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7. Appendix

Appendix 1: Overview of participating expert stakeholders & contacted stakeholders

Organisation	Category of stakeholder	Participation to Policy WG (13)	Participation to Innovation WG (10)	Participation to Consumer Behaviour WG (8)
Andalusian Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development. General Secretariat for Agriculture, Livestock and Food	Regional institutions	X		
AZTI Foundation	Foundation		X	
COPA-COGECA	Industry	X		
Emilia-Romagna Region - DG Agriculture	Regional institutions	X	X	X
Es-imperfect	Industry		X	
Eurocommerce	Industry			
FoodDrink Europe	Industry	X		
Fundació Espigoladors	Foundation	X		X
Future in our hands (Norway)	NGOs/Non-profit	X		
Good Food Good Farming	NGOs/Non-profit	X		X
ITL (Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation)	Industry	X	X	
c	Research Centres/Institutes		X	
Joint Research Centre (JRC)	EU Institutions	X	X	X
Polish Zero Waste Association	NGOs/Non-profit	X	X	X

Thünen Institute (German Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries)	Research Centres/Institutes	X		
UCAUCE-Andalusian Consumers' Union	NGOs/Non-profit			X
University of Bologna	Universities	X	X	X
University of Tuscia	Universities		X	
World Resources Institute	Research Centres/Institutes	X	X	X

WG Innovation

Organisation	Stakeholder group	Stakeholder subgroup	Geographical area	Country/Region
ALICE	Industry & innovators	Innovation/tech platform	Europe	Belgium
AINIA Technological Center	Industry & innovators	Innovation/tech platform	Europe	Spain
Association of Hotels and Restaurants (HOTREC)	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
BIO BEAN company	Industry & innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)	Europe	United Kingdom
Biobased Industries Consortium	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
C'est qui le Patron ?! (CQLP)	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	France
CogZum Ltd.	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Bulgaria
Colruyt	Industry & innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)	Europe	Belgium

Consum	Industry & innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)	Europe	Spain
COPA-COGECA	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
Coviran	Industry & innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)	Europe	Spain
Eat me app	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Serbia
EIT Food	Industry & innovators	Innovation/tech platform	Europe	Belgium
Eroski	Industry & innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)	Europe	Spain
Es-imperfect	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Spain
EUCOFEL	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
EUROCOMMERCE	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
European bioplastic	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium

European Consumer Food Waste Forum	Research communities	Research centre/institute	Europe	Belgium
European Coordination Via Campesina (ECVC)	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
EUROPEN	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
FoodDrink Europe	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
FOODSCALE HUB	Industry & innovators	Innovation/tech platform	Europe	Serbia
FoodShare	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	
Foodways consulting	Industry & innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)	Europe	Switzerland
FORESIGHTEE	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Belgium
FRESHFEL	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
Future Food Institute	Research communities	Research centres	Europe	Italy

ING Belgium	Industry & innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)	Europe	Belgium
IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute	Research communities	Research centre/institute	Europe	Sweden
Karma	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Sweden
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	Research communities	University	Europe	Belgium
Keep-it	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Norway
Matomatic AB	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Sweden
OLIO	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	United Kingdom
Open ENLoCC	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
Phenix	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	France
Thünen Institute (German Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries)	Research communities	Research centre/institute	Europe	Germany

TotalCtrl	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Norway
YourLocal	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Denmark

WG Policy

Organisation	Stakeholder group	Stakeholder subgroup	Geographical area	Country/Region
Agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI) Operational Groups	Institutions & policymakers	EU institution	Europe	Belgium
Agroecology Europe	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium
Andalusian Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development. General Secretariat for Agriculture, Livestock and Food	Institutions & policymakers	Regional institution	Europe	Spain
Association of Cities and Regions for Sustainable Resource Management (ACR+)	Civil society & citizens	Coalition/network	Global	Belgium
Association of Hotels and Restaurants (HOTREC)	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium

AZTI Foundation	Research communities	Foundation	Europe	Spain
BEUC	Civil society & citizens	Consumer organisation	Europe	Belgium
Biobased Industries Consortium	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership	Research communities	Research centre/institute	Global	United Kingdom
Centre for European Policy Research (CEPS)	Research communities	Think tank	Europe	Belgium
Changing Markets Foundation	Civil society & citizens	Foundation	Europe	Netherlands
Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU)	Institutions & policymakers	EU institution	Europe	Belgium
Collaborating Centre for Sustainable Consumption and Production (CSCP)	Research communities	Think tank	Europe	Germany
COPA-COGECA	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
Ellen McArthur Foundation	Civil society & citizens	Foundation	Global	United Kingdom

Emilia Romagna Region - DG Agriculture	Institutions & policy makers	Regional institution	Europe	Emilia-Romagna, Italy
Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS)	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Global	Belgium
EU Agricultural civil dialogue groups	Institutions & policymakers	EU institution	Europe	Belgium
EU Council Presidency	Institutions & policymakers	EU institution	Europe	Belgium
EU Food Policy Coalition	Civil society & citizens	Coalition/network	Europe	Belgium
EU Waste Coalition	Civil society & citizens	Coalition/network	Europe	Belgium
EUCOFEL	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
EUROCOMMERCE	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
European bioplastic	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA)	Institutions & policymakers	EU institution	Europe	Belgium

European Coordination Via Campesina (ECVC)	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
European Environmental Bureau (EEB)	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium
European Food Banks Federation (FEBA)	Civil society & citizens	Food bank	Europe	Belgium
European Food Information Council (EUFIC)	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium
European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)	Institutions & policymakers	EU institution	Europe	Belgium
European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)	Industry & innovators	NGO/non-profit	Global	Belgium
European Region of Gastronomy Platform	Civil society & citizens	Coalition/network	Europe	Spain
EUROPEN	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
Feedback	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Global	United Kingdom
Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)	Institutions & policymakers	International organisation	Global	Italy

FoodDrink Europe	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
FRESHFEL	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
Fundació Espigoladors	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Spain
Future Food Network	Civil society & citizens	Coalition/network	Global	Italy
Good Food Good Farming	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium
Healthy Food, Healthy Planet	Civil society & citizens	Foundation	Europe	Netherlands
IDDRI	Research communities	Think tank	Europe	France
International Food Waste Coalition (IFWC)	Civil society & citizens	Coalition/network	Europe	Belgium
International Rice Research Institute	Research communities	Research centre/institute	Global	Philippines
IPES Food	Research communities	Think tank	Europe	Belgium

IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute	Research communities	Research centre/institute	Europe	Sweden
Joint Research Centre (JRC)	Institutions & policymakers	EU institution	Europe	Belgium
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	Research communities	University	Europe	Belgium
Kayma Labs (IL-USA)	Industry & innovators	Think tank	Global	United States
Lean and Green	Civil society & citizens	Coalition/network	Europe	Netherlands
Louis Bonduelle Foundation	Civil society & citizens	Foundation	Global	France
Oak Foundation	Civil society & citizens	Foundation	Global	Switzerland
Open ENLoCC	Industry & innovators	Industry/trade association	Europe	Belgium
Open Society European Policy Institute (OSEPI)	Research communities	Think tank	Europe	Belgium
Real Junk Food Project network	Civil society & citizens	Coalition/network	Global	United Kingdom

RESOIL Foundation	Civil society & citizens	Foundation	Europe	Italy
RREUSE	Civil society & citizens	Coalition/network	Global	Belgium
Sejong University	Research communities	University	Global	South Korea
Slow Food Europe	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium
Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3) thematic groups	Institutions & policymakers	EU institution	Europe	Belgium
SP Technical Research Institute of Sweden AB	Research communities	Research centre/institute	Global	Sweden
SUSFOOD2	Research communities	Coalition/network	Europe	
Thünen Institute (German Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries)	Research communities	Research centre/institute	Europe	Germany
UN Food Systems Summit Food Waste Coalition	Institutions & policymakers	International organisation	Global	
University of Putra Malaysia	Research communities	University	Global	Malaysia

World Food Programme (WFP)	Institutions & policymakers	International organisation	Global	Italy
World Health Organisation	Institutions & policymakers	International organisation	Global	Switzerland
World Resources Institute	Research communities	Research centre/institute	Global	United Kingdom
World Trade Organisation	Institutions & policymakers	International organisation	Global	Switzerland
WRAP	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Global	United Kingdom
WWF EU Office	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium
Zero Waste Europe	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium

WG Consumer Behaviour

Organisation	Stakeholder group	Stakeholder subgroup	Geographical area	Country/Region
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Agroecology Europe	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium
ART-ER Attractiveness Research Territory (Emilia-Romagna Joint Stock Consortium)	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government	Local/regional	Emilia Romagna
BEUC	Civil society & citizens	Consumer organisation	Europe	Belgium
Bond Beter Leefmilieu (BBL)	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Local/regional	Flanders
Centre for European Policy Research (CEPS)	Research communities	Think tank	Europe	Belgium
C'est qui le Patron ?! (CQLP)	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	France
CogZum Ltd.	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Bulgaria
Collaborating Centre for Sustainable Consumption and Production (CSCP)	Research communities	Think tank	Europe	Germany
Department Economy, Science and Innovation (EWI), Flemish Government	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government	Local/regional	Flanders
Eat me app	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Serbia

Es-imperfect	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Spain
European Environmental Bureau (EEB)	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium
European Food Banks Federation (FEBA)	Civil society & citizens	Food bank	Europe	Belgium
European Food Information Council (EUFIC)	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium
Flemish Department of Economy, Science & Innovation	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government	Local/regional	Flanders
Flemish Food Supply Chain Platform for Food Loss	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government	Local/regional	Flanders
FoodShare	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	
FORESIGHTEE	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Belgium
Fundació Espigoladors	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Spain
Good Food Good Farming	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium

IDDRI	Research communities	Think tank	Europe	France
IPES Food	Research communities	Think tank	Europe	Belgium
Karma	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Sweden
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	Research communities	University	Europe	Belgium
Keep-it	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Norway
Matomatic AB	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Sweden
Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Development of Andalusia (Consejería de Agricultura, Ganadería, Pesca y Desarrollo)	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government	Local/regional	Andalusia
Municipality of Milan	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government	Local/regional	Italy
Municipality of Warsaw	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government	Local/regional	Poland

OLIO	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	United Kingdom
Open Society European Policy Institute (OSEPI)	Research communities	Think tank	Europe	Belgium
OVAM (Flemish Public Waste Agency)	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government	Local/regional	Flanders
Phenix	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	France
Slow Food Europe	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium
Tel Aviv Municipality	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government	Local/regional	Israel
TotalCtrl	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Norway
UCAUCE-Unión de Consumidores de Andalucía (pending confirmation)	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Spain
Waste Watcher International Observatory	<i>Research communities</i>	<i>Research centres</i>	Europe	Italy

WWF EU Office	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium
YourLocal	Industry & innovators	Start-ups & social business	Europe	Denmark
Zero Waste Europe	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit	Europe	Belgium

Appendix 2: Interview grids

WP8

Stakeholder outreach – Questionnaire

Survey: Engaging stakeholders to build consistent policies for a just transition pathway towards near-zero FLW

Stakeholder Survey on EU Food Waste Reduction

Thank you for participating in this survey. Your feedback is essential in understanding the perspectives and strategies of stakeholders in the EU food sector regarding Food Loss and Waste (FLW) reduction. This survey aims to gather insights on your views about current EU legislative developments and your organization's approaches to tackle food waste.

PART 1 – Your organisation

Section 1: Demographics

- Name of Organization:
- Your Position:
- Type of Organization (e.g., Food Producer, Retailer, NGO, Government Agency, etc.):
- Location (Country):
- Number of Employees in Your Organization:

Section 2: EU Legislative Developments

Please rate your organization's level of awareness and support for the following EU legislative developments related to Food Loss and Waste (FLW) reduction on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 is "Not Aware/Not Supportive" and 5 is "Highly Aware/Strongly Supportive."

2.1. The EU Circular Economy Action Plan and its objectives:

- Awareness (1-5): 1-2-3-4-5
- Support (1-5): 1-2-3-4-5

2.2. The EU Farm to Fork Strategy and its impact on FLW:

- Awareness (1-5): 1-2-3-4-5
- Support (1-5): 1-2-3-4-5

2.3. The EU Waste Framework Directive revision (July 2023):

- Awareness (1-5): 1-2-3-4-5

- Support (1-5): 1-2-3-4-5

Section 3: Food Waste Reduction Strategies Please provide information about your organization's strategies and initiatives to tackle food waste.

3.1. Does your organization have a formal FLW reduction policy or strategy in place?

- Yes
- No

3.2. If yes, please briefly describe your organization's FLW reduction policy or strategy (*hyperlinks are welcome*).

.....

3.3. What specific measures or technologies has your organization implemented to reduce FLW? (e.g., food donation programs, waste tracking systems, packaging innovations, etc.)

.....

3.4. Has your organization set any FLW reduction targets or goals? If yes, please specify.

.....

3.5. How does your organization collaborate with other stakeholders in the food value chain to address FLW? (e.g., suppliers, retailers, NGOs, government agencies)

.....

Section 4: Challenges and Recommendations

- What are the main challenges your organization faces in reducing FLW?

.....

- What recommendations or improvements would you suggest to enhance the effectiveness of EU legislation in reducing FLW?

.....

Section 5: Additional Comments Please feel free to provide any additional comments or insights regarding EU legislative developments or FLW reduction strategies that you believe are important.

PART 2 – Modelling impact of FLW reduction measures

Section 6: Request for data

The ZeroW project is building a model to assess the impact that changes in consumer behaviours, policies and innovation can have on FLW generation. The model considers 6 stages of the supply chain, schematically illustrated in Figure 1. Each stage optimizes its supply/demand and waste. As each stage needs to be calibrated, we need the data below.

Please answer to the best of your knowledge – hyperlinks and recommendations for further readings are welcome.

*Food served at hotels, restaurants and institutions (like Universities, hospitals, etc.)

Figure 1. Stages of the vertical supply chain (de Gorter et al., 2021).

Among the stages (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6^a, 6^b) of the supply chain listed above, in which one(s) is your company active?

<p>Which food commodity/ies is/are the most interesting from the point of view of your sector?</p> <p>.....</p>
<p>What are the selling prices and quantities per commodity in your stage of the supply chain?</p> <p>.....</p>
<p>What are the typical marketing margins at your stage of the supply chain?</p> <p>.....</p>

What are the typical edible and inedible loss and/or waste rates per commodity at your stage of the supply chain?

.....

How much food (in percentage) is lost before harvest? *(For primary producers only)*

.....

Which interventions are taken by farmers to prevent pre-harvest losses? *(For primary producers only)*

.....

What are the typical modes of disposing of food waste at your stage of the supply chain: composting, valorization (reuse), incineration, landfill?

.....

Section 7: Contact Information (Optional) If you are willing to provide further insights or be contacted for follow-up questions, please provide your contact information below.

- 7.1. Email:
- 7.2. Phone:

Thank you for participating in this survey. Your input is invaluable in shaping EU initiatives for Food Loss and Waste reduction.

Acknowledgements

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Appendix 3: Summary table – Key barriers and opportunities

Stage of the value chain	Political barriers/opportunities	Economic barriers/opportunities	Sociocultural barriers/opportunities	Technological barriers/opportunities	Legal barriers/opportunities	Environmental barriers/opportunities
Primary production	<p>Competitive level playing field and reduction of subsidies.</p> <p>Adoption of new technologies to reduce pesticide and fertiliser use.</p> <p>The UN's SDG 12.3 mainly focuses on tackling FW at retail and consumer level.</p>	<p>Limited innovation capacity for small EU farms.</p> <p>Intermediaries between producers and consumers.</p> <p>Wasteful market practices.</p>	<p>Agriculture is unattractive for young people, favouring automation.</p> <p>The balance of power favours markets over farmers.</p> <p>PA manufacturing and PATs can provide work opportunities and improve working conditions.</p> <p>Advanced automation</p>	<p>Full automation in farms is still not attainable.</p> <p>Higher demand and lower cost for automation components.</p> <p>Adaptability of technologies in the agrifood sector varies.</p> <p>Most SFTs are at a very early stage of development.</p>	<p>The Directive (EU) 2019/633 on unfair trading practices (UTP) may tackle power imbalances between actors.</p> <p>The Legislation on infectious diseases outbreaks prevention (Regulation (EU) 2016/429) may hinder FLW reduction.</p>	<p>Food production has a significant manmade environmental footprint, alongside FLW management.</p> <p>PATs provide possible reduction of the carbon footprint and increased efficiency in fuel use.</p> <p>Digital innovations may reduce the use of pesticides and fertilisers.</p>

			technologies can attract highly-skilled workers to the agricultural sector.	Controlled Traffic Farming is the most successful segment in PA. Sub-optimal storage and cooling conditions reduce the lifetime of fruits and vegetables. The international Consortium for Innovation in Post-Harvest Loss and Food Waste Reduction addresses these challenges.		
Food processing	EFSA's control over the food supply chain The Global Protocol on Packaging	Highly diverse and fragmented market with prevalence of SMEs. Accreditation schemes and	Dependency on consumers' acceptance and awareness of innovations.	Early adoption of robotic technologies in Europe. Most technologies applied at commercial scale,	General Food Law Regulation EC 178/2002 FIC Regulation (EU) 1169/2011	Decentralised systems are not always the most environmentally friendly.

	<p>Sustainability (GPPS)</p> <p>The Upcycled Food Association: standards and certifications for upcycled foods.</p> <p>The Juice CSR Platform as a sustainability initiative</p>	<p>voluntary programmes.</p> <p>Lack of market opportunities for new food from upcycling technologies.</p> <p>Higher food discard levels from industrial food processing.</p> <p>Overproduction of bread and bakery products driven by the marketing standards (SK).</p> <p>Low financial support to businesses for investment in food upcycling technologies.</p>	<p>Consumers' neophobia and technophobia toward innovation acceptability.</p> <p>Consumers' awareness of food packaging' environmental impact rather than food waste's.</p>	<p>such as RF heating, ohmic reading, ultrasound, UV & PL, HHP, and PEF.</p> <p>Change in fundamental quality parameters in food products with upcycled ingredients.</p> <p>Complexity of the packaging value chain with downstream consequences.</p> <p>Machine breakdowns and human errors during handling leading to waste.</p>	<p>Active and Intelligent Materials Regulation EC 450/2009</p> <p>FCMs Regulation EC 1935/2004.</p> <p>GMP Regulation EC 2023/2006</p> <p>Plastic and Materials Regulation EC 10/2011</p> <p>PPW Directive 94/62/EC and amending Directives 2004/12/EC and 2013/2/EU.</p>	<p>Lack of research studies on the environmental impact of innovative technologies.</p> <p>Need for LCA studies on Food upcycling.</p> <p>Underpacking causes more FLW than overpacking.</p> <p>Need to reach a balance between safety and environment.</p>
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		<p>Insufficient availability of qualified staff,</p> <p>Little time to unpack, sort and redistribute food for logistics.</p> <p>43% waste decrease from the processing and packaging sector.</p>				
Distribution and wholesale	<p>The EU Farm-to-Fork Strategy commitments.</p> <p>The EU proposed legislative framework for Sustainable Food Systems</p> <p>The Renewable Energy Directive</p>	<p>The industry is dominated by micro enterprises.</p> <p>The Waste Framework Directive recommends public bodies to use fiscal instruments as incentives for FW prevention.</p>		<p>Portioned and divisible packaging can be a solution to consumers' complaints about package size.</p> <p>Immature technologies used for FLW revalorisation.</p>	<p>Regulation (EU) 1308/2013 (December 2013)</p> <p>The annexes of Regulation (EC) 852/2004 on food hygiene.</p> <p>Amendments by Regulation (EC)</p>	

	2018/2001/EU revised in 2021.	<p>Unpacking food items is time consuming and costly.</p> <p>Some countries are applying waste or incineration taxes or pay-as-you-throw (PAYT) to households.</p>		<p>Insufficient logistics capacity for food donation (for retail too).</p>	<p>2021/382 in March 2021.</p> <p>Use of shorter expiration period to avoid liability/image deterioration in case of food safety concerns (NDL, IT).</p> <p>No tax reduction/refund for businesses that donate food (DK).</p> <p>A VAT refund on damaged (food) items but not for donations. (NDL).</p>	
Retail	The UN's SDG 12.3: halving retail and consumer food waste by 2030.	<p>Estimated total cost of FW can be up to 2% of total sales.</p> <p>Business-led marketing standards and practices, such as</p>		<p>Little research assessing the viability of technologies for food waste management.</p>	<p>Regulation EU 1169/2011 (FIC regulation) setting the labelling requirements of food products.</p>	<p>Solutions favouring prevention of wastage or alternative uses (animal feed) for the most impactful food types, such as bread and beef.</p>

		<p>on shape and appearance.</p> <p>The food retail sector leads the food redistribution process in Europe but faces several costs.</p> <p>These costs should be lower than the market prices of the obtained products to make economic sense.</p> <p>Preventing FLW upstream the FSC could result in less resources for waste management innovations downstream the FSC.</p>		<p>FW measurements currently made manually.</p>	<p>Regulation (EC) 853/2004 on specific hygiene requirements for food of animal origin, amended by Regulation (EC) 2021/1374 in August 2021,</p> <p>Most EU member states have set legislative and non-legislative measures to reduce FLW.</p>	
Horeca		<p>Portions of dishes are too large and there are too many items on canteens' buffets.</p>		<p>Food Donations: insufficient logistics infrastructure to timely capture</p>	<p>Government obligation to divert food waste to compost or biogas plants (DK).</p>	

				and redistribute all food surplus.	<p>Food Surplus Donations: not legally binding. Less costly to throw away food than donating it (DK).</p> <p>Horeca Food Safety regulation on food donation procedures: delivery must be made within a limited time lap. (DK).</p>	
End consumer		Consumers' purchasing and conservation habits.	<p>Consumers' cultural context, perceptions and attitudes regarding food influence FLW.</p> <p>FLW reduction on the consumers' part can be achieved</p>		<p>Date marking: confusion over the interpretation of "Best Before" date and "Use by".</p>	<p>Waste produced at household level has the greatest environmental impact.</p> <p>Campaigns focusing on the environmental</p>

			<p>either by reducing purchase of food or by consuming all the food purchased.</p> <p>Raising awareness on FW among consumers may not have a significant impact. Blaming the consumers would be unproductive.</p> <p>Consumer acceptance of carbon labels differs across member states.</p>			<p>issues caused by FLW may have a limited impact due to consumers' fatigue of receiving constant messages about it.</p>
Cross-cutting issues		Complex and long Food Value chains.		Lack of human capacity (and investment) in personnel dedicated to food redistribution logistics.	<p>No Mandatory and well-established FW quantification and reporting system.</p> <p>No mandatory regulation on food surplus management to</p>	<p>Pyrolysis as an eco-friendly alternative for treatment of food waste.</p> <p>Composting as one of the fastest ways of revalorising FW but with considerable GHG emissions.</p>

					<p>avoid food dumping (exception of FR).</p> <p>Food waste collected with its packaging is not considered food waste, and therefore it does not need to be measured (1501 European Waste Code).</p> <p>Government subsidies to green energy/biogas plants</p> <p>Lack of inspections and fining system on FW generation by FVC operator.</p>	
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Appendix 4: Overview of WP8 and WP9 regular interactions

N.	Date	Expert group followed/Meeting attended	Aim	ZeroW participant(s)
1	17/02/2022	EU platform on FLW (EC)*	Updates on EC state of play of F2F Strategy FW initiatives	SAFE ICLEI
2	10/06/2022	DG SANTE, JRC, DG RTD (EC)	(Ad hoc meeting) Align project policy objectives to DG SANTE/JRC needs Gather more information on JRC IIA methodology or results	SAFE ICLEI ILVO VLTN ICP
3	20/10/2022	EU platform on FLW (EC)*	Updates on EC state of play of F2F Strategy developments regarding reduction targets/revision of rules on date-marking	SAFE
4	23/01/2023	DG SANTE (EC)	(Ad hoc meeting) Discussion with EC officials on potential shortcomings, updates on state of play of IIA	SAFE ICLEI
5	13/03/2023	Joint EU platform on FLW & Advisory Group on SFS (EC)*/**	Presentation of Eurostat data (published in Oct 2022) Presentation of probable revision proposal for WFD	SAFE
6	12/07/2023	Advisory Group on SFS (EC)**	Presentation of FSFS: principles, definitions and scope	SAFE
7	05/09/2023	DG SANTE/MARE/ENV/AGRI (EC)	Discussion on FSFS: details on scope and inclusion of obligations for middle-chain actors	SAFE
8	11/09/2023	EESC	Expert hearing to inform EESC opinion on its report about WFD revision	SAFE
9	19/09/2023	Advisory Group on SFS (EC)**	Gathering information on indicators designed by JRC to	SAFE

			monitor the F2F implementation	
10	7-8/11/2023	EU platform on FLW (EC)* and European Citizens' Panel on FLW	Two-day presentations of	SAFE
11	17/11/2023	Advisory Group on SFS (EC)**	Presentation of the State of play concerning food waste legislative proposal (WFD revision)	SAFE

*: the [EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste](#) was established in 2016, bringing together EU institutions, experts from the EU countries, international organisations and relevant stakeholders selected through an open call for applications. The Platform aims to support all actors in: defining measures needed to prevent food waste; sharing best practice; and evaluating progress made over time. As ZeroW project partners (except WUR - Wageningen University & Research) are not official members of the platform, we followed meetings of the platform through livestreams and remained in touch with several [member organisations](#).

**= the [Advisory Group on Sustainability of Food Systems](#) (AGSFS) has been established to consult all relevant stakeholders on issues relating to the implementation of the Farm to Fork Strategy and food systems' sustainability. SAFE (WP8 lead) is a [member organisation](#) of this group on behalf of ZeroW.

Appendix 5: Contributions from SILLs periodic reports

ZeroW creates impact through the demonstration of innovative FLW reduction solutions in nine [Living Labs](#) along the real-life food chains to effectively address the multidimensional issue of FLW. Each of the SILLs (WP4, see section 1.4.2) has been required, through their development, to report on the barriers and opportunities they faced by the end of the first year of the ZeroW Project (M12, December 2022). Information from each of the SILLs is described below and complements the present section with additional information.

SILL1

Within FLW monitoring and assessment, the main objectives of SILL1 concern prevention and reduction. To achieve them, it focused on the development of an open, data-driven IT platform for FLW monitoring and assessment throughout the entire food supply chain, from food producers to end consumers. Special focus is on the solutions' providers, mainly SMEs and startups. The following challenges have been identified. Nonetheless, they did not have a significant impact on the activities' implementation and the achievement of results:

- Data availability
- Stakeholders' interests in the topic
- Interest of actors sharing their data
- Participation in additional work burden of collecting data
- Economic disruptions in priorities caused by the energy crisis and proximity of war
- Lack of policy awareness and lack of enforceability of existing policies
- previous experience with projects aiming at reducing waste
- Lack of a community of practice/platform of discussion

It is important to mention that no data at regional-levels has been collected, but only at the national-level which is based on estimation. Therefore, this has resulted in a lack of trust in the quality and accuracy of the data, since stakeholders tend to report less to paint a better picture of their actions or situation.

SILL2

SILL2 is concerned with the innovative, sustainable, and smart packaging for fresh food products, the key objective being food waste prevention. It is relevant to the processing, wholesale, retail, and consumption stages of the food supply chain. It focused on two main innovations:

- The development of packaging for oily fish made from compostable materials and with an integrated freshness label that facilitates the visualisation of shelf life, thereby reducing waste.

- The development of a mobile app software for reading freshness colour changes. It would help retailers and marketers have a clearer idea of the product's freshness status, thereby helping them reduce waste.

The main identified challenges concern the regulatory uncertainty that could impact the commercialisation of these innovations. It is crucial to identify who should be considered the final users, either retailer or consumers. In this regard, more data from consumers is being collected.

SILL3

SILL3 aims to find wasteless greenhouse solutions for the pre-harvest stages, with the objective of food loss reduction. It concerns the pre-harvest and post-harvest stages of the food supply chain and focuses on innovation, specifically the development of technology to address the following three aspects:

- **MONITORING – greenhouse fruit and vegetable growth monitoring, ripeness assessment, and yield forecasting** (initially, specific focus on tomatoes).
- **EVALUATING – automated quality evaluation** according to “cosmetic standards” at the harvest and pre-harvest stages. The objective is to enable early initiation of alternative marketing channels to avoid food loss.

PLANNING – data-driven software to assist farmers scheduling harvest at the best time and predict short-term downstream demand. Such innovation would benefit greenhouse fruit and vegetable farmers, food logistics and export service providers, food manufacturers, and retailers. However, a behavioural challenge from the farmers' side may considerably hinder progress. In fact, they showcase limited willingness to participate in Research and Development activities and accept new technological advancement in their daily activities. This unwillingness stems from an underlying lack of trust in these new technologies and uncertainty about their reliability. A guiding question for this SILL would be whether there are any implementing barriers in the greenhouses.

SILL4

SILL 4 aims to reduce food waste through mobile food valorisation as a service. Thus, it focuses on the development of a mobile processing unit to be made available as a service, affecting the processing stage of the food supply chain. By being mobile, this unit eliminates the prohibitive costs of transporting food surpluses for valorisation. As a processing unit, it will allow the processing, and consequently, valorisation of underutilised fruits and vegetables surpluses into high added-value food products such as juice or purée. The expected benefits for local communities include new business opportunities for regional hubs, besides providing good quality, locally produced food for the local community and local businesses. The SILL has been occupied with evaluating and demonstrating the possibility of marketing a mobile processing unit as a service, built as part of the **Food in a Box Project (FOX)**. Even if it concerns primarily processing actors, it is expected to have spill-over

benefits throughout the entire supply chain. Nonetheless, while policy challenges seem resolved for now, an organisational challenge and the difficulty of putting the product on the market represent significant limitations. In fact, to remove uncertainties about the marketing of the product, it is important to identify stakeholders interested in marketing it, as well as setting a price and identifying unique selling points. Moreover, the Novel Food regulation does not allow the tasting of the juice produced by the unit's container.

The SILL recommends resolving the issue with the competent Belgian authority to allow for test and demos in Belgium. As of 07/03/2023, there are no restriction for research and development as long as food safety is guaranteed. Therefore, there should be no problems to commercialise the juices because there is no scientific evidence that the juice is different from those produced via other technologies, and there are already PEF juices on the EU market. Another significant challenge concerns the uncertainty about the practical cooperation with potential users. It is still not clear who will be reaching out to who, whether there will be central locations to pick up the feedstock and whether the feedstock will be free. However, multiple scenarios exist to set up new collaborations and value chains. It is important to assess what are these different scenarios and which ones would lead to the most optimal impact in terms of FLW reduction.

SILL5

Sill5, which is connected to SILL3, deals with the early identification of ugly food, shelf-life assessment and alternative valorisation, with the objective of FLW reduction. It affects the processing and retail stages of the food supply chain. The main focus has also been on innovation, specifically:

- The development of a **multi-sensor platform** with the capacity of analysing and processing around 300,000 fruit per hour and with the possibility of classifying them in three different outputs based on quality and shelf-life parameters. It would help identify “ugly food” that does not comply with retail requirements at an early stage, improving prospects for revalorisation.
- The development of a data service platform to control input produce. Food processors and retailers would be the end users of this technology.

These innovations face similar behavioural, organisational, and market barriers as those in previous SILLs. For instance, farmers show reluctance as they might not appreciate the increase in control and quality standards, which is arguably one of the most significant problems to tackle. The commercialisation of these innovations is also a significant problem as it is rendered difficult by their specificity. Additionally, NG sensors technology might require further certification and compliance in the future. Even within businesses, some companies maintain a conservative attitude, often preferring to keep using old fashion methods. Some of them lack resources for efficient implementation as well. Moreover, there are potential problems arising within the value chain, especially concerning the solution upscaling due to dimensions and capacity. The integration of these new solutions into pre-existing

lines is potentially problematic and made worse by potential logistics and specific adaptation mistakes. Potential data from SILL5 could be useful to demonstrate the positive impact of these innovations.

SILL6

SILL6 concerns food waste reduction through advanced data-driven production process control and optimisation, aiming to prevent and reduce food waste. It affects the processing stage of the food value chain and focuses on the development of an advanced IT software platform for controlling and optimising food production lines. More specifically, its focus lies on the production of breaded chicken products. Food processing SMEs would be the end users of this technology. Nevertheless, there is an organisational challenge to take into consideration. A lack of sufficient harmonisation in the food losses accounting has been identified. To tackle this challenge, the creation of a specific database for ZeroW is currently under discussion. As of now, it is imperative to assess this discussion and the SILL's status, focusing on the potential outcomes of this specific database.

SILL7

SILL7 deals with food waste reduction through efficient food bank networks, aiming to prevent and reduce food waste. Thus, it affects the processing, retail, and consumption stages of the chain. Its objective is to develop models and tools to support food banks and companies donating to food banks:

- **Demand prediction tool** for food banks.
- **Supply prediction tool** for food banks.
- **Decision support tool for food banks** for waste reduction initiatives.
- **Donation tool for donors** to advise them what products to donate to food banks.
- Development of a **handbook of all possible waste reduction strategies** for food banks.

This SILL faces mainly behavioural and organisational challenges. For instance, there is a lack of reliable data within the organisation of food banks. More specifically, food banks lack the use of advanced information systems because of their costs and unfamiliarity. Moreover, the later stages of the food supply chain, such as distribution, are characterised by informal organisation and operations, which are therefore difficult to measure.

SILL8

SILL8 features the main objective of valorisation for retail food waste through algae production for high-value application. Thus, it affects the retail stage and algae and cosmetic producers especially. It aims to achieve this objective by:

- Developing **an in-store/in-warehouse food waste pre-treatment process**, which transforms waste into micro dehydrated "powder" that can be used

for microalgae culture and later utilised for biopolymers and cosmetic production.

- Developing **a new hermetic container for FLW pre-treated transportation** from the retail to microalgae producers.

SILL8 has faced an organisational challenge related to the lack of standardised procedure to operate the dehydrator process unit in a way that would guarantee reliable samples. It has been resolved by defining clear requirements and responsibilities. Moreover, there was a time-lag between storage of output and actual start of the laboratory tests, which compromised some of the samples but has been resolved by using hermetic containers. Currently, it is important to assess whether SILL8 experiences any regulatory challenges.

SILL9

SILL9 aims to inform and nudge consumers towards food waste prevention. It affects the retail and consumption stages of the food supply chain and focuses on the development of a label for meals, recipes and meal packages to inform consumer about:

- The meal's nutritional value;
- The meal's impact on FLW and other environmental factors;
- Information on how to buy and store food responsibly.

To strengthen the effectiveness of these labels, it has been focusing on the Development of an app allowing consumers to obtain these scores for their own recipes or even for complete diets. Additionally, it promotes the development of new recipes, fresh meal packages, and semi-prepared packets of ingredients specifically developed to have a low impact on FLW and the environment and high nutri-score. The crucial challenge concerns the lack of data regarding food waste at the consumer-level, for instance at the household-level. Thus, it is important to assess what specific data are needed and which ones are being used currently. An additional challenge concerns the definition of food waste for the selection of recipes and how to balance it with other objectives (e.g., low GHG emissions, health). In fact, recipes with the lowest CO₂ emissions will not be the ones with the least amount of waste, showcasing an important area to focus on.